

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

9.1. First report on TA provision

Date of delivery - 31/10/2023

Author(s): Jerónimo Puertas (UDC), Andrea Ciambra
(UDC), Juan Naves (UDC), José Anta (UDC)

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101008626

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D9.1
Work package number	WP9
Deliverable title	1st report on TA provision
Lead beneficiary	UDC
Authors	Jerónimo Puertas Agudo (UDC), Juan Naves (UDC), José Anta (UDC), Andrea Ciambra (UDC)
Due date	31/10/2023
Actual submission date	30/10/2023
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V0.1	Juan Naves (UDC), Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	15/09/2023	First draft
V0.2	Alma Schellart (USFD), James Shucksmith (USFD), Isabel Douterelo Soler (USFD)	30/09/2023	USFD contribution to TA summaries
V0.3	Irene Scheperboer (IKT), Thomas Brüggemann	04/10/2023	IKT contribution to TA summaries
V0.4	Gislain Lipeme Kouyi	05/10/2023	INSA contribution to TA summaries
V0.5	Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG)	25/10/2023	EAWAG contribution to TA summaries

V1.0	Jerónimo Puertas Agudo (UDC), Jose Anta Álvarez (UDC), Juan Naves (UDC), Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	26/10/2023	Final working draft ready for consolidation
V1.1	Simon Tait (USFD)	27/10/2023	Final revisions and edits to working draft
V1.2	Alfredo Chavarría (EAWAG), Pierre Lechevallier (EAWAG), Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG)	30/10/2023	Final revisions to TA summaries
V2.0	Juan Naves (UDC), Andrea Ciambra (UDC), Jose Anta Álvarez (UDC), Jerónimo Puertas Agudo (UDC)	31/10/2023	Consolidated draft for submission

All information in this document only reflects the authors' view.

The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of contents

List of figures	5
List of tables.....	5
List of acronyms.....	6
Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project	7
Executive summary.....	8
1. Introduction.....	9
2. The 1 st call Transnational Access projects.....	9
2.1. UDC-01-BENS-Pena	11
2.2. UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra.....	11
2.3. UDC-03-STREET-Bellos	12
2.4. USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot.	12
2.5. USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro.	13
2.6. USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morato	14
2.7. USFD-04-BURIED-Li	14
2.8. EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares.	15
2.9. EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld	15
2.10. EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer.....	16
2.11. IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst.....	16
2.12. IKT-02-LTF-Beenen	17
2.13. INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs	17
3. TA user-group members and visiting researchers	18
4. Expected impact of the TA projects.....	20
5. Expected outcomes and dissemination of results	22
6. User-group evaluation of the TA.....	23
7. Conclusions.....	25
Annex 1. Final reports of 1 st call TA projects.....	27
Annex 2. Survey on ‘Co-UDlabs Transnational Access Programme: quality and process evaluation’	130

List of figures

Figure 1. Installation of instrumentation at Bens facility for UDC-01-BENS-Pena project (left), camera and surface velocity results (middle), and velocity profiler in egg-shaped pipe (right).	11
Figure 2. Images of RDS initial distribution over the surface (left), outflow sampling (middle) and vacuuming of remaining RDS at the end of the experiment (right) from the experimental campaign developed during UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra project.	12
Figure 3. Preparatory works and model set-up of STREET facility for UDC-03-STREET-Bellos project.	12
Figure 4. Experimental setup for the USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot project (left: image calibration procedure; right: dispersion test with model layout)	13
Figure 5. Works in the Annular flume, thermal sensors in the sediment bed and overview of the rotating annular flume.	13
Figure 6. A) Annular flume charge with sediment and water collected from the river Don (Sheffield, UK). B) Annular flume operation during treatment evaluation. C) Representative photograph of the biofilm sampling process.	14
Figure 7. Construction works and experimental set-up of BURIED facility for USF-04-BURIED-Li project.	14
Figure 8. Experimental setup of Hall facility for EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares project.	15
Figure 9. Left: Experimental setup with the heating and temperature monitoring elements, middle: scheme of sediment, sensors and water bath, right: Temperature timeseries measured during EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld project.	16
Figure 10. First results from input modelling and User Facility Group visiting the UWO facility at Fehrltorf and Eawag.	16
Figure 14. Countries of user-group leading institutions highlighted in green; countries of user-group members in blue.	19
Figure 15. Survey responses on providers/user-group communication (left) and evaluation of facility conditions and technical support in place (right)	24
Figure 16. Survey responses on post-TA assessment.	25

List of tables

Table 1. Selected proposal by the External Evaluation Panel awarded with Transnational Access.	9
Table 2. Overview and main indicators for selected TA projects in Co-UDlabs' 1st call for proposals. *Modality of access: IP, in person; PR, partially remote	10
Table 3. Data on TA projects' composition by number of users, first-time, female, academia, and non-academia users.	Error! Bookmark not defined.

List of acronyms

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning/Full text
AIR	Assessment of Inspection tools for Rising Mains
ARG	Antibiotic-resistant genes
CSNs	Combined sewer networks
CSOs	Combined sewer overflows
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPHP	Dual-probe heat-pulse
EEP	External Evaluation Panel
GANs	Generative adversarial networks
HIC	International Conference on Hydroinformatics
HMs	Heavy metals
IAHR	International Association for Hydro-Environment Engineering and Research
ICUD	International Conference on Urban Drainage
ITWH	Institut für technisch-wissenschaftliche Hydrologie GmbH
LTF	Large Test Facility
MPC	Model Predictive Control
RDS	Road-deposited sediments
SUDS	Sustainable Urban Drainage System
TA	Transnational Access
TES	Toronto Exfiltration System
UD	Urban drainage
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
WP	Work Package
YPN	Young Professional Network

Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

Executive summary

This document is Deliverable D9.1 of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101008626. The Deliverable is included in Work Package 9, "Transnational Access Provision". The lead beneficiary of the Work Package is the University of A Coruña (Universidade da Coruña, UDC). UDC is the main author of this Deliverable.

The aim of this document is to provide a report of the TA Projects developed during the first call of Co-UDlabs' Transnational Access programme, carried out from March 2022, when 13 proposals out of the 15 submissions received were eventually selected, until July 2023, the official closing date of the first call.

The 1st TA call awarded 13 proposals for 10 of the 17 Co-UDlabs available facilities. The awarded projects involved 103 users, from 19 countries and over 60 different institutions (including universities, regulators, industry, and SMEs). Only 24.3% of all user-group members were female, with gender balance among participants in the TA programme still being a substantial issue to be addressed. 44.7% of all users had a non-academic background. The Deliverable includes a short description of all 13 projects, an overview of preliminary and current results and output, as well as an analysis of potential new research agendas and working partnerships.

The 13 TA projects are expected to have a significant impact on at least four main dimensions of urban drainage studies and technical development. Several TAs have addressed – from both a more academic and a commercial point of view – key challenges that urban drainage and water management in urban contexts are facing because of rapid and underregulated urbanisation and climate change. Some of TA user groups have also used their research visits at Co-UDlabs' facilities to explore new commercial paths for the development of new technologies, instrumentation, equipment, and methods and techniques. TAs users have also worked on more effective academic-commercial partnerships, with scientific progress being coupled with improvement of innovative tools in underexplored research fields. Finally, some TAs have worked on the definition of new protocols, standards, data, and measurements that could support local regulators, policy-makers, and utilities to improve local urban drainage decision-making.

All TAs user groups have committed to work on the dissemination of their results and output. Many user-group are already at the stage of planning co-edited publications in peer-reviewed outlets, and all data derived from the TAs will be made available in open-access repositories and sources.

The Deliverable also explores the results of a self-assessment survey that was distributed to all user-group members of this TA 1st call. The results show a high degree of satisfaction with both the logistic organisation of the programme and the scientific outcome of the work performed. The surveys contain valuable information that has already been used for the improvement of certain aspects of the TA programme and have guided the facility providers in the organisation of Co-UDlabs' 2nd TA call, which closed on October 13, 2023, with 24 new proposals (a 60% increase from the first call).

1. Introduction

The key goal of Co-UDlabs is to provide an open and inclusive platform for the development of research and innovation in urban drainage and sanitation management, a field which is facing massive scientific, technological, and societal challenges due to rapid urbanization, climate change, and public health and environmental risks. The project aims to do so with three main tools: joint research activities, networking activities, and the provision of free-of-charge Transnational Access (TA) to its research infrastructure. The latter is a complex network of 17 research installations and facilities hosted by seven Co-UDlabs partners in as many European countries. By providing access to unique large-scale and complex research installations and tools to a worldwide audience of academics, businesses, utility regulators, practitioners, and local policy-makers, at no cost, Co-UDlabs aims to increase the accessibility and effectiveness of high-level, strongly innovative research for all.

Establishment and management of the TA programme is tasked to Work Package 9, led by the University of A Coruña (UDC). The TA programme officially began on October 31, 2021, when the global call for proposals was officially open. The official date for the conclusion of all TA projects from the first call was July 31, 2023.

The following Deliverable explores the key aspects of this first round of TA projects. Section 2 provides an overview of funded projects with the latest available details on progress in their implementation as well as early and consolidated results from performed experiments. Section 3 provides information on the user-groups that performed their TAs in the Co-UDlabs facilities, with an analysis of participants according to a set of useful variables. Section 4 outlines the main expected impact – both in academic and socio-economic terms – of funded TA projects, and Section 5 provides a summary of key and expected (early) results from finalised experiments. Section 6, finally, introduces the more qualitative feedback that facility providers have received directly from user-groups involved in the TA programme via the results of an official evaluation form.

2. The 1st call Transnational Access projects

Following the meeting between the Co-UDlabs' International Steering Committee and the External Evaluation Panel (EEP), tasked with performing the selection procedure for the proposals submitted to Co-UDlabs' 1st TA call, which took place on March 24, 2022, 13 TA proposals were officially selected to be carried out at 10 of the 17 available Co-UDlabs facilities. The final list of selected proposals is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Selected proposal by the External Evaluation Panel awarded with Transnational Access.

Host Co-UDlabs Institution	Facility	Awarded Proposal	Group leader institution	Country	Number of granted access days
Universidade da Coruña	BENS	Evaluation of new flow and quality monitoring devices for sewers	Photrack	Switzerland	60
Universidade da Coruña	BLOCK	Methodology to determine the potential resuspension load of heavy metals from road sediments associated with surface runoff	Francisco José de Caldas University	Colombia	60
Universidade da Coruña	STREET	Urban Flooding: Houses as reservoir (UF-HOUR)	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece	40
University of Sheffield	A/B	Pollutant Transport in Urban Floodwaters	Fluid Mechanics and Acoustics Laboratory (LMFA-INSA)	France	60

University of Sheffield	ANNULAR	Temperature time series analysis for predicting sedimentation in sewer systems	Universidade da Coruña	Spain	60
University of Sheffield	ANNULAR	Annular Flume studies to test the effect on Antibiotic Resistant Genes and Use of CRISPR- Cas in E. coli from sediments affected by sewage pollution	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Spain	60
University of Sheffield	BURIED	Hydraulic Analyses of the Toronto Exfiltration System (TES)	Toronto Metropolitan University	Canada	60
EAWAG	HALL	Non-contact assessment of TSS and COD concentrations in wastewater with hyperspectral imaging	Czech Technical University in Prague	Czech Republic	40
EAWAG	HALL	Characterization of thermal properties in drainage systems with temperature probes	Delft University of Technology	The Netherlands	40
EAWAG	UWO	A Probabilistic Machine Learning-based Framework to Improve Urban Drainage Modeling Reliability	Technical University of Kaiserslautern	Germany	20
IKT	IKT-LTF	Assessment of Inspection tools for Rising Mains (AIR)	Stichting RIONED	The Netherlands	40
IKT	IKT-LTF	Investigation of the rehabilitated wastewater pressure pipes in response to pressure surges in operation	VLARIO	Belgium	40
INSA Lyon	OTHU SuDS	In-situ SUDS modelling	Institut für technisch-wissenschaftliche Hydrologie	Germany	20

Arrangements for measurements and partially-remote experiments began in May-June 2022. On August 30-31, 2022, staff from the Institut für technisch-wissenschaftliche Hydrologie GmbH (ITWH), a research institution based in Hannover (Germany), visited the installations at the OTHU-SuDS facility of INSA Lyon. This marked the official beginning of Co-UDlabs' transnational accesses at the project's facilities.

Table 2. Overview and main indicators for selected TA projects in Co-UDlabs' 1st call for proposals.
*Modality of access: IP, in person; PR, partially remote

Provider	Facility	Expected access per project			Acronym	Modality of access *	Date of start of TA	Date of end of TA	Expected days of Access		
		Initial expected projects	Projects 1st call						Expected days of Access	Days of access provided**	Balance of access days
UDC	STREET	40	2	1	UDC-03-STREET-Bellos	IP	17/10/2022	14/12/2022	40	40	0
	BLOCK	60	2	1	UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra	IP	09/01/2023	25/04/2023	60	66	-6
	BENS	60	2	1	UDC-01-BENS-Peña	IP	11/04/2023	20/09/2023	60	71	-11
USFD	BURIED INFRASTRUCTURE	60	1	1	USFD-04-BURIED-Li	IP	28/02/2023	22/06/2023	60	65	-5
	ANNULAR	60	2	2	USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro	IP	01/06/2023	01/09/2023	60	60	0
	A/B FLUME	60	2	1	USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morato	IP	15/03/2023	15/06/2023	60	50	10
EAWAG	HALL	40	2	2	EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares	IP	15/05/2022	15/04/2023	40	36	4
					EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld	IP	01/06/2022	01/03/2023	40	40	0
	UWO	20	3	1	EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer	PR	13/03/2023	31/12/2023	20	2	18
IKT	IKT LTF	40	2	2	IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst	IP	23/03/2023	11/08/2023	40	41	-1
					IKT-02-LTF-Beenen	IP	24/04/2023	23/08/2023	40	40	0
INSA	OTHU SuDS	10	2	1	INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs	PR	30/08/2022	01/04/2023	10	3	7

All accesses were to be completed by July 31, 2023. Five accesses required additional time to carry out final measurement and analysis tasks. By the official closing day of Co-UDlabs' 2nd call for TA proposals (October 13, 2023), only one access from the first call – EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer – had not yet been completed. Table 2 provides an overview of the status of all TAs from the first call.

The following subsections introduce all TA projects performed in the framework of Co-UDlabs' first TA call, with a short overview of the scientific goals, outcome, and preliminary results and dissemination. Annex 1 includes all official reports from the user-groups of all TA performed, except for EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares and EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer, which are still either performing their access or working on data elaboration and could not provide an early working draft on their activities

2.1. UDC-01-BENS-Pena. Evaluation of new flow and quality monitoring devices for sewers.

This TA project involved two SMEs (Ubertone and Photrack) and the Polytechnical University of Cartagena (UPCT) aiming to adapt and validate new monitoring flow and quality technologies for sewers through a series of tests where the wastewater flow through two pipes with circular and egg-shaped cross-sections was characterized. The experimental campaign comprises a total of 76 tests for different discharges, slopes, and downstream boundary conditions. Depths, flows, velocities, and water quality were measured. Ubertone installed a new average velocity profiler, which has been tested and compared to other methods available in the flume facility in terms of capability, quality, and limits for realistic conditions. Photrack tested an imaging system that had originally developed in river monitoring and is being brought into operational use in sewers. This proposal also aimed to evaluate the SSC variations by surface images and acoustic backscattering. A novel spectrophotometer developed by UPCT complemented quality measurements. Preliminary results showed the high potential of tested devices in realistic but controlled conditions, and the data generated is being used to improve their performance in sewer systems.

Figure 1. Installation of instrumentation at Bens facility for UDC-01-BENS-Pena project (left), camera and surface velocity results (middle), and velocity profiler in egg-shaped pipe (right).

2.2. UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra. Methodology to determine the potential heavy metal loads washed-off by stormwater runoff from road-deposited sediments.

This TA project focused on the analysis of the potential Heavy metals (HMs) load washed-off in rainfall events from urban road deposited surface (RDS). HMs represent one of the most significant factors in the environmental pollution of water, soil, and air. HM's research in urban environments has gone into the transport and dynamics runoff direction, especially for the road-deposited sediment (RDS) present in urban areas. The project comprised the characterization of the RDS load in a real street and the assessment of HM wash-off in BLOCK facility at UDC. The assessment of HM wash-off in the physical model was performed through eight tests with deionized water for RDS loads of 0, 100, 150, and 200 g/m² and two different rainfall intensities (30 and 50 mm/h). Project results will help

public and private stakeholders for decision-making and visualize possible management scenarios of urban drainage systems in the framework of HM pollution.

Figure 2. Images of RDS initial distribution over the surface (left), outflow sampling (middle), and vacuuming of remaining RDS at the end of the experiment (right) from the experimental campaign developed during UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra project.

2.3. UDC-03-STREET-Bellos. Urban Flooding: Houses as reservoirs (UF-HOUR)

A laboratory experiment was proposed to investigate the impact of the potential storage of flooded houses acting like reservoirs in a pluvial flood hitting an idealised city. The stored flood volume, the so-called storage effect, has not been previously investigated, either numerically or experimentally. A 26.1 m² concrete platform with 25 blocks (representing buildings with basements) with detachable doors was built in STREET facility. Different scenarios for several city configurations were implemented as the distorted physical model will allow various rainfall-runoff intensities and adjustment of the flood volume stored in buildings. Flood characteristics such as water depths, velocities and hydrographs have been measured during the experiments. The results suggest that the storage effect of the houses has a significant impact on the overall flood characteristics in densely urbanized areas, suggesting that further consideration should be given to include the storage effect in urban flood modelling.

Figure 3. Preparatory works and model set-up of STREET facility for UDC-03-STREET-Bellos project.

2.4. USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot. Pollutant Transport in Urban Floodwaters

This transnational access involves a series of laboratory experiments to investigate the spreading and transport of soluble material from a surcharging manhole within urban floodwater in the Above/Below Ground Flume facility at UFSD. Initial tests involved the assessment of several different experimental techniques for the 2D characterization of solute plumes in the laboratory. This included the use of intrusive conductivity probes to measure saline concentrations at points in the plume, the injection of hot water into the surcharging flow and the non-contact characterization of the plume using a thermal camera, as well as the use of a colorimetry technique based on the injection of a soluble dye. Further tests were then conducted following the installation of different model streets/urban layouts. These tests collected datasets describing 2D solute transport under different experimental

scenarios and hydraulic conditions. Open access datasets will be used by the urban drainage modelling community for the development and validation of numerical modelling tools which aim to develop tools able to characterize the spread of water borne contamination in shallow urban floods.

Figure 4. Experimental setup for the USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot project (left: image calibration procedure; right: dispersion test with model layout)

2.5. USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro. Temperature time series analysis for predicting sedimentation in sewer systems

Sediment accumulation in sewers is a major concern in many urban drainage systems as it causes the loss of hydraulic capacity, can generate hazardous gases, and increases the risk of blockages which can result in localised flooding in urban areas. There is currently no methodology available to continuously monitor this process. The main objective of this study is to develop a novel methodology to analyse temperature oscillations and predict sedimentation processes under different flow conditions, by utilising thermal probes in the temperature controlled annular flume at UFSD. In total, 18 tests have been carried out, with 3 different sediment thicknesses, two different water temperature gradients, and 3 different velocities.

Figure 5. Works in the Annular flume, thermal sensors in the sediment bed and overview of the rotating annular flume. (left to right: installing sediment, installing temperature sensors, view of temperature sensor array, flume operating in temperature control mode, with sediment bed and temperature sensors installed)

The results clearly indicate that the temperature sensors can pick-up different delays between temperature gradient in the sediment and the overlying water phase, clearly distinguishing the different depths of sediment. The novel methodology thus has a high potential for scientific relevance and operational application in terms of planning and implementing urban drainage maintenance strategies. The practitioners involved in this proposal can use the findings to justify investment in the development of instrumentation strategies able to be deployed in real environments to monitor sedimentation processes.

2.6. USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morato. Annular Flume studies to test the effect on Antibiotic Resistant Genes and Use of CRISPR- Cas in *E. coli* from sediments affected by wastewater pollution.

Assessment of antibiotic resistant bacteria in water and sediment samples is essential to determine the persistence of potentially hazardous pathogens in aquatic ecosystems. In addition, the implementation of control measurements and biotechnological approaches to reduce the impact and environmental persistence of both antibiotics and resistant pathogens is necessary to improve water quality in receiving water bodies. The aim of this study was to evaluate the role of microbial biofilms attached to sediments in riverbeds that are affected by wastewater discharges. The exchange of antibiotic resistance between sediment-based biofilms and river water was investigated using the annular flume facility at USFD. The experiments allowed for the study of the dissemination of antibiotic-resistant genes (ARG) in rivers and the use of the CRISPRCas9, a genome editing technology, as a potential mitigation method in *E. coli*.

Figure 6. A) Annular flume charge with sediment and water collected from the river Don (Sheffield, UK). B) Annular flume operation during treatment evaluation. C) Representative photograph of the biofilm sampling process.

2.7. USFD-04-BURIED-Li. Evaluation of the Toronto Exfiltration System.

A hybrid SUDS termed the Toronto Exfiltration System (TES), which utilizes the pore space of the excavated trench for storm sewers and coupled with the traditional pipe drainage, was tested at full scale in the Buried Test Cell at USFD. Two series of experiments seek to collect high quality flow and infiltration data to facilitate the widespread application of TES by optimizing the design and maintenance requirements and address sandy and non-sandy surrounding soil conditions. Experienced and early career researchers from Canada, China and Germany contributed to the experimental work and collected full-scaled, steady, and unsteady hydraulic and sediment accumulation data with clay and sandy surrounding soils.

Figure 7. Construction works and experimental set-up of BURIED facility for USF-04-BURIED-Li project. (Left to right: installation of full-scale TES in “clay” bed, entry manholes, instrumented system water level monitors in manhole, perforated pipe and surrounding soil, entry manhole with water level and ADV velocity monitors)

Preliminary analysis indicates that a TES with sandy surrounding soil efficiently retained runoff under the steady and unsteady design rainfall conditions. A TES with clay surrounding soil retained runoff up to a design storage capacity under the steady and unsteady design conditions. In both cases, a tangible amount of inflow runoff sediments remained within the TES' perforated pipes under the typical 1-hr inflow hydrograph.

2.8. EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares. Non-contact assessment of turbidity and COD concentrations in wastewater with hyperspectral imaging.

The use of non-contact spectrophotometric techniques, such as hyperspectral imaging, is investigated for the measurement of the chemical composition of wastewater-derived pollution. Based on previous laboratory tests, which demonstrated the potential of this imaging technique for the specific application, a monitoring campaign was designed to generate an extensive dataset of hyperspectral images, absorbance spectra and reference measurements including online turbidity measurement and laboratory analysis of 5 key pollution variables (concentration of: dissolved organic carbon, total dissolved nitrogen, ammonium, phosphate and sulfates). After a period of 4-months testing in early 2023 to optimize the sensor installation, the flume experiments started and will run until mid-October 2023. As of late September 2023, the TA had collected 460 (TA goal = 50) laboratory references during different daytimes, and during dry and wet days. While finishing the data collection, our efforts are now towards data analysis and comparison of sensor and reference data. Preliminary analysis reveals that the hyperspectral imaging sensors is particularly suited for the measurement of turbidity and organic nitrogen, but further analysis is required to assess fully the other parameters studied.

Figure 8. Experimental setup of Hall facility for EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares project. Left: overview of the flume with the black tarpaulin to block out light for the optical measurements, Middle: flume in and out of operation, Right: backside of the flume, autosampler for reference measurements and member G.Gruber during a visit (TU Graz).

2.9. EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld

The presence of sediments in urban drainage systems has a significant impact on their functionality. Monitoring sediment accumulation can offer valuable insights into sediment transport dynamics and system performance. This project tested an innovative solution for measuring sediment depths in sewer systems through temperature monitoring. The methodology involves analyzing temperature time series during dry weather flow conditions to identify harmonic patterns between wastewater and sediment-bed temperatures. The project also focuses on characterizing the thermal properties of sediments, which are crucial for understanding heat transfer processes. For this purpose, a dual-probe heat-pulse (DPHP) system and a commercial sensor were used to accurately measure sediment thermal properties. To validate the temperature monitoring system, laboratory-scale experiments were performed. Results proved the relationship between the sediment depth and thermal properties and the attenuation of the temperature time series. As a main output, this temperature-based system may contribute to the optimization of sewer system operation and cleaning strategies by providing reliable information on sediment depths and properties.

Figure 9. Left: Experimental setup with the heating and temperature monitoring elements, middle: scheme of sediment, sensors and water bath, right: Temperature timeseries measured during EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld project.

2.10. EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer

One of the primary challenges associated with combined urban drainage systems (UDSs) is the occurrence of combined sewer overflows (CSOs). It is important to optimize the operation of existing combined sewer networks (CSNs) to minimize the frequency and volume of CSOs. In this TA project, these issues are tackled through the implementation of cutting-edge deep learning techniques, such as generative adversarial networks (GANs). GANs have garnered considerable attention in machine learning over the past decade for their distinctive approach, involving learning from a set of training data and generating synthetic data that mimics the characteristics of the training data. In a visit to the UWO facility, the group has been doing a reality check with a field visit, which helped to revise fundamental assumptions of the rainfall runoff processes. They have mainly been working on “Step 1” of their framework, which involves pre-processing tasks like handling missing data, detecting anomalies, and monitoring data drift. Also, progress has been made to discuss concepts applied in “Step 2”, which includes employing GANs, surrogate models, and both lumped and physically-based models of CSOs and urban flooding. In Step 3, post-processing activities involve the utilization of high-resolution weather prediction data provided by the partner Oceans Research Co (Figure 10). The accuracy of these predictions is currently under evaluation. If successful, this framework has the potential to also facilitate Model Predictive Control (MPC) by adjusting discharges of flow limiters in real time and implementing intelligent green-blue infrastructure to reduce CSOs.

Figure 10. First results from input modelling and User Facility Group visiting the UWO facility at Fehraltorf and Eawag.

2.11. IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst

This project investigated for the first time the extent to which pressure surge loads can have an influence on a pipeline rehabilitated using a liner. A tailored experimental setup was used in IKT’s Large Test Facility (LTF) consisting of a wastewater pressure circuit system. A defined section with a length of 8 meters was rehabilitated with a so called close-fit-liner (polyethylene of high density), the system was subjected to a range pressure surge

loads that can occur in wastewater pressure pipes. The liner survived all tests without damage and the results were compared with those of a common simulation programme, which could be approximately adapted to the tests. However, the results of the investigation also showed that any errors and deviations that occurred were due to factors that should be considered such as the determination of the actual pressure wave velocity in the system and the real valve characteristic curve, proportions of degassed air in the negative pressure area or transient friction approaches. These potential influencing factors need to be identified in detail in further investigations.

Figure 11. Test setup and User Facility Group visiting the facility.

2.12. IKT-02-LTF-Beenen

In recent years, some new and innovative promising inspection techniques have been further developed. Within the framework of this TA project, selected innovative inspection techniques have been examined in a test set-up for their performance and application limits. Two pilot products in an early research stage from academic institutions and three commercial solutions from Acquaint, Rosen Group and Xylem were tested in a test setup constructed in the large-scale test facility of IKT. It consisted of a system of wastewater pumps and pressure pipes, with typical damage patterns to be detected by the inspection techniques. Steel and PVC pipe segments were installed in sections of the test setup to determine their influence on the different inspection techniques. The project showed that the newly developed sensors of the academic institutions are promising techniques for use in wastewater pipeline inspections, although are currently not very robust and stable and need further development. The commercial parties were able to detect a variety of defects in the experimental pipeline environment and showed their added value in strategic asset management of pressure sewer networks.

Figure 12. Pipebots air-coupled Ultrasonic device (University of Bristol), Acquarius Acquaint and SmartBall Xylem

2.13. INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs

An experimental campaign was conducted in OTHU SUDS facility located at INSA in order to improve hydraulic and hydrological models of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS). The facility was equipped with a flowmeter at the outlet and soil moisture sensors installed at different depths. A bespoke device for the irrigation of the swale was developed in the TA to simulate runoff water linked to rainfall of different return periods. The inflow and soil

moisture were measured over a week. The objective is to use these data to improve the capacity of the models to simulate the evolution of the volumetric water content in the soils of SUDS when extreme events occur. This type of events are likely to become more frequent due to climate change. The Horton model, water balance equation and various empirical functions (power and sigmoid functions) were tested to represent the variation of soil moisture. Results show that Horton model demonstrated the capacity to simulate the storage change in the swale (using the averaged values of performed measurements). The sigmoid function seems better than the power law to capture the variation of the soil moisture according to the depth in the soil.

Figure 13. Swale general view and original supplying system to wet the facility.

3. TA user-group members and visiting researchers

One of the key goals of the TA programme within the Co-UDlabs project was to make the 17-facility research infrastructure not just available, but accessible to the largest possible number of researchers and practitioners. The call was designed to make transnational accesses a viable opportunity for the worldwide urban drainage community, and this implied that – even at the early project design stage – the TA programme aimed to engage as many users as possible from the most diverse backgrounds available. Accordingly, the Grant Agreement already set a baseline of minimum granted access days (645 days across all installations) for the whole TA programme over the project’s lifetime, and an estimated number of expected TA projects (29 overall) and involved TA users (141 overall). The projects from the 1st TA call alone already accounted for 416 access days granted to visiting user-groups, with 103 users (73% of baseline) from 19 different countries involved (see Figure 14 and Table 3 below).

71% of all users were from institutions based in EU countries or associated countries. 51 users have recorded attendance in the facilities’ logbooks for TA activities – that is, have physically participated in tasks performed at the installations. In terms of diversity of the user-group membership for the TA programme, key insights can be drawn about the role of academic and non-academic institutions, gender equality, and the attractiveness of the programme for junior scientists and other participants at an early stage of their professional trajectories.

24.3% of user-group members were female. While this data can arguably be considered consistent with the overall composition of researcher and practitioner communities in urban drainage, it still exposes a glaring problem within this sector, with an imbalance of opportunity and participation across genders. This topic has been systematically addressed by Co-UDlabs’ Steering Committee, especially in dialogue with the office of Co-UDlabs’ Project Advisor and with a particular regard to the possibility to target this imbalance explicitly when planning the project’s activities and audience. a slightly higher percentage of the users that eventually physically visited the facilities for research tasks during the TAs (27.5%) were female. Proposals submitted to the 2nd TA call show, however, an upward trend (31.1% of all users are female).

Figure 14. Countries of user-group leading institutions highlighted in green; countries of user-group members in blue.

44.7% of all users had a non-academic background or were associated to non-academic institutions such as companies, utilities, public regulators, or public administrations. This was an extremely encouraging figure in terms of Co-UDlabs' ability to engage the urban drainage community outside academia, making the research infrastructure attractive also for businesses and stakeholders from the industry – who managed to see the potential that an openly-accessible and shared network of large-scale facilities can have on making design and production more efficient, sustainable, and technologically innovative.

Only 21% of users with an academic profile, however, were in the process of obtaining their PhD, Masters', or another academic qualification. This raises an issue of communicating better about Co-UDlabs' opportunities and the uniqueness of its research infrastructure to early-stage researchers and students. In various occasions, the Steering Committee has agreed to improve outreach with the student community in urban drainage – especially through increased cooperation with large and transversal organisations such as the IAHR's Young Professional Network (YPN) sections across the world – since this specific pool of potential participants can (on average) be more available for longer or more intensive visits at the facilities, and the availability of a 17-facility Europe-wide network of installations can provide a unique contribution and added value to the research this community may be developing.

Building also on recommendations and guidance provided by the office of the Project Advisor assigned to Co-UDlabs the project's Steering Committee agreed unanimously to seek more diversity in the 2nd TA call in terms of user-group and individual members' diversity. More specifically, besides a general commitment to expand the range of visitors' countries involved in Co-UDlabs, it was agreed to make additional efforts to engage stakeholders, researchers, public regulators, and industry from Eastern and Southern European countries – whose participation was very limited in the first call – as components of an urban drainage community with potential synergies with the rest of Europe.

Table 3. Data on TA projects' composition by number of users, first-time, female, academia, and non-academia users.

FACILITY	PROPOSAL TITLE	Group leader institution	Total Users*	First-time users	FTU %	Female users	Female users %	PhD (or lower) users	PhD (or lower) users %	Academia users	Academia users %	Non-academia users	Non-academia users %
A/B	Pollutant Transport in Urban Floodwaters	LMFA-INSA	16	13	81.3%	1	6.3%	2	12.5%	12	75.0%	4	25.0%
ANNULAR	Temperature time series analysis for predicting sedimentation in sewer systems	UDC	6	6	100.0%	4	66.7%	0	0.0%	4	66.7%	2	33.3%
ANNULAR	Annular Flume studies to test the effect on Antibiotic Resistant Genes and Use of CRISPR- Cas in <i>E. coli</i> from sediments affected by sewage pollution	UPC	3	3	100.0%	1	33.3%	0	0.0%	3	100.0%	0	0.0%
BENS	Evaluation of new flow and quality monitoring devices for sewers	Photrack	7	5	71.4%	1	14.3%	1	14.3%	3	42.9%	4	57.1%
BLOCK	Methodology to determine the potential resuspension load of heavy metals from road sediments associated with surface runoff	Fº J. De Caldas University	6	6	100.0%	2	33.3%	1	16.7%	2	33.3%	4	66.7%
BURIED	Hydraulic Analyses of the Toronto Exfiltration System (TES)	Toronto Metropolitan University	7	7	100.0%	2	28.6%	0	0.0%	4	57.1%	3	42.9%
HALL	Non-contact assessment of TSS and COD concentrations in wastewater with hyperspectral imaging	CTU Prague	5	5	100.0%	1	20.0%	0	0.0%	2	40.0%	3	60.0%
HALL	Characterization of thermal properties in drainage systems with temperature probes	TU Delft	6	6	100.0%	4	66.7%	0	0.0%	4	66.7%	2	33.3%
IKT-LTF	Assessment of Inspection tools for Rising Mains (AIR)	RIONED	20	19	95.0%	5	25.0%	2	10.0%	5	25.0%	15	75.0%
IKT-LTF	Investigation of the rehabilitated waste water pressure pipes in response to pressure surges in operation	VLARIO	6	3	50.0%	1	16.7%	0	0.0%	1	16.7%	5	83.3%
OTHU	In-situ SUDS modelling	ITWH	7	7	100.0%	2	28.6%	2	28.6%	4	57.1%	3	42.9%
STREET	Urban Flooding: Houses as reservoir (UF-HOUR)	DUTH	6	6	100.0%	1	16.7%	2	33.3%	6	100.0%	0	0.0%
UWO	A Probabilistic Machine Learning-based Framework to Improve Urban Drainage Modeling Reliability	TU Kaiserslautern	8	8	100.0%	0	0.0%	2	25.0%	7	87.5%	1	12.5%
			103	94	91.3%	25	24.3%	12	11.7%	57	55.3%	46	44.7%

4. Expected impact of the TA projects

The establishment of a Europe-wide network of large-scale research infrastructure was an essential part of Co-UDlabs' expected impact. On the one hand, there is an impact on the improvement of Europe's overall research infrastructure in politically sensitive areas such as urban drainage, water resource management, and sustainable urbanization. The project itself and the TA programme calls, in particular show that there is an existing and growing demand for:

- the opportunity to test knowledge and innovation in large-scale or full-size installations that allow the analyst to approach specific urban drainage phenomena with otherwise unavailable precision, reliability, and comparability and with an almost seamless reproduction of real-life and natural conditions in a laboratory environment;
- a sustainable network of collaborating institutions in which resources and capacities are pooled together for an impact that transcends the academic impact of dissemination and results and leads to broader societal impact in the improvement of urban infrastructure, public policy, and the overall quality of life connected to a better use and conservation of water resources in a community and territory.

On the other hand, the establishment of such a network would expand the need for more partnerships based on shared infrastructure, minimising the costs of accessing otherwise unavailable facilities, instrumentation, techniques, and practical know-how. For these reasons, part of the communication effort of the Co-UDlabs project

has been targeting early-career scientists and industrial researchers, in an attempt to widen the opportunities available to this growing audience of junior academics, practitioners, and even developers and technicians in private businesses or local administrations and regulators. The linkages made in the CoUD_Labs TA projects have the potential to develop into long last personal and scientific collaborations so strengthening the research efforts in this area for many years to come.

The TA programme's impact on research and science, in terms of available output and overall excellence of academic and technological innovation, and on the creation of shared research agendas has led, over the implementation of the programme's first call, to key tangible impacts on the facility providers, the user-groups that accessed the installations, and the urban drainage community at large:

- Innovative, testable, and replicable tools to allow water utilities to face the key challenges facing urban drainage systems such as urbanisation, climate change, and unsustainable activities;
- Commercial and technological development for products, instruments, machinery, and technologies that are either available and need further evidence to validate their performance or are on their way to become accessible to worldwide markets;
- An efficient hybrid of academic advancement and commercial or market-oriented collaborations among diverse stakeholders with shared co-responsibility and benefits from working together in unique partnerships and on groundbreaking topics and applications;

All TAs performed through the first call have planned for and achieved relevant contributions to one or more of these impacts. Experiments such as **USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot** and **USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morato**, both performed at facilities of the University of Sheffield, made significant progress in key processes associated with pollutant dispersion within flood water and the release of microbial pathogens in aquatic environments respectively, with a clear link between the opportunity of working at these facilities and advancing urban drainage's focus on public health impact and community-wide risks.

Exploration of innovative commercial paths was also at the core of several TA projects in this first round of the programme. The work at **INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs** allowed user-group leaders at ITWH Hannover to re-think the company's commercial and market planning on the specific products and sensors that were being tested. Preliminary results of the **IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst** TA show that some of the conclusions may significantly alter current parameters in the lining processes for wastewater pressure pipes, to the extent that these developments may exert, in the near future, sufficient market pressures on companies that they may be incentivised to adapt and upgrade their production processes. Work at **EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares** provided early evidence of the potential of using hyperspectral imaging for non-contact wastewater quality monitoring.¹ The work performed at **EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld** and **USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro** was promising in opening new research avenues on sediment accumulation monitoring as a complement to hydrodynamic measurements for accurate sediment transport models in sewer systems, but at the same time it also opened a window of opportunity for improved sewer system designs at the policy level and the development of digital twin for larger socio-economic impact on the sector.

¹ The outcome of the TA is an industrial Research and Development project, PollutionKeeper. This proposal is now actively progressing towards the development of hardware solutions tailored to non-contact monitoring of wastewater treatment plant inflows to address the critical needs in this domain. More information available online: <http://www.photrack.ch/pollutionkeeper.html>.

This is also an example of the extent to which the TA proposals of the first call have followed a specifically innovative path in between scientific and academic advancement and the establishment of enabling environments for further commercial competitiveness and the streamlining of marketable technology and products. Staff in the **UDC-03-STREET-Bellos** TA were particularly confident of the wide-spectrum impact that fully open-access data from the experiments could have not only on additional research on this aspect of urban drainage linked to urban flooding, but also in the interest that this could elicit from water utilities, public regulators, and water companies involved in the management of urban flood risk.

Impact on public decision-making, the design of better, safer, and more sustainable urban and human settlements was also at the core, finally, of most TAs performed in the programme. Work at **IKT-02-LTF-Beenen** catered also to the interests of water regulators, utilities, and local policymakers in an attempt to make pipe and sewer inspection techniques more reliable and, in turn, ensure that investments in these assets better informed. The outcomes of **IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst** have knowledge that could affect the daily work of service and utility providers at the local level – for instance with pressure surges in terms of validated calculations and quality monitoring and assurance approaches. The effect of this information could influence tendering of maintenance and rehabilitation activities of urban drainage systems, or even improve and adapt the manufacturing and market availability of re-lining products. This project provides additional evidence of the innovative middle ground between academic knowledge and practical applications in which some of the first call TAs have worked and planned.

5. Expected outcomes and dissemination of results

The main goal of Co-UDlabs' TA programme is to make its research infrastructure available to the largest public possible, granting an opportunity to research, technical, and policy teams to access a facility, a technology, or a laboratory that would otherwise be unavailable for their work. While granting physical access to a user-group is the key element of this process, there is also a very relevant component in the ability to adequately disseminate and circulate the main data, information, knowledge, and results that will be obtained throughout the TA programme as a whole.

For this reason, the consortium has agreed on a set of ambitious performance indicators. As stated in the project's Grant Agreement, Co-UDlabs expects to be acknowledged in at least 15 journal papers and 30 open-access datasets, directly linked to work performed and results obtained through the transnational accesses at Co-UDlabs facilities.

Each TA project has developed a diverse array of dissemination opportunities, ideas, and potential tools. Scientific publications and participation in conferences and other international events are the key goals for most user-groups. Preliminary outcomes of **UDC-03-STREET-Bellos**, for instance, were presented at a poster session of Novatech 2023, an international conference organised by Co-UDlabs partner GRAIE in July 2023, with over 500 attendees, where it earned a special prize as the most voted early-stage researcher project. Some TAs also plan to disseminate results and knowledge in specific communities – especially among practitioners, business consortia, and local regulators.

User-group members at **IKT-02-LTF-Beenen**, for instance, were involved in dissemination activities *while* the access was being performed, which involved many members of IKT's long-standing network, collaborators, and community. Some of these very being actively included in the project, identifying the main damage scenarios that should be applied to the test set-up. Reports on these activities will be available in English and Dutch, and outcomes of the TA will be disseminated at various internal events of user-group member RIONED. Facility providers and user-

group members have also already planned scientific publications linked to the access' results: Joanna Watts (University of Sheffield) and Alex Towlson (University of Bristol) will be the key coordinators of this task.

In the **USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot** TA, the user-group is working on a journal publication – coordinated by James Shucksmith (University of Sheffield) and Emmanuel Mignot (INSA) – which will be based on open access datasets obtained in the TA and the comparison of measurement techniques. Industrial partners are also working on complementary modeling work on the TA datasets, which will be disseminated via both academic and commercial routes.

Several TAs have planned to present their results and scientific output at conferences and events of international relevance in the field of urban drainage and water and sanitation. Some user-groups (**UDC-03-STREET-Bellos**, **INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs**, **EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld**) were able to show results of their work already at Novatech 2023, an international conference on water (and the location of the 2nd Co-UDlabs General Assembly) co-organised by GRAIE, a partner of the Co-UDlabs consortium, in early July 2023. Other relevant venues in which TA work and results have been presented include the 12th European Water Resources Association Congress (**UDC-03-STREET-Bellos**) in June-July 2023. Researchers involved in **USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morató** plan to disseminate results through specific activities developed in collaboration between the UNESCO Chair on Sustainability at the Polytechnical University of Catalonia (UPC) and the University of Sheffield. The team of **USDF-04-BURIED-Li** plans to be presenting TA results at, at least, one major international conference (either ICUD, IAHR, or HIC) in 2024. Finally, the TA group of **IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst** plans to have several publications based on TA results under the coordination of VLARIO/Aquafin, and a series of lectures and training activities to be held at the University of Leuven.

6. User-group evaluation of the TA

Part of Co-UDlabs' reporting effort on the actual performance of the selected TA projects in its infrastructure was based on polling participating user-groups about their overall experience with the TA programme and their facility of choice. UDC as WP9 leader set up an online survey which was immediately distributed to all the active members of a user-group upon completion of their TA (see Annex 2 for the template of the survey). At the time of drafting of this report, the survey had collected 20 replies from personnel involved in 10 of the 13 TAs.² The survey's N of respondents was lower than expected and betrays a difficulty for facility providers to obtain feedback from user-groups after the TAs reliably. While the information obtained through the survey has been very valuable, the consortium has committed to improve post-TA communication with participants. This should lead not only to better feedback on the functioning of the TA programme, but also to more opportunities for additional scientific collaboration even once the TA programme has been completed.

The survey was divided into three sections: one on the process *before* the TA visit (call rules, application procedure, requirements, communication with facility providers); one on the performance of the TAs at the research infrastructure; and one on the process *after* the TA, with questions about the effectiveness of the programme and the expected output (data management, publications, new applications, etc.).

² No responses were provided by the user-groups of EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares and IKT-01-LTF-Velhurst. EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer was still in progress at the time of submission of this Deliverable and the survey had not been distributed to the user-group members yet.

For the process before the actual performance of the TA, participants were asked for details about the main sources of information on the TA call and the opportunity to access the Co-UDlabs research infrastructure free of charge. Most replies identify fellow academic contacts in the participants' networks or their home institutions as the main sources of information. This kind of data has been relevant for Co-UDlabs members also in the organisation of the 2nd TA call, as consortium members used alternative channels of information such as conferences, international events, and training activities as vehicles to extend the reach of the 2nd call to a wider community and therefore expand the potential pool of participants in new TAs.

A significant majority of users declared to have participated for research-related goals (64%), while accessing the Co-UDlabs infrastructure and community was also an incentive to apply (32%). A vast majority of the participants (95%) agreed that the information about the TA call provided by Co-UDlabs through its website and social media was adequate and useful to take advantage of the opportunity. The 1st TA call opened on October 31, 2021, and closed on January 31, 2022. Applicants were given three months for the preparation of their proposals. The official results of the evaluation were published on March 15, 2022. Participants were satisfied with the amount of time available to draft their applications (4.11 rating out of 5.0), and 70% of respondents thought that six weeks between closure and evaluation results was a fair amount of time in terms of logistical arrangements and planning. Finally, participants highly regarded (4.65/5.0) the availability of facility providers and the support they delivered during the application phase. The Data Management Plan (DMP) – a requirement of all TA projects to guarantee that all methods, techniques, and formats for data collection are openly available and that project activities will follow the European FAIR standard, i.e., making data and metadata findable, openly accessible, interoperable, and re-usable – was a more technical and demanding task for most TA users, which rated the process less favourably than other aspects of their research stays (4.05/5.0). Figure 15 visualises feedback on communication between facility providers and user-group, as well as the assessment of quality of TA facilities and technical supported provided by facility staff.

Figure 15. Survey responses on providers/user-group communication (left) and evaluation of facility conditions and technical support in place (right)

In the framework of the TA programme, host institutions were required to provide all technical support necessary to improve or adapt the facilities for the performance of the TA experiments, as well as all logistical support, accommodation, and a reimbursement of daily allowances for all visiting staff that accessed the infrastructure. Generally, the opinion of user-groups on hospitality, technical assistance, and guidance in the undertaking of experiments and the organisation of output was extremely high. Accommodation and logistical support were rated 4.55/5.0, whereas the overall quality of installations reached 4.65/5.0. It was scientific and technical support to the visiting teams, however, that was rated the highest (4.9/5.0).

The survey also wanted to find out about the researchers' opinion of the process after the TA, including an assessment of the work performed and the opportunity for follow-up in terms of publications, disseminations, and further collaboration and partnership within the Co-UDlabs community. Figure 16 below shows this information more visually. Assessment was highly positive. 85% of respondents stated that the TA project they participated in was ultimately successful. The remaining 15% was unsure because more information on data and results was needed. All respondents stated that their projects had managed to produce new data and make it available with open access. 90% of respondents affirmed that they planned to publish academically the results of the research they had conducted at Co-UDlabs facilities.

Figure 16. Survey responses on post-TA assessment.

The survey was a key resource in the re-assessment of the TA call procedures. It has provided useful insight on how the logistics, hospitality, support, and the research purpose of the programme are perceived by the participants. Recommendations on the management of data, the relationship with facility providers, and the availability of information for academic outreach have been clear and will be of guidance for the improvement of the TA experience overall. One of the survey's final questions highlighted that 75% of respondents would consider re-applying for another Co-UDlabs TA call: 23 users participating in proposals submitted to the 2nd TA call – 14.4% of total users – had been involved in a TA project from the first call.

7. Conclusions

There are several metrics (both quantifiable and not) that show that the first Co-UDlabs call for Transnational Access was successful in achieving its expected outcomes and results. In quantitative terms, the call was successful in that it managed to mobilise the involvement and participation of 100 users from nearly 20 different countries and over 60 institutions between universities, research centres, small and medium enterprises, technology companies,

utilities, industry representatives, and public regulators. In more qualitative terms, surveys among TA participants show that the response to this research opportunity has been very positive, with hospitality, result expectations, cooperation and technical support by facility providers, and dissemination and commercialisation prospects all highly graded across the 13 performed TA experiments and studies.

Participation in the TA programme exceeded the initial expectations, with over 63% of the baseline expected TA users (for the whole project's lifetime) already achieved with the first TA call projects alone. High participation in the TA programme also implied a remarkable and valuable degree of interdisciplinary diversity, with user-groups often building on mixed academic-business partnerships and a significant juxtaposition of both early-stage and more senior research profiles within the groups.

The data is also consistent with a very valuable impact of the TA programme on the establishment of a more specific 'hybrid' of academic long-term progress and planning for the advancement and refinement of urban drainage knowledge and experimental expertise, alongside more market-oriented progress in the development and improvement of commercially valuable techniques, methods, technologies, instrumentation, and new standards.

The assessment performed for this deliverable has also been an essential exercise of self-evaluation and has identified the TA programme's current strengths and those elements that can be improved via better collaboration, dialogue, and strategic planning. Some of the outcomes of this process – e.g., a stronger focus on gender-equality engagement, outstanding ideas, and progress in specific regions such as Central-Eastern Europe, and improved cooperation with industry and utilities – have been used to streamline and improve the TA offer for the 2nd call (officially closed on October 31, 2023, with new TAs set to begin in early 2024).

The positive outcomes of the TA programme so far, have also shown the intangible added value of the Co-UDlabs research infrastructure in that researchers and technology developers have been able to work collaboratively and learn from a much larger community and network of partners and collaborators. This has generated new ideas, provided stimuli to individuals and organisations, and clarified their research needs. The practice of collaborative research has also required more efficient mechanisms of cooperation *within* the Co-UDlabs consortium. These efforts have had positive and long-lasting spill-over effects on the way the Co-UDlabs facilities and institutions are able to work internally and cooperate with partners. These impacts should enable more impactful research, and the faster development of innovation in the EU and international urban drainage and water and resource management sectors.

Annex 1. Final reports of 1st call TA projects

TA reports from individual projects at Co-UDlabs facilities are added to this Annex in the same format they were submitted by the user-groups. Some of the reports build on provisional data analysis and will be updated at a later stage, once more refined data and information is available. Some of the reports are attached in an early provisional form since, at the time of finalisation of this deliverable, user-group members still had time available to revise their reports before the 90-day deadline after the end of their TAs.

Reports from EAWAG-01-HALL-Bares and EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer could not be attached since the user-groups are still either performing their access or working on data elaboration and thus could not provide an early working draft on their activities.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Evaluation of new flow and quality
monitoring devices for sewers
UDC-01-BENS-Pena.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	Co-UDLabs_TA-BENS-PENA
TA project title	Evaluation of new flow and quality monitoring devices for sewers
TA project theme	Testing and assessment of sensors for sewer monitoring
Facility provider	Universidade da Coruña
Facility	BENS
TA period	17/04/2023 – 20/09/2023
Days of access:	71 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Salvador Peña Haro	Photrack	CTO	SME	No	Switzerland	M	5
Marie BURCKBUCHLER	Ubertone	CEO, R&D engineer	SME	Yes	France	F	8
Stéphane FISCHER	Ubertone	R&D director, founder	SME	No	France	M	8
Antoine KUHN	Ubertone	Engineer student	SME	Yes	France	M	16
Juan García Bermejo	UPCT	Lecturer	Academia	No	Spain	M	2

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

Operation and planning of sewer networks and wastewater treatment plants, as well as the fulfilment of legal obligations require knowing the volumetric flow and pollutant loads. Standard methods for flow measurements include the average velocity measurement with acoustic sensors, the so-called Dopplers, which have limitations in low flow conditions and need to be in contact with the fluid. The objective of this project is to adapt and validate new monitoring flow and quality technologies for sewers. Regarding the flow, Ubertone developed and commercializes an average velocity sensor, the UB-Flow AV, which has already been proven to give better data quality than Dopplers on the market, especially in low charge and low depth conditions. Ubertone would like to test and compare a new profiler in terms of capability, quality and limits, with the other methods available in the flume facility. From a different perspective, devices in contact with the medium may be victim of the harsh medium environment inside sewers, thus non-contact measurement methods can be of advantage. Photrack has developed image-based systems for flow monitoring which have been tested and successfully implemented in river monitoring, however they have not yet been brought into operational use in sewers. Further, regarding water quality, images of the surface of the water could also offer appreciable correlation with Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC). This proposal also aims to evaluate the SSC variations by surface images from Photrack with the aid of optical turbidity, acoustic backscattering from Ubertone, spectroscopy measurements from UPCT.

Keywords | Sewer monitoring, Non-contact monitoring, Spectroscopy, Velocity profiler.

Material and methods

BENS facility:

The BENS flume test facility consists of a 10 m long and 0.9 m width bench for studying sewer processes using real wastewater from the pre-treatment system of A Coruña WWTP. A conventional circular PVC pipe (inner diameter of 300 mm) and an egg-shaped cross section pipe (385 mm high, top radius of 110 mm and a bottom radius of 55 mm) were available in parallel. Wastewater was pumped with a submersible sludge pump from post-sieving system of the WWTP (3 mm aperture) towards a head tank placed before the entrance into the pipes. Wastewater can also be obtained from pre-sieving tank by gravity. Both inflows were regulated by a set of valves and an ultrasonic flowmeter. Then, wastewater was incorporated into both pipes through two equal triangular weirs. The slope of the metallic bench and thus of the pipes can be set from 0 to 2%. Two top apertures of 0.9 m and two holes were opened along each pipe to allow the installation of equipment and monitoring of water depths. Both pipes drain the wastewater into a common reception chamber equipped with an automatic tailgate used to set different downstream boundary depth conditions during the experiments. Figure 1 shows a general view of the BENS facility including the position of each monitoring device.

*Depth_upstream includes flow from lever over triangular weirs

Figure 1: BENS flumes and sensors scheme.

Sensors of the facility:

The sensors from the facility provider installed at the facility were:

Depth: Eight UB500-18GM75-I-V15 (Pepperl and Fuchs, Germany) ultrasound distance sensors were installed in the facility for water height and flow rate measurements. First, a sensor was placed in the inlet chamber to register the height of the water over two equal triangular weirs that drain the same amount of water into the two pipes. Three sensors were then installed along each pipe to characterize water depths in the positions shown in Figure 1. Finally, a last depth sensor was placed at the downstream chamber to register the downstream boundary condition imposed by the gate. The flow discharge and depths were estimated from sensor signal through a preliminary calibration.

UB-Lab X2: Velocity profiles and backscattered echo were measured for both pipes in the central measurement area using 3 MHz probes. The probes were placed for 5 mins on the water surface after the end of the experiments. This to avoid the possible influence and disturbances that introducing the probes in the water flow may produce.

Water quality: Turbidity (SOLITAX, Hach, USA) and conductivity (LANGE 3798-S, Hach, USA) probes were installed in the inlet chamber for online inflow measuring. Additionally, the total, fix and volatile suspended and dissolved Solids (TSS,FSS,VSS,TDS,FDS,VDS), conductivity, turbidity and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) concentrations were analysed from samples taken with an autosampler (SIGMA900, Hach, USA), the nozzle of which was placed near the online probes in the inlet chamber.

Figure 2: Inlet tank with water quality probes and depth sensors to measure flows through the triangular weirs; facility observed from downwards chamber and UBlab X2 probe.

Photrack installed their DischargeKeeper. An image-based system for volumetric flow monitoring. The system mainly consists of an IP camera, processing unit and data transition unit. The camera was mounted on top of both pipes (Figure 3), to make it possible to calculate the

discharge of both pipes using only one video. The DischargeKeeper is capable of optically measuring the water height, and it measures the surface velocities using a cross-correlation technique. Since the cross section is known and assuming a vertical velocity distribution the volumetric flow is calculated.

Four devices from Ubertone were installed in the facility: a UB-Flow AV, a UB-Flow (new generation registering velocity profiles and backscattered echo, 1MHz), a UB-Lab X2 owned by UDC and a UB-Lab P reference velocity profile and backscattered echo (3MHz, 1MHz). It should be noted that the velocity (profile, average, max) from these instruments is measured in the plane of the sensor, i.e. the vertical central radial plane in the pipes if not indicated otherwise. Ubertone python libraries were used for processing raw files (https://github.com/ubertone/udt_extractor, https://github.com/ubertone/udt4_extractor)

Figure 3. Installation of DischargeKeeper equipment. UB-Flow AV in the egg-shaped pipe.

The Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena's has also tested a broad-spectrum spectrophotometric analysis equipment based on LED technology for continuous characterization of the pollutant load of urban wastewater, without the need for chemical reagents or water handling. The equipment takes a sample of wastewater at regular time intervals, and performs a spectrophotometric analysis of the same within the range 380-700 nm. From this analysis, the equipment determines, with the help of correlation models, various water quality parameters. Likewise, in order to analyze the size of the solids present in the sample, the equipment performs multiple analyses spaced in time on each sample, in order to obtain the spectral response associated with the sedimentation process.

Test procedure:

A total of 53 short tests (ST) of less than 30 mins were carried out where the input flow rate, the weir and the slope were set constant for different conditions covering the full range of the facility. Additionally, 16 long tests (LT) were performed, which consisted in leaving a ST condition for more than 12 h. During 3 of those long tests, the sediments accumulated at the bottom of the pipes (LT12, LT13, LT15) may be used to understand the affecting of sediment bed load to the different sensors. Last, 4 turbidity tests (TT) varying suspended solids concentration (SSC) and 3 tests varying flow rate or boundary condition (BC) during the test were completed the experimental campaign.

Description of the Results

The User Group is currently working together in data collected to assess the performance of sensors in estimating the following hydraulic variables for 25 Short tests selected to cover the full range of the facility: Depths, surface velocity, bulk velocity, average and maximum velocity in the center vertical profile, depth where Vmax is in the centerline and Flow rate.

As an example, results for the test ST25 from the ultrasound sensors installed by the facility provider and the velocity profiler from Ubertone were shown in the following Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Inlet flow and depths results from depth sensors for ST25 with variable flow discharge.

Figure 5: Reference velocity in the circular pipe estimated from depth sensors (left-top), UB-Flow backscattered echo (left-bottom), projected velocity (right-top), Doppler SNR (right-bottom) profiles along distance to the sensor on the beam axis (y-axis) and time (x-axis) for ST25.

Figure 6 includes an example of the measured surface velocity of the Short Test ST03 on the circular pipe showing the velocity vectors render on top of the image as well a plot of the velocity magnitude on the direction of the flow versus the pipe width.

Figure 6. Surface velocity processing for circular pipe.

The great amount of data collected during the project is still being processed. A series of activities are therefore planned for the short and medium term. First, a detailed analysis and inter-comparison for certain selected short experiments are being carried out by Ubertone and Photrack using depth sensor measurement as reference of depths and flow discharge. Beside analyzing and comparing the flow velocities, the experiments which were done with sediment accumulation are also being analyzing. It is planned that Ubertone will evaluate the sensitivity of the UB-Flow and UB-Flow AV to sediment accumulation, check the evolution of the shape of the velocity profile throughout sediment accumulation and evaluate the possibility to get the quantitative and time-resolved evolution of the sediment accumulation height throughout each concerned LT. Photrack will analyze the evolution of the surface velocities, at a given level, which are a signature of the cross section. This will give an approximation of the sediment accumulation. The accuracy and feasibility of this measurements will be analyzed. UPCT will correlate the results of the spectrophotometric analysis obtained for each of the samples spaced 3-5 min in time, with the analytical data measured in the laboratory to generate models for estimating the pollutant load of wastewater indirectly. It will also evaluate the temporal behavior of the recorded data to determine the existence of stationary patterns among them, which will help in the development of better prediction systems.

Regarding water quality measurements. Ubertone, although 1MHz emission frequency seemed not sensitive to the SSC following preliminary processing and no 3MHz emission frequency measurements were recorded during any turbidity test, will check for available turbidity, autosampler and spectrometric data throughout the project duration, and will compare them with 3MHz measurements taken at the same periods. By analyzing the water color, photrack, will estimate the suspended solid concentration. UPCT observed the existence of a temporal behavior in the data recorded by the spectrophotometer, a crucial aspect to be able to estimate the levels of contaminants. Likewise, the sedimentation of the samples in different stages of time shows behaviors in accordance with what is expected, and the nature of the elements present in the water. This will be further analyzed in the following months.

Dissemination activities

Different dissemination activities are planned. We are going to submit an extended abstract to the [16th International Conference on Urban Drainage 2024](#) (ICUD), which will take place from 9-14 June 2024 in Delft University of Technology, NL, about “Data fusion – combination of data from different sensing techniques to improve flow data (velocity, discharge)”. This conference abstract will present the first analyzed data of flow measurements and the submission deadline is 15th of December 2023.

Furthermore, a more extensive analysis is going to be prepared and submitted in a journal paper, such as the Urban water journal (impact factor of 3) or the Journal of Water Process Engineering.

Before mid-2024, the relevant datasets from this project will be made publicly available in a shared folder, with a description of how the datafiles are arranged. We are also going to submit a paper with the data description for the Scientific data journal (impact factor of 8) within the year 2024.

Career Development

Antoine Kuhn is an engineering student from TPS (Telecom Physique Strasbourg) from the University of Strasbourg, France. To complete his work-study, he needs to spend time abroad. This Co-UDLabs access was a very nice opportunity for him to get a project experience abroad, improving his speaking English, seeing a different culture in the professional domain, having an academic research environment experience, etc.

Impact

Photrack and Ubertone, both companies working on sensor development, could test, check feasibility, limitations and improve their instrumentation and data processing, which will allow to bring into the market new and better instrumentation for the purpose of sewer monitoring. Better monitoring will help better dimensioning structures and networks, taking better care of our wastewater and reducing overflows polluting our environment.

It is intended that all relevant data will be freely accessible by other researchers to use them for model verification or scheduling a similar physical model. The project can be a benchmark test for verifying numerical models and testing them in case studies of high complexity.

Finally, this project has served for networking with different sectors on instrumentation for urban drainage.

Conclusions

In total 76 tests were performed, out of them 53 were short tests with different boundaries and flow conditions, 16 long tests with sediment accumulation, 4 turbidity tests and 3 tests varying flow rate or boundary condition during the test. During those experiments an extensive set of data has been collected, which is still being analyzed. This is being used to check and improve the tested sensors.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

Transnational Access report:

**Methodology to determine the potential heavy
metal loads washed-off by stormwater runoff
from road-deposited sediments.**

UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra
TA project title	Methodology to determine the potential heavy metal loads washed-off by stormwater runoff from road-deposited sediments
TA project theme	Water quality - Stormwater
Facility provider	Universidade da Coruña
Facility	BLOCK
TA period	18/01/2023-19/04/2023
Days of access:	90 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Carlos Alfonso Zafra Mejía	Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas, Colombia	Professor	Academy	No	Colombia	M	30
David Santiago Hernández Medina	Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas, Colombia	Environmental Engineer	Academy	Yes	Colombia	M	90

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

Heavy metals (HMs) represent one of the most reviewed factors in the environment pollution of water, soil, and air. Especially in urban environments, where HMs are relevant for the urban planning. So far, HM's research in urban environment has gone into the transport and dynamics runoff direction, where its theme has become a distinguished topic, especially for the road-deposited sediment (RDS) present in urban areas. For this reason, a project focused on the analysis of the potential HM load washed-off in rainfall events from the urban RDS was proposed. The project consisted of three phases: (1) Characterization of the RDS load, (2) assessment of HM wash-off in a physical model, and (3) application of the wash-off equation model. All the phases were carried out at the University of A Coruña (Spain) facilities. The simulation of HM wash-off was executed in the Block (Scientific platform for urban runoff tests), complex attached to the CITEEC (Centro de Innovación Tecnológica en Edificación e Enxeñaría Civil). The assessment of HM wash-off in the physical model was performed through eight tests. Six tests were conducted with deionized water. This for three RDS loads (100, 150, and 200 g/m²) and two different rainfall intensities (30 and 50 mm/h). Lastly, two tests were conducted with no RDS load and two rainfall intensities (30 and 50 mm/h).

Keywords | Road-deposited sediment, Heavy Metals, Physical model, Urban Runoff.

Materials and methods

The methodology consisted of three phases. (1) Characterization of RDS load. (2) Assessment of HM wash-off in the physical model (Block). (3) Application of a wash-off equation model (calibration and validation): Particulate HM fraction (transport) and dissolved HM fraction (leaching) relative to the total mass of HMs associated with dry-weather RDS deposition.

(1) Regarding the characterization of RDS concentration, the methodology for collection of sediments was developed in previous works in Colombia and consisted of two stages. The first stage consisted of a direct vacuuming of the sediment from the road surface, next to the road curbs (0.50 m). In the second stage, a plastic-fiber brush was used to remove the RDS adhered to the surface. The user group provided the RDS for the tests (20 kg, high traffic tunnel in A Coruña, Spain). These RDS were collected and stored in properly labeled plastic bags. The RDS was characterized at the University of A Coruña: Particle size distribution (PSD) of RDS (ISO 2591 and UNE-EN 933-1, size fractions: < 63, 125, 250, 500, 1000, and 2000 µm), HM concentration (SM 3125, Mass spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma source), and perform leaching test for HM associated with RDS in line with DIN 38414-S4 standard. The metals analyzed in both the dry RDS (total fraction), and the leachate (dissolved fraction) were as follows: Pb, Zn, Cu, Cr, Ni, Cd, Fe, Al, Mn, As, V, Co, Hg, and Ba. In addition, the following parameters were determined in the RDS: TOC and DOC (total and dissolved fractions). The above analyses were performed in the laboratories of the research support services (SAI) and sanitary and environmental engineering (GEAMA) of the University of A Coruña (Spain).

(2) For the development of the wash-off test in the physical model - Block, the methodology proposed by Zafra et al. (2017) was considered and implemented in the facility requested. The

following activities were carried out. (2.1.) *Hydrologic characterization of the wash-off test in the Block model* (CITEEC, Centro de Innovación Tecnológica en Edificación e Enxeñaría Civil). We performed hydrological characterization tests consisting of three rainfall intensities (30, 50, and 80 mm/h; 10 minutes duration, $n = 3$, see Table 1). At this stage, the following hydrological parameters were determined for each test: Rainfall intensity, scupper flow depth, and runoff flow at the scupper outlet (ultrasound technique). The team from the University of A Coruña carried out the final processing of these analyses. In addition, these hydrological characterization events were recorded using a video system consisting of two cameras. The test platform was divided (installation of a barrier) into two street sub-basins (B1 and B2). This to perform the RDS washout tests in a single sub-basin. The sub-basin used was B1 (Figure 1). That is, sub-basins B2, B6, B7, B8, and B9 were not used during the development of this study. The longitudinal and cross slope of the facility were 1% and 2%, respectively. The surface was impermeable and therefore it was not necessary to consider infiltration processes through the concrete pavement. The only scupper used in this study was No. 2. The other scuppers (1, 3, and 4) and manhole covers (N1, N2, N3, and N4) were sealed. This was to direct only surface runoff to the selected scupper.

Figure 1. Experimental setup. Plans showing the complete BLOCK installment (Top), street basin (B1) used for the wash-off rehearsals (Left bottom), and setup for wash-off test (Right bottom). All the measures of the plans are in meters.

(2.2.) *Wash-off tests in the Block model.* After the hydrologic characterization of the physical model, a series of RDS wash-off tests were performed on the pavement. For the simulation within the scientific platform, three RDS loading scenarios were considered: 100, 150, and 200 g/m². The RDSs were deposited within the cross-sectional area of the selected sub-basin (1 x 2

box; see RDS in Figure 1). Namely, the following six simulation scenarios (tests) were considered for two rainfall intensities: 30 mm/h – 100 g/m², 50 mm/h – 100 g/m², 30 mm/h – 150 g/m², 50 mm/h – 150 g/m², 30 mm/h – 200 g/m², and 50 mm/h – 200 g/m². The duration for all tests was 10 minutes (Table 1). Specifically, in total 1.8 kg of RDS were required from high traffic roads for all simulations. The RDS particle size distribution used in the simulations was prepared from reference studies (i.e., synthetic RDS was used in the simulations). Additional technical details of the methodology developed are described below.

Table 1. Characterization tests and simulation scenarios considered.

RDS Load (g/m ²)	Rainfall intensity (mm/h)	Water of the rainfall simulator	Duration (sec)
No RDS was applied	30	Drinking water	600
No RDS was applied	50	Drinking water	600
No RDS was applied	80	Drinking water	600
100	30	Deionized water	600
100	50	Deionized water	600
150	30	Deionized water	600
150	50	Deionized water	600
200	30	Deionized water	600
200	50	Deionized water	600
No RDS was applied	30	Deionized water	600
No RDS was applied	50	Deionized water	600

(2.2.1.) The determination of the scupper outlet pollutograms for both the particulate fraction and the dissolved fraction was carried out using single samples (on average every 30 seconds with 1 L bottles). Thirty-one bottles used for each test: Six bottles, every 10 sec, until 01:00; 13 bottles, every 5 sec, between 01:00 - 02:00; 3 bottles, every 20 sec, between 02:00 - 03:00; 2 bottles every 30 sec, between 03:00 - 04:00; and 7 bottles, every minute, between 04:00 - 11:00. The measured parameters are shown in Table 2.

(2.2.2.) Once the tests were completed, a mass balance was performed in relation to the RDS load initially deposited. This considered the load remaining on the road surface, the load retained in the scupper, and the load collected at the outlet of the scupper after each test. This sediment was collected by wet aspiration. (2.2.3.) A PSD characterization by laser diffractometry (Beckman Coulter LS 13 320, Aqueous Liquid Module) was carried out on each of the samples collected, the remaining sample on the road surface, the sample retained by the scupper, and the sample discharged by the scupper. The team from the University of A Coruña carried out the final processing of these samples.

(2.2.3.) An HM analysis was performed for the RDS collected on the road surface and scupper after each test. The following two fractions were considered in this analysis: < 250 µm and > 250 µm. For the water samples collected at the scupper outlet, part of the volume (100 mL) of eight selected bottles was filtered. The selection of these bottles was conditioned by the occurrence of the pollutogram according to the turbidity observed. For all the samples described above, the HMs considered in this study were analyzed for both the total and dissolved fractions. Table 2 shows all the analysis parameters considered for the water samples discharged from the

scupper. The team from the University of A Coruña carried out the final processing of these samples.

Table 2. Runoff pollution parameters considered (scupper outlet).

Physicochemical parameter	Unit	HM	Unit	HM	Unit
DQO	mg/L	Al	mg/L	Hg	mg/L
COT	mg/L	As	mg/L	Ni	mg/L
COD	mg/L	Ba	mg/L	Pb	mg/L
TUR	UFT	Cd	mg/L	V	mg/L
CON	µs/cm	Co	mg/L	Zn	mg/L
pH	Unit	Cu	mg/L		
TSS	mg/L	Cr	mg/L		
TDS	mg/L	Fe	mg/L		
TS	mg/L	Mn	mg/L		

(3) Lastly, for the application of simplified Wash-off equation model, the simplified wash-off model described in Zafra et al. (2017) will be applied to the dataset gathered at the facility.

Description of the Results

Preliminary results suggested that conductivity and turbidity tended to increase with increasing RDS load (200 g/m^2) and precipitation intensity (50 mm/h) (Figure 2). Indeed, for the series with lower RDS load (100 g/m^2) or no RDS load, the lowest values of turbidity and conductivity were observed. In addition, it was observed that the highest concentrations of total solids (TS), suspended solids (TSS), and dissolved solids (TDS) occurred for the highest RDS loadings (200 g/m^2) and precipitation intensity (50 mm/h). Conversely, the lowest concentrations of these parameters were observed for the lowest simulated RDS loadings (100 g/m^2) and precipitation intensity (30 mm/h) (Figure 3). Regarding the behavior of the grain size curves for the road surface and scupper after each test, these were detailed together in Figure 4. After each simulation, it was observed that the grain size present in the scupper was coarser compared to that observed on the road surface.

Figure 2. Behavior of turbidity (left) and conductivity (right) in nine tests with deionized water and different RDS loads.

Figure 3. Total solids (Upper left), total suspended solids (Upper right) and total dissolved solids (Bottom center) behavior on six tests with deionized water and different RDS loads.

Figure 4. Particle size distribution according to rainfall intensity and RDS load.

Datasets

During the completely transnational access, a total of 9 folders and 48 datasets were created for the development and organization of the project (Table 3).

Table 3. Dataset collection.

Name	Theme	Dataset Link
Folder: 1. RDS Characterization	PSD, leaching, and HM tests performed on the road surface.	CS, MN, CM, DG, CG, CSS, RM, ME
Folder 1.1. Laboratory forms for sample submission - SAI	HMs, COD, COT, DQO, and HM analysis of the RDS original matrix collected inside the tunnel.	FM, FA, FO, FU, FUA, FOR, FUE, FUP, FUM, FIU, FORM, FAR

Folder 1.2. SAI sample results	HMs, COD, COT, DQO and mill results: surface matrix (VF1-2), original matrix (AF1-2) and RDS synthetic matrix of RDS.	RMSAI , DCOT , DCOTAF1 , DCOTS , BOD , total BOD , TOC , TIOC 1 , BOD , total BOD , TOC , TIOC 2 , BOD , total BOD , TOC , TIOC 3
Folder 2. Hydraulic testing	Calibration, preliminary tests, and hydraulic experiments.	HT
Folder 3. RDS washing tests	BLOCK - RDS wash-off in three tests: With drinking water, (ii) deionized water and (iii) with deionized water but no RDS.	WT , HMC , WOC , PE , CMS , CMo , CM2 , EBG
Folder 3.1 Drinking water test	BLOCK rehearsals of RDS (100 g/m ²). Wash off with drinking water (30, 50, 80 mm/h).	EAg , E30 , E50 , E80
Folder 3.2 Deionized water test	BLOCK rehearsals of RDS (100, 150, 200 g/m ²). Wash off with deionized water (30, 50 mm/h).	EAd , E30 , E50 , E30150 , E50150 , E30200 , T1 50 200 , T2 50 200 , E30B , E50B , Bsed , CompSól , CompTDSTSS , CompTurCond
Folder 3.3. BLOCK test forms	Sheets for the BLOCK tests.	FRD , Fturb , Fturbdes , Fturblan , FAsp , FMetales , Forrecip , ForSol , Forsusp
Folder 3.4 SAI forms	HMs, COD, COT, DQO and mill analysis of the RDS collected from the BLOCK - deionized water: wet vacuum of the surface, wet vacuum of the scupper, and RDS at scupper outlet. Dissolved (TDS), suspended (TSS) and total (TS) solids.	ForSAI , F3050200 , F3050150200 , Flixiv3050150200 , FLixiv30100 , FLixiv50100 , FelemBlan , FBlanco

Dissemination activities

The datasets will be uploaded to the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), where the data will be available to CO-UDLabs researchers who wish to dig deeper into the project information. Researchers will continue to search for any datasets that need to be reviewed. In addition, the results of this study will be presented during the first year at an international event, and during the second year, two articles will be submitted to national and international journals. Lastly, the results of this study will be shared with the academic community of the research groups GEAMA of the University of A Coruña (Spain) and GIIAUD of the Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas (Colombia).

Career Development

The research team describes the access provided by Co-UDlabs as an enriching experience in their academic career. In the case of researcher Hernández-Medina, this study allowed him to learn about new research scenarios at the international level, which allowed him to visualize new postgraduate opportunities in Europe. In the case of Professor Zafra-Mejía, this research project will allow him to strengthen his academic activity within the Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas (Colombia), both at the undergraduate and graduate levels. In fact, this is for the development of new research projects in collaboration with European universities.

Impact

Initially, this study allowed to deepen the knowledge regarding the phenomena associated with sediment flow over road surfaces. The physical model called Block also made it possible to simulate the RDS washout phenomenon under the conditions imposed by the usual storm drainage structures on roads. Thus, work was done on the road surface, scupper, and discharge from the scupper to the manhole. This project is probably a pioneer worldwide due to the scale

of the installation and the use of deionized water to simulate rainfall events. Indeed, the dissemination products generated from this research project will allow positioning worldwide the simulation facilities of the University of A Coruña and all the researchers involved in Co-UDlabs.

Conclusions

The present study stands out as an asset for the design and construction of urban drainage systems. This is based on the understanding of the phenomena associated with the washing of heavy metals from the RDS accumulated on urban road surfaces. This access lasted 90 days. In that time, the user group composed of two people (visiting researchers) managed to meet all the research objectives proposed in the work plan. In addition, the user group managed to extract information about the phenomenon under study from a physical model and under conditions that make it stand out worldwide (turbidity, conductivity, solids, PSD, and HM concentration). This information will be available on the open access platform Zenodo for all CO-UDlabs partners. Indeed, the information originated by this project will help public and private stakeholders for decision-making and visualize possible management scenarios of urban drainage systems in the framework of HM pollution.

References

Zafra, C., Temprano, J., & Suárez, J. (2017). A simplified method for determining potential heavy metal loads washed-off by stormwater runoff from road-deposited sediments. *Science of the Total Environment*, 601–602, 260–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.178>

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

Transnational Access report:

**Urban Flooding: Houses as reservoir (UF-
HOUR)**

UDC-03-STREET-Bellos.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	UDC-03-STREET-Bellos
TA project title	Urban Flooding: Houses as reservoir (UF-HOUR)
TA project theme	Investigation on the impact of the potential storage of flooded houses acting like reservoirs in a pluvial flood hitting an idealized city.
Facility provider	Universidade da Coruña
Facility	STREET
TA period	17/10/2022-14/12/2022
Days of access:	40 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Vasilis Bellos	Democritus University of Thrace	Assistant Professor	Academia	Yes	Greece	M	5
George Sylaios	Democritus University of Thrace	Professor	Academia	No	Greece	M	0
Franz Tschekner-Gratl	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Associate Professor	Academia	Yes	Norway	M	3
Bermudez Maria	University of Granada	Associate Professor	Academia	Yes	Spain	F	3
Ilias Papakonstantis	National Technical University of Athens	Assistant Professor	Academia	No	Greece	M	3
Pritis Spyros	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	PhD student	Academia	Yes	Norway	M	40
Nikolas Deltsidis	Democritus University of Thrace	Undergraduate student	Academia	Yes	Greece	M	5

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

The percentage of the houses flooded during an urban flood event depends on the vulnerability of the system within all scales (from the entire city to each building). The flooded houses are acting as a reservoir storing flood volume, the so-called storage effect. So far, this phenomenon has not been approached, neither numerically nor experimentally. To address this gap, this study presents measurements of water depths (inside and outside of buildings) as well as the outflow hydrograph for five pluvial flood scenarios simulated under laboratory conditions. The setup consists of an artificial rainfall simulator which provides controlled precipitation for a 26.1 m² concrete platform with 25 blocks (representing buildings with basements), with detachable doors. Varying configurations of the setup regarding storage availability were tested using two different rainfall intensities. The results suggest that the storage effect of the houses has a significant impact on the overall flood characteristics in densely urbanized areas, suggesting that further consideration should be given to including the storage effect in urban flood modelling.

Keywords | urban flooding, pluvial flooding, storage effect.

Material and methods

A model of an idealized city was built for testing using an artificial rainfall simulator in the Hydraulic Laboratory of the Centre of Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering (CITEEC) at the University of A Coruña. The simulator provides three possible rain intensities, 30, 50 and 80 mm/h. The total surface of the platform representing the urban catchment is 5.8 m × 4.5 m (=26.1 m²). To define the outlet of the catchment, a major and a minor slope were given to the platform, of 0.5% and 0.1% respectively. A grid of 25 (5×5) blocks, representing buildings, were built near the outlet of the catchment. The area of each block is 30×30 cm, with a height of 20 cm above ground level and 7 cm below, representing a basement. Small detachable parts, representing doors, were installed on two sides of each block (one facing the major slope, one facing the minor one). A 5 cm high wall was built at the perimeter of the platform with a 50 cm opening to create a clearly defined outflow point. PVC was used for the blocks and the removable doors, concrete for the ground surface and wood for the perimeter wall. Figure 1 shows the planned and built laboratory setup.

Figure 1 Experimental setup. Top view, CAD plans showing the blocks and sensor placement (left). Photograph of the final setup from personal archive (right)

The discharge at the outflow was measured using a volumetric method. The water was gathered in a (50 × 50 × 70 cm) tank and an ultrasonic depth sensor was mounted on top. To measure the water depth in the catchment, 8 ultrasonic sensors were placed between the buildings and 2 more were placed outside the house matrix (one upstream and one downstream) (Figure 1). The water depth inside of the houses was also measured using pressure sensors connected to a 10 mm tube connected to a hole at the bottom of 11 of the 25 houses. Finally, 5 digital cameras (Raspberry Pi Camera V2) were installed around the platform capturing video from different angles. A small number of scenarios were also simulated with the added component of seeding particles (fluorescent plastic particles illuminated with UV light) and 2 additional high-quality cameras installed.

Frames were extracted from the videos to perform LSPIV and these were rectified, scaled and filtered before using OpenPIV open-source code to obtain surface velocities. All the cameras captured video at 20 frames per second. The sampling frequency of the ultrasonic and the pressure sensors was 10 Hz. A rolling median filter was applied to the timeseries recorded by the ultrasonic and pressure sensors. After discarding the outliers, the timeseries was upsampled to a 1 second resolution. Finally, a rolling average of 5 seconds was calculated.

Description of the Results

A total of 22 scenarios were simulated (Table 1). The results confirm the initial thesis, that the storage effect of buildings can be significant in urban pluvial floods. This is demonstrated in Figure 2, where scenarios with different numbers of open doors are compared by plotting the hydrographs at the outflow of the platform and water depths in the street nearest to the outflow.

The rain intensity was 80 mm/h for all presented scenarios. The only difference was in the configuration of the open doors. For S1, all doors are open, in S2, all doors facing at the direction of the major slope are open, in S3, all doors facing at the direction of the minor slope are open, in S4, the doors of nine of the houses are open and in S5, all doors are closed. In both graphs we can clearly see a correlation between the measured parameter (i.e., discharge and water depth) and the number of open doors. The significance of the direction of the doors is also seen in the differences between S2 and S3.

Figure 2 Measurement comparison of different scenarios. Hydrographs (left) and water depths (right).

Table 1: Experimental scenarios

Scenario #	Rain intensity (mm/h)	Duration (sec)	Doors open	Basements utilized
2022_11_29_2	80	300	–	–
2022_11_29_3	30	300	–	–
2022_11_29_4	80	300	[11, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18, 21, 22, 23]	YES
2022_11_30_2	30	300	[11, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18, 21, 22, 23]	YES
2022_11_30_4	30	300	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 15, 16, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25]	YES
2022_11_30_5	80	300	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 15, 16, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25]	YES
2022_12_2_3	80	300	[3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15]	YES
2022_12_2_4	30	300	[3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15]	YES
2022_12_2_5	80	300	ALL	NO
2022_12_2_6	80	300	ALL	YES
2022_12_5_2	30	600	ALL	YES
2022_12_9_2	80	300	[1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13]	NO
2022_12_9_3	30	300	[1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13]	YES
2022_12_9_4	80	300	[1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13]	YES
2022_12_9_6	80	300	ALL (facing up)	YES
2022_12_9_7	30	300	ALL (facing up)	YES
2022_12_12_3	80	300	ALL (facing up)	NO
2022_12_13_2	80	300	[13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24, 25]	YES
2022_12_13_3	30	300	[13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20, 23, 24, 25]	YES
2022_12_13_4	80	300	ALL (facing side)	YES
2022_12_13_5	30	300	ALL (facing side)	YES
2022_12_13_6	30	600	ALL (facing side)	YES

Datasets

From the experiments performed during the TA period, 53 datasets were created (some scenarios were run more than once).

Each dataset contains the following files:

- *"Voltage.txt"*, containing the raw output of the ultrasonic and pressure sensors used. The second line of the file contains the channel name of each sensor. The fourth line contains the local starting time of each measurement timeseries. The sixth line specifies the sampling frequency. The rest of the file is the output of the sensors, in volts, as they were indexed in the second line.
- *"Voltage_meta.txt"*, containing metadata about the experiment and measurement setup. The fourth line of this file contains information about the specific scenario simulated. The format of the comments is: " t_wet, roofs, i, t_run, doors, basements". Where:

t_wet	time (in minutes) between the last time the platform was wetted and the start of the measurements
roofs	can take the values " yes roofs" and " no roofs" describing whether or not roofs were used on the buildings
i	rain intensity (in mm/h)
t_run	rainfall duration (in seconds)
doors	can take the values " doors open" and " no doors open" describing whether or not doors were open in at least 1 building
basements	can take the values " yes basements" and " no basements" describing whether or not the buildings had basements

- *"doors.txt"*, containing information about which doors were open. This file only exists in datasets where doors were open. See *"doors_legend.txt"* for more information.
- *"layout.pdf"* contains a CAD of the setup, including the positions and numbers of the houses and sensors.
- *"doors_legend.txt"* is a text file used to understand the information in the "doors.txt" files.
- *"calibraion.zip"* contains three folders, *"calibration_ultrasonic"*, *"calibration_pressure"* and *"calibration_tank"*.
- *"calibration_ultrasonic"* contains 6 folders for each sensor. Each of those folders contains the measurement of a known distance with the ultrasonic sensor. The distances are given in "ultrasonic_distances.xlsx".
- *"calibration_pressure"* contains 4 folders for each sensor. Each of those folders contains the measurement of the pressure sensor when the respective house contained water. Between each measurement (d01, d2, d03, d04), 1 litre of water was added in the house.

- "*calibration_tank*" contains 5 folders and a file ("tank.xlsx"). The folders contain measurements of the distance between the sensor and the water level in the volumetric tank. The spreadsheet file contains the readings of the flowmeter attached to the outlet used to add water between measurements.
- "*volt_to_values.zip*" contains the Python scripts created to convert the data in the "*voltage.txt*" files to the measured quantities (depth and discharge), using the sensor calibration data from "calibration.zip". This includes the propagation of uncertainty from the calibration data to the final results.

The open dataset can be a benchmark test for verifying numerical models and testing them in case studies of high complexity. All the experimental datasets obtained (including data and metadata) will be made openly available on Zenodo repository, as part of the broader Co-UDlabs community. The Python code will be uploaded to a GitHub repository which will be included in the Zenodo repository.

Dissemination activities

Until now, a preliminary presentation of the work is submitted for the International conference of urban water – Novatech 23, which will be held at Lyon, 3-7 July, led by Spyros Pritsis. Except of this conference paper, a conference paper will be submitted for the 12th European Water Resources Association Congress which will be held in Thessaloniki, 27/6-1/7, focusing on the numerical simulation and the comparison of the results against the experimental data. This work will be led by Nikolas Deltsidis. Finally, it is scheduled to develop a journal paper in order to submit it in an international peer-reviewed journal (e.g. Journal of Hydraulic Engineering) which will present the entire framework. This will be led by Spyros Pritsis as well.

Career Development

The majority of the professors of the Team are in their early stage of their career (Vasilis Bellos, Franz Tscheikner-Gratl and Maria Bermudez). This project helped them to expand their international network and integrated their scientific background, while they gained experience for guiding young researchers (PhD or undergraduate students). The other two professors were in their medium stage of their career (George Sylaios and Ilias Papakonstantis), gained experience in different scientific fields and also expanded their networks. The younger researchers (Spyros Pritsis and Nikolas Deltsidis), developed a scientific project for their first time, while they gained valuable experience working in an international environment.

Impact

This action can be part of the wider attempt for connecting people working on urban drainage from several sectors, such as universities, institutes, water companies, civil services, etc. The open data policy of the project will also have an impact to the urban drainage community focusing on flooding. The intention of the group members is that the data will be freely accessible by other researchers in order to use them for model verification or scheduling a similar physical model. The project can be a benchmark test for verifying numerical models and testing them in case studies of high complexity. Moreover, the findings can indicate which

phenomenon is more crucial for urban flooding (and hence researchers can focus on this) and probably they can contribute for posing new research questions and strategies for answering them. A proper flood defense scheme should couple structural measures, such as flood walls or retention basins, and non-structural measures, such as flood warning systems or several personal actions in which flood defense is performed in the scale of house, as previously described. The impact of a partial protection of a city against floods to the buildings which are finally flooded is probably significant and hence, the findings might be useful to public services oriented to civil protection or to insurance companies.

Conclusions

The members of the group were 8, which could be classified in three categories (early-stage professors, medium-stage professors and young researchers). Nearly all the team visited the facility (7/8) for 59 days in total, while one young researcher worked for the entire duration (40 days) of the project. The group members were from three countries (Greece, Norway and Spain) and four institutions (DUTH, NTNU, UGR, NTUA). The research objectives were accomplished: a) an open dataset is developed, which can be a benchmark test for verifying numerical models, and will be made openly available on Zenodo repository; b) two publications for international conferences and one publication in an international peer-reviewed journal are scheduled.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report: Pollutant
Transport in Urban Floodwaters**

USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	USFD-01-ABFLUME-Mignot
TA project title	Pollutant Transport in Urban Floodwaters
TA project theme	Investigation of the spread of soluble contaminants in shallow urban floodwater
Facility provider	University of Sheffield (UoS)
Facility	A/B Flume
TA period	30/10/2022-10/01/2023
Days of access:	28 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Emmanuel Mignot	LMFA	Professor	Academia	No	France	M	6
James Shucksmith	UoS	Senior Lecturer	Academia	No	UK	M	NA
Louis Gostiaux	LMFA	R.A.	Academia	No	France	M	6
Clément Fagour	LMFA	PhD Student	Academia	Yes	France	M	1
Nathalie Grosjean	LMFA	R.A.	Academia	No	France	F	1
William Addison-Atkinson	University of Exeter	PhD Student	Academia	Yes	UK	M	20
Albert Chen	University of Exeter	Professor	Academia	No	UK	M	0
Matteo Runinato	University of Coventry	Assistant Professor	Academia	No	UK	M	0
Benjamin Dewals	University of Liege	Professor	Academia	No	Belgium	M	0
Sébastien Ericum	University of Liege	Professor	Academia	No	Belgium	M	0
Julien Lhomme	Autodesk	Engineer	Software Engineer	No	UK	M	0

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

The aim of this project was to study pollution dispersion in shallow flow flood flows within a controlled laboratory setting. The work utilized 3 different tracer methods: dye (for the PCA method), salt (for the conductivity method) and temperature (for the thermometry method). In first phase, testing compared 2D concentrations estimated by these 3 methods against benchmark probes, applied on a limited set of experimental configurations. Then, a number of further experimental configurations are studied to establish reference experimental benchmarks to be used by numerical modelers to calibrate operational models of pollutant transport in floodwater. To date, initial comparison of the different measurement techniques have been completed, with ongoing data analysis and processing required to finalize the datasets before being made open access.

Keywords | Pollutant Transport, Measurement Techniques, Urban Flooding.

Material and methods

Part 1 Comparison of Measuring Techniques for Pollutant Transport

Experimental set-up: A 1/1000 slope, straight and smooth street of 1.2m wide is set-up at UoS with a manhole of diameter 18 cm, centerline located at a distance 160 cm downstream from the street entrance. To do so the 4m wide flume of UoS is separated in 3 flow domains: the street flow at the center of the flume and two corridors flows on the sides, separated by a building line. The center of the axis system is located along the left street façade, aligned with the center of the manhole (see below). X axis is oriented streamwise and Y axis is oriented spanwise.

Figure 1: Sketch of experimental setup (config 1)

Boundary conditions: The upstream boundary conditions are the street flow discharge and the surcharged manhole discharge. Note however that given the constriction of the flume into the street and the two corridors, the exact inflow discharge in the 1.2m wide street is assessed by LSPIV measurement. Consequently, the only adjustable boundary condition on the surface is the total inflow Q_{surface} (equal to the sum of the street flow and both corridor flows). The downstream boundary condition is a free outflow (critical flow condition).

Flow configurations: Three flow configurations are considered herein, labeled “Q01”, “Q02” and “Q03”. The exact same geometry and same surface inflow discharge Q_{surface} are considered for these three flows. Only the manhole surcharging overflow is varied among the three configurations, see Table 1.

Table 1: flow configurations and measured discharges (Config 1 straight street)

Flow config.	Surface flow		Manhole overflow	
	Current loop (mA)	Measured discharge (L/s) (several repetition)	Current loop (mA)	Measured discharge (L/s) (several repetition)
Q01	10.55	4.6 – 4.6 – 4.63	7.9	0.73 – 0.67 – 0.78)
Q02	10.55	4.57 – 4.57 – 4.59 – 4.59	8.3	1.4 – 1.3 – 1.26 – 1.2
Q03	10.55	4.6 – 4.58 – 4.59 – 4.6	9.2	2.55 – 2.38 – 2.47 – 2.52

Method 1: conductivity probes: A solution of high salt concentration is added to the pipe reaching the manhole (upstream from the flowmeter) in order to increase the conductivity of the manhole outflow water compared to the surface inflow water. As both flows mix, the conductivity of the street flow then homogenizes towards downstream. The conductivity is then measured at different locations in the street, using 4 conductivity probes (by Hendress Hauser).

Four probes are used herein, labeled “P1”, “P2” and “P3” for the probes measuring the conductivity in the street and “P0” which is used in the right-side corridor (with only surface inflow – clear water – to register potential conductivity drifts in the water pumped from the main sump). The three measurement probes are attached to each other, aligned along x direction, with an inter-distance along y axis of 40cm (see Figure 2). Given the limited flow depth in the experiment, the elevation of each probe had to be adjusted to keep each probe measuring part immersed underneath the free surface and keep it at a distance larger than 1cm from the bed. The bar supporting the three measuring probes (P1, P2 & P3) can be moved transversally so that P1 moves the along the first 1/3 of street width, P2 along the 2nd and P3 along the third 1/3. For each section, the probes are thus located at:

Table 2 : Spanwise location of the conductivity probes for each cross-section

Position Id	Y1 (mm)	Y2 (mm)	Y3 (mm)	Y4 (mm)	Y5 (mm)	Y6 (mm)
P1	10	80	150	220	290	380
P2	410	480	550	620	690	780
P3	810	880	950	1020	1090	1180

Note however that the street width slightly changed: it equaled $b=1190\text{mm}$ for Q01 and Q02 configuration measurements and $b=1200\text{mm}$ for Q03 measurement

The measurement domain covers four street sections located at:

$$X1=100\text{cm} \quad X2=182\text{cm} \quad X3=264\text{cm} \quad X4=364\text{cm}$$

Figure 3: Sketch of the locations of the conductivity probes (Config 1 straight street)

Procedure: For each one of the four flow configurations, the conductivity probes are moved along six transverse positions (Table 2) so that $6 \times 3 = 18$ measurement points are available. For each position, the conductivity is measured at a frequency of 1Hz, during 100s.

Method 2: thermal camera (Xenics Gobi+ 640 GigE): The same three flow configurations Q01, Q02 and Q03 were measured with a thermal camera located near the downstream end of the flume, looking down at the free surface towards upstream. The manhole flow is heated by adding a limited discharge of hot water (at 60°C) in the pumping loop (upstream from the flowmeter). The surcharging overflow is thus warmer by 1 to 2 degrees than the surface inflow. This limited temperature difference between both flows does not alter much the water densities but permits to register the dispersion of the surcharging overflow when flowing in the street.

For each flow configuration, the surcharging and surface flows are first established with cold water in the manhole. Then, the temperature of the overflow is suddenly increased and the 2D field of surface temperature over the whole domain is registered at a frequency of 3Hz and a spatial resolution that depends mainly on the streamwise position: due to the camera angle, the spatial resolution is higher in the downstream part than the upstream part of the street.

As the flow around the manhole entirely registered, the temperature of the surface and manhole flows can be directly obtained on the recorded temperature fields (see Fig.6). These values are then used to normalized the manhole flow concentration from 0 in the surface flow to 1 in the manhole surcharged flow.

As for all optical 2D methods, the thermal camera measurement requires to orthorectify the images to the Cartesian axis system presented above. This is performed by placing 40 resistors at known 2D locations and at the water elevation (on the dry set-up) and recording the pixels corresponding of these hot points on the images (without moving the camera). The rectification procedure thus becomes straightforward.

Method 3: Planar Concentration analysis: In this case a colored dye (injected upstream of the manhole) was used as a tracers and light intensity was recorded and used to determine 2D concentration using overhead cameras. Further technical details of this method can be found in (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flowmeasinst.2018.10.022>). The same three flow configurations Q01, Q02 and Q03 were measured.

Part 2 - Development of Benchmark Datasets

Following part 1 measurement techniques 2 and 3 were used to quantify the spreading of solute concentrations under a number of different geometrical configurations set up in the facility (around an obstacle, and through a meander) and flow rates (table 3). Due to the number of tests, data processing of these experiments is ongoing, and therefore full results are not yet presented here.

Table 3 : Flow conditions for part 2 tests

Geometrical Configuration	Flow Condition Name	Flow Rates (l/s)	
		Sewer Surcharge (Qe)	Surface Flow (QinF, from LSPIV)
1 - Straight Street	S01	0.9	0.11
1 - Straight Street	S02	1.06	0.11
1 - Straight Street	S03	1.11	0.11
2 - Obstacle	O01	0.84	0.11
2 - Obstacle	O02	1.07	0.12
2 - Obstacle	O03	1.14	0.11
3 - Meandering	M01	0.9	TBC
3 - Meandering	M02	1.04	TBC
3 - Meandering	M03	1.09	TBC

Description of the Results

As some datasets are still being processed, this report presents a selection of results currently available. In order to compare the measurement technics, Figure 4 plots on the same graphs the profiles of normalized conductivity and temperature. The agreement seems very high. One main limitation of the temperature measurement seems to be a high spatial fluctuation / oppositely, the main advantage is the high spatial resolution.

Figure 4: Comparison of temperature and conductivity normalized profiles for the 3 flows along the 3 first sections (Config 1 straight street, 3 flows)

V Effect of a high temperature gradient between both flows

A second series of measurement was performed by setting a high temperature difference (more than 10 K) between the sewer and street flows. The thermography measurement reveals in Figure 5 that this temperature gradient seems to highly impact the temperature (and thus mixing) fields. The buoyancy effect seems to artificially spread the flume.

Figure 5: Comparison of temperature normalized profiles for the 3 flows with a low (1 to 2 Kelvin) or a high (more than 10 Kelvin) temperature difference between the sewer and the street flow (Config 1 straight street, 3 flows)

B) Configuration 2 : Obstacle

Only one flow configuration is considered here : O03 ($Q_{\text{sewer}} = 1.1 \text{ L/s}$)

Figure 6 :2D field of surface thermal measurement of the Configuration 2 Obstacle: O03 a: an instantaneous, b: the time averaged, c: the RMS of the surface temperature

C) Configuration 3 : Meandering

Only one flow configuration is considered here: M03 (with $Q_{\text{sewer}} = 1.1$ L/s)

Figure 7 :2D field of surface thermal measurement of the Configuration 3 Meandering: M03 a: an instantaneous, b: the time averaged, c: the RMS of the surface temperature

Further analysis of PCA datasets conducted at UoS will enable full comparison between the different approaches. Further to the results presented here 2D velocity datasets (measured using LSPIV) are available for each condition and will be included in the final open access datasets.

Datasets

Datasets are currently being collated in a group google drive folder hosted by UoS. This includes metadata and technical details of sensors, testing configurations, flow rates and analysis procedure. Once completed UoS will transfer files and data to an OA Zenodo site and using via Co-UDlabs dissemination channels.

Dissemination activities

A journal publication is currently under development focused on the open access datasets and the comparison of measurement techniques. This will be developed during 2023 and is currently being coordinated by James Shucksmith and Emmanuel Mignot. Industrial partners are also working on a complementary modeling work utilizing the datasets which will be disseminated via academic and commercial routes.

Career Development

The project included in person visits from 2 PhD students who have benefited by gaining directly involvement in an international collaborative project. The project has also strengthened links between international groups working on urban flooding, with potential for future collaboration between partners.

Impact

Anticipated impacts include more accurate tools and techniques to estimate health risks associated with pollutants within floodwaters. Robust testing will enable direction of future research in understanding key processes associated with pollutant dispersion within flood water. The outcome will support the configuration of modelling parameters, not only for academic research models but also commercial software such as Mike Urban, Infoworks ICM and HYSTEM EXTRAN, that will help researchers and practitioners better simulate the spreading of contaminated floodwaters.

Conclusions

This access project hosted five researchers from France and the UK at UoS facilities from 30/10/22 to 10/1/23 over 28 calendar days. Work focused on the measurement of pollutant transport processes in shallow urban flood water, specifically on ten viability different measurement techniques to describe the 2D spread of solute and the development of an Open Access dataset. Preliminary results show the effectiveness of a thermal camera instrumentation to characterize the 2D spreading of solute in a robust manner, with further analysis ongoing on the final measurement technique (PCA). Open access datasets are currently being collected and will be hosted on a zenodo site. This is expected to be of high value for the modelling community, as the datasets can be used to test and calibrate different modelling approaches describing the spread of pollution in shallow urban floodwater.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Temperature time series analysis for
predicting sedimentation in sewer
systems**

USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	USFD-02-ANNULAR-Regueiro
TA project title	Temperature time series analysis for predicting sedimentation in sewer systems
TA project theme	In-sewer processes
Facility provider	University of Sheffield
Facility	ANNULAR
TA period	01/06/2023-01/09/2023
Days of access:	60 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Manuel Regueiro	Universidade da Coruña	Postdoc Researcher	Academia	Yes	Spain	M	60
Maria Viklander	Lulea Technical University	Professor	Academia	No	Sweden	F	0
Mehwish Taneez	Lulea Technical University	Postdoc Researcher	Academia	Yes	Sweden	F	0
Jeroen Langeveld	TU Delft	Professor	Academia	No	The Netherlands	M	0
Petra van Daal-Rombouts	Water Board De Dommel	Engineer	Industry	No	The Netherlands	F	0
Jessica Thorsell	Stockholm Vatten AB	Engineer	Industry	No	Sweden	F	0

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)

Summary

Sediment accumulation in sewers is a major concern in urban drainage systems, as it causes the loss of hydraulic capacity, generates hazardous gases, and increases the risk of blockages. Sewer maintenance operations are in most cases performed based on previous experiences, as there is no methodology to continuously monitor sedimentation processes. This proposal suggests an innovative use of thermal probes to continuously monitor the temperature oscillations in the liquid and solid phases to measure the heat transfer processes between both media and, thus, estimate the presence of bed deposits. For this purpose, a series of laboratory experiments in the ANNULAR are proposed using different sediment thicknesses and water temperature gradients. The main advantages of this facility are: i) room temperature control, ii) steady flow conditions to reproduce convection and conduction processes. The main objective of this study is to develop a methodology to analyse temperature oscillations and predict sedimentation processes under flow conditions. The envisioned results have a high potential for scientific relevance and operational purposes in terms of urban drainage maintenance strategies. The practitioners involved in this proposal can use the findings in real environments to improve the knowledge of sedimentation processes.

Keywords | Heat transfer processes, Temperature sensors, Sewer sediments, Urban drainage systems.

Material and methods

The annular flume was used to perform the experimental campaign (Figure 1). The annular flume consists of a rectangular cross-section 0.20 m wide and 0.48 m high. In addition, the annular platform shows a 2.20 m external and 1.80 m internal diameters. The side walls and the bottom plate are made from acrylic, and the lid can be manually lowered or lifted to set the desired water depth in the flume. The two units can be rotated independently. Finally, the annular flume was placed in a temperature-controlled room. No additional systems were introduced to ensure insulation and temperature control.

Figure 1: Photo of the Annular Flume facility at University of Sheffield.

The experiments were carried out by pouring a sediment layer and a water layer on top. A water bath recirculator was used to develop a temperature-controlled system to simulate daily temperature variations in sewers. For this purpose, water was pumped from the temperature-controlled system into the water layer of the flume. On the other hand, flow conditions were established by setting top and bottom rotational velocities.

24 PT100 temperature sensors (model PS6/60/PT100/CLA, RS Pro, UK) were installed at three cross-sections. The distribution of sensors covered the measurements of the room, water, and sediment temperatures. One sensor was installed in the water bath recirculator to control the temperature profile introduced in the flume. The data was controlled and collected in a laptop.

Figure 2 summarizes the experimental setup performed at University of Sheffield facilities (Sheffield, United Kingdom).

Figure 2: Top (left) and front-section (right) view of the experimental setup.

The lab-scale experiments replicated the water temperature variations in sewer pipes, which show marked daily patterns that depend on basin activities, habits, and network operation strategies. Tests were carried out by setting daily temperature patterns using the water bath recirculator and flow conditions by setting top-bottom rotational velocities. The objective was to measure the temperature time series in the system (water and sediment layers) and estimate the sediment depth by analysing these time series. Two daily cycles (48 hours) were simulated for each test, trying to minimise the influence of the initial conditions.

A total of 18 experiments were carried out because of the combination of the following conditions:

- 3 sediment depths: 60-, 110- and 160-mm. Sediment layers were composed of a combination of three materials. The lower layer was thicker than the upper layer and was composed of fine silica sand, while the upper layer (thickness of 10 mm) was

composed of 5 mm of coarse sand and 5 mm of gravel. The objective of the upper layer was to prevent erosion of the fine sand.

- **Fine silica sand.** The thicknesses of the fine silica sand layers were: 50-, 100- and 150-mm.
- **Coarse sand.** The thickness of the coarse sand layer was constant: 5 mm.
- **Gravel.** The thickness of the gravel layer was constant: 5 mm.

The methodology for estimating sediment depths is based on the analysis of heat transfer processes. Therefore, a characterisation of the thermal properties of the sediments was required. For this purpose, samples were analysed in the laboratory by using a TP01 sensor (Hukseflux, The Netherlands). Table 1 summarizes the thermal properties:

Table 1: Thermal conductivity (W/m/°C) and volumetric heat capacity (MJ/m³/°C) of the fine and coarse sand, and gravel. Mean value ± standard deviation.

Sample	Thermal conductivity (W/m/°C)	Volumetric heat capacity (MJ/m ³ /°C)
<i>Fine Sand</i>	1.72 ± 0.03	2.86 ± 0.03
<i>Coarse Sand</i>	2.25 ± 0.05	2.99 ± 0.03
<i>Gravel</i>	1.63 ± 0.01	3.68 ± 0.02

- 3 flow velocities: 0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 m/s conditions were set as bottom rotational velocities because they define the convective heat transfer processes in annular flumes. Top rotational velocities were set after calibrating the optimal ratio between top and bottom rotational velocities (Cecchetto, 2017).
- 2 temperature patterns: two temperature profiles were defined in the water bath to reproduce real daily temperature patterns in sewers (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Daily temperature patterns set in the water bath recirculator and temperature measurements in the water layer of the annular flume.

Description of the Results

The experimental model reproduced daily patterns in sewer pipes under dry weather conditions. As a result, temperature series were obtained. We could differentiate two types of results:

- Flow conditions.

Flow conditions were set by establishing bottom rotational velocities of 0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 m/s and calculating the top rotational velocities based on the optimal ration. A calibration of the optimal ration between the top and bottom rotational velocities was performed for each sediment depth condition. The calibration process was performed by introducing a near-neutral buoyancy balls in the annular flume, establishing a bottom rotational velocity, and adjusting the top rotational velocity to a value at which the ball was rolling at the centre of the cross-section. This process was repeated up to 9 steps, ranging bottom rotational velocities from 0.25 to 0.45 m/s. Lower values could not be performed as the balls did not move because of the high roughness introduced by the gravels in the sediment surface, and higher values were not considered to avoid erosion processes. The average optimal ratio was considered to establish the flow conditions. Table 2 summarises the main hydraulic parameters of the experimental campaign.

Table 2: Hydraulic conditions of the experimental campaign. H_{sed} : sediment depth; H_{water} : water depth; ω_{opt} : optimal ratio; U_{bottom} : bottom rotational velocity (m/s); U_{top} : top rotational velocity (m/s); U_{mean} : mean rotational velocity (m/s).

Flow condition	H_{sed} (mm)	H_{water} (mm)	ω_{opt}	U_{bottom} (m/s)	U_{top} (m/s)	U_{mean} (m/s)
Flow 1.1	60	307	3.841	0.10	0.38	0.16
Flow 1.2				0.20	0.77	0.32
Flow 1.3				0.40	1.54	0.64
Flow 2.1	110	256	3.739	0.10	0.37	0.16
Flow 2.2				0.20	0.75	0.33
Flow 2.3				0.40	1.50	0.66
Flow 3.1	160	206	3.377	0.10	0.34	0.16
Flow 3.2				0.20	0.68	0.32
Flow 3.3				0.40	1.35	0.64

- Sediment depth estimations.

The harmonic characteristics, defined from the amplitude and phase, were computed from the temperature series in the water layer and at the bottom of the sediment layer to estimate the sediment depth. Figure 4 shows how the sediment-bed temperature series attenuates as a function of sediment depth. The greater the sediment depth, the greater the attenuation and phase difference between the temperature series in the water layer and at the bottom of the sediment.

Figure 4: Temperature time series in the water layer (blue line) and sediment-bed at sediment depth conditions of 60-, 110-, and 160mm (brown lines).

A surrogate model, which was previously developed by members of the user group (Regueiro-Picallo et al. 2023), was applied to estimate the sediment depths. These estimations were compared with sediment depths measured with visual observations. Figure 5 shows the comparison of sediment depth estimations between the temperature-based system and the reference observations. As a main result, we observed that the flow rate conditions and, subsequently, the convective heat transfer process in the water-sediment interface barely affects the sediment depth estimations. Therefore, temperature-based systems are suitable for monitoring sediment accumulation in field applications without requiring hydraulic measurements.

Figure 4: Preliminary comparison of the sediment depths estimated with the temperature-based system (boxplots) and the reference visual observations (dashed lines) at 60- (top graph), 110- (middle graph), and 160-mm (bottom graph).

Datasets

The database and a descriptive report of the experimental campaign will be published on ZENODO under a Creative Commons CC BY-NC 4.0 license, which allows anyone to download and read the report free of charge without using the material for commercial purposes. Furthermore, the dataset may be reused and cited, provided that the original published version is cited. These conditions allow maximum use and publication of the work and at the same time ensure that the authors receive appropriate credit.

The dataset will include i) the variations of room, water, and sediment-bed temperatures (time series format); ii) the flow settings; iii) the mechanical and thermal properties of sediments; and

iv) the sediment depth observations. The measured parameters, including the units, are listed below:

- Processed temperature time series and sensor calibration process: T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Hydraulic conditions: U_{bottom} (m/s), U_{top} (m/s), U_{mean} (m/s).
- Sediment characteristics: Thermal conductivity ($\text{W/m}^{\circ}\text{C}$), Volumetric heat capacity ($\text{J/m}^3/^{\circ}\text{C}$).
- Sediment depth observations: H_{sed} (m).

Dissemination activities

The user group members decided to publish the results as part of a communication at the ICUD conference, 9th-14th June 2024, Delft (The Netherlands). The user group members are also considering the publication of the results in a peer-review journal.

Career Development

The experimental work developed within this TA Project contributed to the development of the postdoctoral work of the visiting researcher. In addition, an international working group was established, bringing together professionals from academia and industry. Therefore, the TA Project was developed from both academic and commercial perspectives, addressing the needs of the urban drainage system sector in terms of sediment management.

Impact

From a commercial point of view, the results showed the potential use of temperature-based systems for monitoring sediment accumulation in sewer systems without requiring the measurement of hydraulic variables (e.g., flowrate). Temperature-based systems could be low-cost and easy to implement in sewer systems. Thus, optimal inspection and cleaning strategies could be performed based on observations rather than periodic operations. This would reduce costs and the risk of combined sewer overflows (CSO) during rainfall events caused by sediment accumulation (social and environmental impact). From an academic point of view, monitoring sediment accumulation may be used to develop more accurate sediment transport models in sewer systems. This would lead to optimal sewer system designs from a sediment management point of view, including the development of digital twin models.

Conclusions

The TA Project was developed in the ANNULAR facility, hosted by the University of Sheffield, where flow conditions and heat transfer processes in sewer pipes were simulated inside a temperature-controlled room. The project granted 60-day access to a postdoctoral researcher, on behalf of a user group composed of international experts from the academia and industrial of urban drainage.

The performance of temperature-based systems for estimating sediment depths in sewers were evaluated, considering different flow conditions and temperature profiles. The results showed that the convective heat transfer processes at the water-sediment interface could be neglected because they barely influenced the sediment depth estimation. Consequently, the initial objectives were fulfilled.

Further steps will include the publication of the database in an open access repository, the communication of the results in an international conference and the eventual publication of an article in a peer-review scientific journal. Future commercial and scientific perspectives include the implementation of these systems for the optimization of sediment management in sewer systems and other urban drainage infrastructures.

References

Cecchetto, M. (2017). *The development of stochastic based transport models to predict the advection and diffusion of bed-load sediment*. PhD Thesis, University of Sheffield, UK.

Regueiro-Picallo, M., Anta, J., Naves, A., Figueroa, A., & Rieckermann, J. (2023). Towards urban drainage sediment accumulation monitoring using temperature sensors. *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2EW00820C>

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

Transnational Access report:

H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1

USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morató

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage Research Labs Communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	USFD-03-ANNULAR-Morató
TA project title	Annular Flume studies to test the effect on Antibiotic Resistant Genes and Use of CRISPR- Cas in <i>E. coli</i> from sediments affected by sewage pollution.
TA project theme	Investigation on the environmental impact and health risk associated with the spread of wild-type antibiotic resistant bacteria in water and sediment samples from a recreational river using an Annular Flume as the testing approach. Evaluation of different efficient DNA cleavage technique to restore bacterial susceptibility to antibiotics.
Facility provider	University of Sheffield
Facility	ANNULAR FLUME
TA period	14/03/2023-19/06/2023
Days of access:	60 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Jordi Morató	UPC	Professor	Academia	No	Spain	M	0
Leonardo Martín Pérez	UPC	Research Fellow	Academia	No	Spain	M	0
Nury Infante González	UPC	Postdoctoral Researcher	Academia	Yes	Spain	F	60

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

Assessment of antibiotic resistant bacteria in water and sediment samples is essential to determine the persistence of potentially hazardous pathogens in aquatic ecosystems. In addition, the implementation of control measurements and biotechnological approaches to reduce the impact and environmental persistence of both antibiotics and resistant pathogens is necessary to improve water quality in receiving water bodies. In this study, the interchange of extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL) producing bacteria between sediment and water samples obtained from a river affected by sewage pollution was evaluated. To this aim, increasing shear stress treatments that resemble river flows were simulated in an annular flume, and the CTX-M-1 gene that encodes for a beta-lactamase enzyme was used as the target sequence for testing antibiotic resistant bacterial presence. This gene was detected in DNA obtained from water and gravel biofilm samples by end-point PCR. Additionally, isolation of ESBL-producing bacteria from river samples was achieved in ESBL selective agar and then identified by using biochemical tests. The profile of antibiotic susceptibility of the isolated strains was tested using the Kirby-Bauer testing method. Likewise, a CRISPR-Cas9 approach was designed and assayed with 10 DNA oligo sequences to determine the efficiency of cleavage to CTX-M-1. Moreover, *in vitro* digestion of DNA using sgRNA+Cas9 was also assessed. Our results demonstrated a higher presence of heterotrophic bacteria and total coliforms in river sediment compared to water samples. Moreover, *E. coli* presence in water samples was significant, representing between 90-95% of the total bacterial load. Likewise, 42 ESBL positive strains were isolated from both river sediment and water samples. From them, 30 *E. coli* strains were confirmed as glucuronidase and beta-galactosidase positive. Notably, these strains presented resistance for cephalothin (KF) (30µg) and ampicillin/sulbactam (SAM) (20 µg). Finally, 6 out of 10 designed sgRNAs (439rev, 812forw, 553rev, 132forw 717forw and 642forw) demonstrated good efficiency for CTX-M-1 gene cleavage in *in vitro* assays.

Keywords | Annular flume, ESBL-producing bacteria, CTX-M-1, CRISPR-Cas9.

1. Material and Methods

1.1. Water and sediment samples obtention

Water and sediment samples were collected from river Don (53°23'41.6"N 1°26'31.8"W). This river flows through Sheffield, starting from the headwaters in the Peak District until South Yorkshire (before joining the river Humber) (Fig. 1). Electrical conductivity, pH, temperature, and total dissolved solid (TDS) of water samples were determined *in situ* using a standard multiparameter probe. The samples were stored at 4 °C until reach the lab for further analysis.

Figure 1. Map showing the location of river Don (Sheffield, UK) and representative images of the site of samples collection.

1.2. Antibiotic susceptibility testing and screening for ESBL-producing bacteria

Microbiological analysis of water and sediment samples were performed using commercial media to quantify the content of total heterotrophic bacteria, total coliforms, and *E. coli*. Briefly, sediment samples (~30g suspended in 50 mL sterile PBS 7.0) and water samples (100 mL) were filtered using a porous membrane (0.20 µm) to retain the microorganisms. Then, the filters were placed on the surface of Petri dishes containing selective Chromocult® agar (Merck) or nutrient tryptic soy agar (TSA, Merck). Finally, the plates were incubated for 24-48 h at 37°C in a culture chamber and colonies were numbered at the unaided eye. Bacterial count was informed as CFU/mL. To test potential ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae the isolated strains were grown on selective agar ChromID™ ESBL (bioMérieux) for 18-24 h at 37 °C. Selected strains were tested for antibiotic resistance against 12 antibiotics (CZA, ceftazidime-avibactam; KF, cephalothin; CXM, cefuroxime; SAM, ampicillin/sulbactam; FOX, cefoxitin; MEM, meropenem; CTX, cefotaxime; TZP, piperacillin/tazobactam; ETP, ertapenem; CEC, cefaclor; IPM, imipenem; ATM, aztreonam). Susceptibility tests were performed on Mueller-Hinton agar according to the EUCAST recommendations and interpreted following the EUCAST breakpoints (European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing, 2022).

1.3. PCR analysis

Whole-cell DNAs were extracted from ESBL-producing strains using the DNeasy kit (QIAGEN) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The recovered supernatant containing the nucleic acids was frozen at -20°C until use. PCR was performed on an VeritiPro 96-Well thermal cycler (Applied Biosciences), using the primers CTXM1-F3 (5'-GACGATGTCAGTGGCTGAGC-3' CTXM1-R2 (5'-AGCCGCCGACGCTAATACA-3') for detection of CTX-M-1 gene (Pitout et al., 2004). Briefly, 1 µL (12-45 ng) of DNA template was used in a final 25 µL master-mix volume. PCR experiments were performed with 35 cycles consisting of 2 min of denaturation at 95°C, 30 s of annealing at 55°C, and 5 min of final extension at 72°C. A commercial *E. coli* strain (NEB® 10-beta Competent *E. coli*, New England Biolabs) was transformed with a pUCIDT-Kan plasmid containing the *E. coli* blaCTX-M-1 gene (GenBank number: X92506.1), and used as positive control for the PCR assays. Additionally, an *E. coli* strain transformed with an ampicillin resistant pUC19 plasmid was used as negative control. All PCR amplicons were separated by gel electrophoresis on a 1.5% (wt/vol) agarose gel and staining with ethidium bromide.

1.4. Hydrodynamic studies

The annular flume was loaded with 5 cm sediment and 300 L of river water by pumping (Fig. 2a). Afterwards, the system was left for 7 days to allow biofilm establishment with a top and bottom modules speed of 7.0 sec/cycle (high) and 22.5 sec/cycle (low), respectively (Fig. 2b). The effect of different hydrological perturbations on sediment bacterial concentration was tested using 4 treatments according to Table 1. A representative scheme of the sampling procedure is presented in Fig. 3. After each treatment, sediment was sampled (Fig. 2c), and compared for the presence of total heterotrophs, coliforms and *E. coli* by plate counting, and expressed as log CFU/mL. Additionally, presence of ESBL-producing bacteria in sediments samples obtained from the annular flume was tested by PCR as described in Section 1.3.

Figure 2. A) Annular flume charge with sediment and water collected from river Don. B) Annular flume operation during treatments evaluation. C) Representative photograph of the sampling process.

Briefly, gravel samples were recovered from the bottom of the annular flume and suspended in 50 mL sterile saline solution. Genomic DNA was extracted from gravel after sonication (40 kHz) to liberate the attached bacterial biofilm. Then, the clarified supernatant was filtered using a porous membrane (0.20 µm pore size) on whose surface the microorganisms were retained. DNA was extracted for filters using the DNeasy kit (QIAGEN) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Table 1. Shear stress treatments. Top and bottom speed refer to the upper and lower compartments of the annular flume.

Treatment ID	Running time (h)	Top speed (sec/cycle)	Bottom speed (sec/cycle)
T1	1	7.0	22.5
T2	1	5.5	20.5
T3	1	4.5	19.5
T4	1	3.0	16.1

Figure 3. Top view of the annular flume and sampling strategy. The annular flume was labeled in 4 sections according to the treatment (T), sediment/gravel samples were composite samples (S1, S2 and S3) from 3 sampling points (1, 2, 3).

1.5. Selection of sgRNAs for CRISPR/Cas9 knockout screening

DNA sequences were selected using web-based programme (e.g., CRISPOR and CHOPCHOP) as potential cleavage sites for the target CTX-M-1 gene. Then, 10 single guide RNA (sgRNA) were designed and purchased from Eurofins Genomics (www.eurofins.com). Further, *in vitro* cleavage of CTX-M-1 using the Cas9 Nuclease, *S. pyogenes* kit (NEB #M0386, New England Biolabs) was achieved. Finally, the efficiency of the digestion procedure was tested by agarose gel (2%) electrophoresis through the analysis of the banding pattern as described by Jun-S et al. (2016).

2. Results

In order to analyse the role of natural waters as reservoir of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and the impact of hydrological events in the spreading of resistant microorganism in aquatic environments, different tasks were performed: i) collection of water and sediment samples from a recreational river, ii) isolation, identification, and characterization of antibiotic resistance bacteria from river samples, iii) fluid dynamics evaluation and its impact on ESBL-producing coliforms spreading using the annular flume facilities located at the University of Sheffield.

2.1. Characterization of the bacterial load from river Don (Sheffield, UK)

As can be appraised in Fig. 4, the bacterial load between sediment and water samples obtained from river Don was different. Total coliforms presence in sediments was approximately 100 times higher than in water. On the other hand, a significant proportion *E. coli* was found in water samples representing around 90-95% of the total coliforms present. By the contrast, around 50% of the coliforms found in sediment samples corresponded with *E. coli* strains.

Figure 4. Total coliforms and *E. coli* load found in sediment and water samples obtained from river Don (Sheffield, UK).

In addition, a broader coliform diversity was observed in sediments (Fig. 5A and 5B), including several ESBL-producing strains (Fig. 5C). A total of 34 ESBL-positive strains were isolated from river Don samples, 27 from sediment and 7 from water.

Future perspectives: Metagenomic tests (e.g., 16S rRNA sequencing) will be performed to identify and classified the microbiological diversity of the river Don in a time frame of one year.

Figure 5. Representative photographs of coliforms and *E. coli* strains from (A) water and (B) sediment samples grown on Chromocult® agar at 37°C for 24 h. (C) ESBL-producing bacteria isolated from sediments samples grown on selective ChromID™ ESBL agar (blue-dark colonies are indicative of *E. coli* strains and green colonies are indicative of *Klebsiella* sp. strains).

2.2. Effect of increasing shear stress on bacteria spreading

Increase shear stress showed a moderately effect on bacteria detachment from the sediment phase. Total heterotrophic bacteria count significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased from 3.6 ± 0.1 at T1 (lower rotation speed) to 2.9 ± 0.3 CFU/mL at T4 (higher rotation speed). Coliforms release from sediments showed a similar tendency than the one observed for total heterotrophs, while *E. coli* did not show a clear behavior (Fig. 6). These results suggest that increasing hydrological impacts could have a positive effect in potentially harmful bacteria release from sediments to the water phase. Regarding this, ESBL-positive isolates were also detected. Moreover, preliminary results suggested that *Klebsiella* sp. were more representative than *E. coli* in sediment samples. Therefore, more studies are needed in order to determine the relationship between microbial adherence and other factors like sediment composition and bacterial biofilm-forming capacity.

Future perspectives: More aggressive treatments (i.e., higher shear stress) should be analysed to validate the presented results. In addition, metagenomic data will be generated to collect extra information on microbiological diversity. It is expected that these activities were performed in a time frame on 1.5 year.

Figure 6. Bacterial-biofilm quantification in gravel samples during the annular flume assay. It can be roughly observed that at higher shear stress (T4) a lesser number of bacteria remains attached to the sediment.

2.3. Susceptibility antibiotic testing of ESBL-positive bacteria

A total of 42 ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* (12 *Klebsiella* sp. and 30 *E. coli*) were tested, including those isolated from river Don (27 from water and 7 from sediments samples) and those isolated from the annular flume (1 from water and 6 from sediment/gravel samples). As expected, an extensive antibiotic resistance was observed, e.g., 18 isolates were resistant to ampicillin/sulbactam (SAM), 10 to cephalothin (KF), 7 to Cefoxitin (FOX) and/or Cefaclor (CEC), 5 to Ertapenem (ETP), 3 to cefuroxime (CXM) and/or cefotaxime (CTX), and 1 to Aztreonam (ATM) (Table 2). Notably, all 42 ESBL-positive bacteria were susceptible to ceftazidime/avibactam (CZA) and imipenem (IPM).

Future perspectives: Whole-genome sequencing experiments will be planned aimed to detect antibiotic resistance genes (including other than CTX-M-1) in all ESBL-positive isolates. Considering the high cost of this technology, it is expected that such experiences be completed in a time frame of two years.

Table 2. Antibiotic resistant pattern of the 42 ESBL-producing strains isolated at the present study.

Antibiotics (dose)	Susceptible isolates	Partially susceptible isolates	Resistant isolates
Ceftazidime/Avibactam (CZA) (10/4 µg)	42	0	0
Cephalothin (KF) (30 µg)	22	10	10
Cefuroxime (CXM)(30 µg)	27	12	3
Ampicillin/sulbactam (SAM) (20 µg)	24	0	18
Meropenem (MEM) (10 µg)	41	1	0
Cefoxitin (FOX) (30 µg),	35	0	7
Piperacillin/Tazobactam (TZP) (36 µg)	39	0	3
Ertapenem (ETP)(10 µg)	37	0	5
Cefaclor (CEC)(30 µg)	35	0	7
Cefotaxime (CTX) (30 µg)	37	2	3
Imipenem (IPM) (10 µg)	42	0	0
Aztreonam (ATM) (30 µg)	39	2	1

2.3.1. PCR assays

End-point PCR suggest the presence of the CTX-1-M gene in some of the ESBL-positive strains (Fig. 7) recovered from the annular flume assay. However, further optimization of the amplification conditions is still needed to improve this assessment.

Future perspectives: Optimization of the PCR conditions will be performed in a time frame of one year. Additionally, a qPCR assay will be developed and implemented aimed to increase the sensibility and specificity of the assay.

Figure 7. Agarose gel showing PCR products amplified from ESBL-positive strains isolated from sediments samples at the annular flume (Lanes 4-15). LAD, 1 Kbp DNA ladder; POS, *E. coli* pUCIDT-Kan containing the CTX-M-1 gene (positive control), NEG, *E. coli* pUC19-Amp (negative control).

2.4. CRISPR-Cas technology for restore bacterial antibiotic susceptibility

To evaluate the use of CRISPR/Cas9 technology to restore antibiotic sensitivity in resistant bacteria, 99 potential sequences within the gene CTX-M-1 were identified *in silico* as potential cleavage sites. Later, 10 sgRNAs sequences were designed and their digestion efficiency to CTX-M-1 was tested *in vitro*. The results obtained from the agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig. 8) revealed a high efficiency of Cas9-mediated CTX-M-1 cleavage for the oligo sequences 717forw, 642forw, 132forw, 812forw, 553rev, and 439 rev (Table 3).

Table 3. DNA sequence for sgRNA synthesis, RNA concentrations obtained and efficient DNA cleavage sites within CTX-M-1

Name	Sequence	sgRNA+Cas9 efficiency
717forw	GTGGGGGATAAAACCGGCAG	✓
642forw	CAGCTGGTGACATGGATGAA	✓
132forw	GAATTAGAGCGGCAGTCGGG	✓
812forw	CGTTTCGTCTCCAGCTGTC	✓
553rev	AGAGTTTGCGCCATTGCCCG	✓
233rev	TTTCTTCAGCACCGCGGCCA	✗
348forw	ATTGCGGAAAAGCACGTCTCGA	✗
461rev	CGTTTCGTCTCCAGCTGTC	✗
439rev	GCGAACGCGGTGACGCTAGC	✓
556forw	GAATTAGAGCGGCAGTCGGG	✗

Multiple bands suggest sgRNA is not efficient at DNA cleavage (both supercoiled and linear DNA present)

439rev is efficient

233rev, 461rev and 556forw are not efficient

6 out of the 10 designed sgRNAs demonstrated good efficiency *in vitro*

- 1 – 1 kb ladder
- 2 – Circular plasmid pBR322
- 3 – pBR322 treated with control sgRNA+Cas9
- 4 – Circular plasmid pCTX-M-1
- 5 – pCTX-M-1 with 233rev+Cas9
- 6 – Circular plasmid pCTX-M-1
- 7 – pCTX-M-1 with 439rev+Cas9
- 8 – Circular plasmid pCTX-M-1
- 9 – pCTX-M-1 with 461rev+Cas9
- 10 – Circular plasmid pCTX-M-1
- 11 – pCTX-M-1 with 556forw+Cas9

Figure 8. Representative photograph of an agarose gel showing the band pattern obtained during the evaluation of the CTX-M-1 cleavage efficiency for some of the designed sgRNA by applying the CRISPR/Cas9 technology.

efficiency **Future perspectives:** To test CTX-M-1 cleavage efficiency with the selected sgRNA *in vivo* using the ESBL-positive strains as the target bacteria. These experiences are planning to be completed in a time frame of two years.

3. Datasets

Metadata was stored in folders named with the type of assay, objective of the study or proposed activity. Each folder contains the corresponding files identified by year/mm/dd, including the name of the researcher responsible of data acquisition and a brief description of the procedure employed. All metadata was incorporated at the institutional web repository and linked with keywords for free access and consultancy.

3.1. Dissemination activities

The results will be considered for publication in specialized journals on applied microbiology and biotechnology. Additionally, some of the obtained results will be partially presented at international congresses/conferences. Finally, relevant technical data will be share in networking activities and other dissemination activities (e.g., courses, workshops, seminars, etc.) organized by both the UNESCO-Chair on Sustainability-UPC and the University of Sheffield.

3.2. Career Development

The Co-UDLabs programme has been a remarkable opportunity for researchers of both institution (i.e., University of Sheffield and UNESCO-Chair on Sustainability-Polytechnic University of Catalonia) to strength collaboration with international colleagues. Training in the use of the annular flume at the University of Sheffield was a unique experience to incorporate new technical background that improves the skills and competitiveness of the working groups, with special emphasis in those young researchers at his/her formation stage. Likewise, the project incorporated several topics, disciplines and expertise areas being a proper frame for the exchange of different knowledges.

3.3. Impact

The development of new biotechnological strategies to face the dissemination of microbial pathogens in aquatic environment is a priority. Even more, considering the current climate crisis, increasing globally water stress situation, and the worrying increase in the outbreak of harmful waterborne diseases.

4. Conclusions

The results achieved were satisfactory for a 60-days internship (~45 working days). The most relevant outcome of this preliminary study was to demonstrate the presence of potential microbial pathogens in river Don samples, a recreational river that flows through Sheffield city and receives the impact of uncontrolled wastewater discharges. Likewise, the studies performed in the annular flume were relevant to begin to understand the environmental and health impacts associated with antibiotic-resistant bacteria spreading in aquatic environments due to hydrological perturbations. Additionally, it was possible to obtain relevant data for designing an effective approach based on CRISPR/Cas9 technology to efficiently cleave the CTX-M-1 gene, aiming to restore antibiotic susceptibility in ESBL-producing bacteria. Finally, this experience was highly positive for promoting a closer collaboration between research groups from Spain and UK. Accordingly, further studies have already been planned to collect extra data, finish ongoing experiences, and continue generating knowledge for sharing with the scientific community.

References

Pitout, J.D., Hossain, A., Hanson, D. (2004). Phenotypic and molecular detection of CTX-M-beta-lactamases produced by *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella spp.* J. Clin. Microbiol. 42(12):5715-21. doi: [10.1128/JCM.42.12.5715-5721.2004](https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.42.12.5715-5721.2004)

The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. (2022). Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs and zone diameters. Version 12.0, 2022. <http://www.eucast.org>.

Jun-S, K., Da-H, C., Myeongseo, P., Woo-J, C., Dongwoo, S., Kwan, S. K., Dae-H, K. (2016). CRISPR/Cas9-Mediated Re-Sensitization of Antibiotic-Resistant *Escherichia coli* Harboring Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamases. J. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 26(2),394–401 doi: [10.4014/jmb.1508.08080](https://doi.org/10.4014/jmb.1508.08080)

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Hydraulic Analyses of the
Toronto Exfiltration System (TES)
USFD-04-BURIED-Li**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	USFD-04-BURIED-Li
TA project title	Hydraulic Analyses of the Toronto Exfiltration System (TES)
TA project theme	Investigation on the hydraulics and sediment impacts of an underground sustainable urban drainage system termed Toronto Exfiltration System (TES)
Facility provider	University of Sheffield (USFD)
Facility	Full-scale Buried Cell (BURIED)
TA period	1/06/2022-21/06/2023
Days of access:	60 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution/ Company name	Position	Field	Early professional career	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
James Li	Toronto Metropolitan University TMU	Professor	Academia	No	Canada	M	58
Darko Joksimovic	Toronto Metropolitan University TMU	Associate Professor	Academia	No	Canada	M	5
Celia Fan	Toronto Metropolitan University TMU	Post-doc Fellow	Academia	No	Canada	F	31
Boji Chen	University of Hong Kong	PhD Student	Academia	Yes	Hong Kong	M	13
Bianca Dickel	University of Siegen	MSc Student	Academia	Yes	Germany	F	5
May Chui	University of Hong Kong	Associate Professor	Academia	No	Hong Kong	F	0
Jorge Leandro	University of Siegen	Professor	Academia	No	Germany	M	0
Soheil Gholamreza-Kashi	GHD Canada Inc.	Technical Director	Industry	No	Canada	M	0
William Trenouth	AECOM Canada Inc.	Project Manager	Industry	No	Canada	M	0

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

Implementing sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS) in highly urbanized areas (characterized by pavements/pedestrian sidewalks and compacted buildings) is always challenging due to lack of space, complex maintenance, and high costs. A one-of-a-kind SUDS termed Toronto Exfiltration System (TES), which utilized the pore space of the storm sewer trench was developed and implemented in the early 1990s at a highly urbanized sandy site in Toronto, Canada. Field monitoring results indicate good hydrologic performance after almost 30 years without maintenance. To facilitate the application of TES in other areas, we need to optimize the design and maintenance requirements and address sandy and non-sandy surrounding soil conditions. The project, started in June 2022 and completed in June 2023, included 3 phases: (1) planning of experiments, (2) physical model construction, (3) experiments. In the planning phase, the Team leader worked with Prof. Simon Tait and his laboratory team to design the physical models, the experimental protocol, and the data management systems. Construction of the physical model began in January 2023 and ended, with final sign off by the leader of the user group on 10th March 2023. All hydraulic and sediment experiments were then started and then completed by 21st June 2023. There was a period from 24/4/23 to 5/5/23 when the test model was reconfigured by the technical staff at Sheffield for the clay test series. We collected the TES's full-scaled, steady, and unsteady hydraulic and sediment accumulation data with clay and sandy surrounding soils. Data analyses are being conducted at TMU, and all data will be compiled following the general principles of the EU Open Data Portal. Preliminary observations during experiments indicate that (1) a TES with sandy surrounding soil efficiently retained runoff under the steady and unsteady design conditions; (2) a TES with clay surrounding soil retained runoff up to design storage capacity under the steady and unsteady design conditions; and (3) a fair amount of inflow runoff sediments was trapped within the TES' perforated pipes under the typical 1-hr inflow hydrograph. Dissemination of research results will be in 2024 at international conferences and refereed journals.

Keywords | stormwater management, exfiltration, sewer trench, runoff sediments.

Material and methods

The layout of the physical model and the sensor locations are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The sandy and clay sections of the TES are each about 11 m long. Sensors included (1) 18 wave probes (frequency of 100 Hz) which measured the hydraulic grade lines from upstream manhole to downstream manhole, along the two PVC perforated pipes, and 4 corners of the granular soil cell; and (2) an ADV velocity probe which measured the inflow velocities at different depths of the PVC perforated pipes. Inflows were delivered by an upstream head tank to the upstream manhole and these inflows were measured and logged by a calibrated flowmeter in the facility with a frequency of 10 Hz.

To determine the experimental flow range, a scaled drainage area based on a typical storm sewer length of 100 m (maximum distance between manholes according to Ontario drainage standards) was used to simulate the flow range. Table 1 summarizes the flow conditions of the experiments. Each flow test was repeated three times.

The experimental procedure was (1) set the inflow pump characteristics; (2) initiate the wave probes to record the water levels at various points; (3) start the experiment; (4) measure the inflow velocities (using an acoustic doppler velocimetry) at half and full depths of the PVC perforated pipes; (5) end the steady-state and unsteady-state experiments in accordance to Table 1. All water level measurements were referenced to the bottom of manhole 5 (datum). Sediment experiments were based on (1) 3000 mg/L of sediments distributed as follows: d_{50} 39 microns, d_{90} 105 microns, and d_{10} 6 microns; and (2) a design hydrograph of 4 hrs based on the long-term simulation of flow-duration curves of a typical urban catchment in Canada. Only one test for the clay section and one test for the sandy section. After each test, the amount of sediments trapped at the upstream manhole, the two perforated pipes, and the downstream manhole were collected, weighed, and scanned for particle sizes.

Figure 1. Layout of the physical models (Clay and Sandy surrounding soil).

Figure 2. Sensor plan.

Table 1. Experimental flow ranges

Soil condition	Steady state flows (L/s)			Duration of unsteady state flows	
	Clay*	3	5	10	5-yr 1-hr hydrograph
Sandy#	5	10	15	10-yr 1-hr hydrograph	50-yr 1-hr hydrograph
*Steady inflows to the upstream manhole continued until water overflowed to the upper storm sewers began steady. Unsteady flows continued until the end of 1 hr.					
#Steady inflows to the upstream manhole continued until the water level at the upstream manhole became steady. Unsteady flows continued until the end of 1 hr.					

Description of the Results

For each experiment, data collected in the experiments include (1) water levels at 18 wave probes, (2) inflow characteristics, and (3) velocities at the inlets of the two perforated pipes. Analyses are being conducted by Ms. Patelle Fong and Dr. Celia Fan of TMU, which comprise (1) compilation of all wave probe measurements to 1 s; (2) plotting of hydraulic grades between upstream and downstream manholes, along the two PVC perforated pipes, and the granular soil cell; (3) plotting of the inflow and outflow hydrographs; (4) evaluation of the storage capacity and exfiltration rates of the TES under different inflow conditions; (5) preparation of data files for hydrologic modeling using the US EPA SWMM model; and (6) determination of the amount of sediment trapped inside the two perforated pipes. It is anticipated that preliminary experimental analyses comparing the TES performance (e.g., % peak inflow reduction, % time attenuation between inflow and outflow, % volumetric reduction) will be completed in early 2024, and other analyses (e.g., sediment accumulation inside the two perforated pipes, estimation of long-term average hydrologic performances of TES using calibrated hydrologic models) be completed by later 2024.

Datasets

To share the datasets collected in this project, we will organize the data (using the general principles of the EU Open Data Portal) into the following categories: (1) project information, (2) data characterization, (3) restrictions, (4) data preservation, (5) data publication, (6) ensuring interoperability.

Dissemination activities

Experimental results will be presented at a conference in 2024 (e.g., ICUD 2024, IAHR 2024, or HIC 2024). A technical paper will be submitted for journal publication in 2024. The Team Leader, Prof. Li, will take the lead in presenting research at conferences and journals. An online seminar will be prepared in 2025 for broader dissemination to industries worldwide.

Career Development

This project has allowed all participants to develop their careers further. For senior academic participants, the experience of inter-continental research collaboration will be valuable for long-term networking and research. For junior participants (e.g., graduate students and post-doctoral fellows), the interactions and experiences benefit them in developing their careers. Based on the experimental results and analyses, industrial participants will better understand the TES performance in applications when applying the TES in their designs.

Impact

The TES is an innovative four-seasoned SUDS technology for controlling urban stormwater (runoff and snow melt). It was demonstrated in sandy environments in Toronto, Canada, 30 years ago. This project produced full-scale hydrologic data to quantify TES performance under sandy and clay settings and support the modeling of its performance for various hydrologic conditions for universal application.

Conclusions

The TA project demonstrated a transnational research collaboration among researchers from Europe (U of Sheffield, U of Siegen), North America (TMU), and Asia (U of Hong Kong). The transnational research team worked together to design and construct the full-scaled physical model of TES and conduct the experiments (Team Leader, a TMU's PhD, a U of Hong Kong's Ph.D. Candidate, and a U of Siegen's MSc student). The experimental plan was developed to consider the design challenges from different continents. As a result, the collected data will be useful to participating researchers. Data analysis and dissemination of results are described above.

Acknowledgments

The research team would like to acknowledge the exceptional research support from Prof. Simon Tait, Fabio Muraro, and Christopher Green of the University of Sheffield.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Characterization of thermal properties in
sediment samples from urban drainage
systems with temperature probes
EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	EAWAG-02-HALL-Langeveld
TA project title	Characterization of thermal properties in sediment samples from urban drainage systems with temperature probes
TA project theme	In-sewer processes
Facility provider	Eawag
Facility	HALL
TA period	01/06/2022 – 01/03/2023
Days of access:	40 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Jeroen Langeveld	TU Delft	Professor	Academia	No	The Netherlands	M	0
Manuel Regueiro	Universidade da Coruña	Postdoc Researcher	Academia	Yes	Spain	M	20
Maria Viklander	Lulea Technical University	Professor	Academia	No	Sweden	F	0
Mehwish Taneez	Lulea Technical University	Postdoc Researcher	Academia	Yes	Sweden	F	0
Petra van Daal-Rombouts	Water Board De Dommel	Engineer	Industry	No	The Netherlands	F	0
Jessica Thorsell	Stockholm Vatten AB	Engineer	Industry	No	Sweden	F	0

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

The presence of sediments in urban drainage systems (UDS) has a significant impact on their functionality, requiring effective cleaning strategies to mitigate adverse effects. Monitoring sediment accumulation can offer valuable insights into sediment transport dynamics and system performance. This project tested an innovative solution for measuring sediment depths in sewer systems through temperature monitoring. The methodology involves analyzing temperature time series during dry weather flow conditions to identify harmonic patterns between wastewater and sediment-bed temperatures. The project also focuses on characterizing the thermal properties of sediments, which are crucial for understanding heat transfer processes. For this purpose, a dual-probe heat-pulse (DPHP) system and a commercial sensor were used to accurately measure sediment thermal properties. To validate the temperature monitoring system, laboratory-scale experiments were performed. Results proved the relationship between the sediment depth and thermal properties and the attenuation of the temperature time series. As a main output, this temperature-based system may contribute to the optimization of sewer system operation and cleaning strategies by providing reliable information on sediment depths and properties.

Keywords | Active sensing, Temperature sensors, Sewer sediments, Sediment transport.

Material and methods

A laboratory-scale model was built to reproduce heat transfer processes in sewer pipes. The model consisted of a cylinder 900 mm high and 250 mm in diameter. The model was placed in a temperature-controlled room at HALL facilities. However, it was introduced inside an insulating FOAM case to ensure complete insulation and temperature control.

The experiments were carried out by pouring a layer of sediment at the bottom of the cylinder and a layer of water on top. A water bath was used to develop a temperature-controlled system to simulate daily temperature variations in a sewer pipe. For this purpose, water was pumped from the temperature-controlled system into the water layer of the model. A coil system was built to distribute the temperature uniformly in the water layer. Figure 1 summarizes the experimental setup performed in the HALL facilities at Eawag (Dübendorf, Switzerland).

Figure 1: Photo (left) and scheme (right) of the experimental setup.

The lab-scale experiments replicated the water temperature variations in sewer pipes, which show marked daily patterns that depend on basin activities, habits, and network operation strategies. Tests were carried out by combining passive and active temperature measurements:

- **Passive temperature measurements:** the objective was to measure the temperature time series in the system (water layer, interface, and sediment-bottom) caused by the daily temperature pattern. The sediment thickness can be determined by analysing these time series. Three daily cycles (72 hours) were simulated for each test to avoid the subsequent influence of the initial conditions on the analysis of the temperatures.
- **Active temperature measurements:** corresponding to the DPHP system. Heat pulses were introduced into the sediment layer to measure the thermal properties of the sediments. An active measurement was programmed every 24 hours.

A total of 24 experiments were carried out as a result of the combination of the following parameters:

- 4 sediment thicknesses: between 30 and 160 mm.
- 6 sediment mixtures:
 - **Inorganic-sand.** Washed sand with a grain size distribution between 0.315 – 0.5 mm was used as inorganic sediment.
 - **Gully pot.** Two samples were collected from different locations: Eawag (industrial area, Dübendorf) and Wipkingen (residential area, Zürich).
 - **Stormwater tank.** A sample of sediments was collected from a stormwater tank in Zürich.
 - **Sewer pipe.** Two samples were collected from two different main collectors in Zürich.

Description of the Results

The experimental model reproduced daily patterns in sewer pipes under dry weather conditions. As a result, temperature series were obtained. We could differentiate two types of results:

- Measurement of the sediment thermal properties.

The sediment thermal properties could be characterized from the active temperature measurements with the DPHP system. For this purpose, the response to heat pulses introduced by a heater were measured with a temperature sensor. The response time and the temperature gradient are related to the thermal conductivity and the volumetric heat capacity of the sediments (Figure 2a). Furthermore, the measurements performed with the DPHP system were compared with a commercial sensor, obtaining similar values between the two systems (Figure 2b). To the authors' knowledge, this is the first time that thermal properties in UDS sediments were measured, because of the analysis of heat transfer processes for measuring sediment depths. As secondary novelty, relationships between the sediment thermal and physical

properties were also found, which would allow this method to be used, for example, to estimate the organic matter content of sediments.

Figure 2: Temperature gradients derived from the DPHP system measurements (left) and comparison of thermal diffusivity measured with the DPHP system and the TP01 commercial sensor for different sediment samples (right).

- Measurements of the sediment depths.

The harmonic characteristics, defined from the amplitude and phase, were computed from the temperature series in the water layer and at the bottom of the sediment layer to measure the sediment depth. Figure 3 shows how the sediment-bed temperature series attenuates as a function of sediment depth. The greater the sediment depth, the greater the attenuation and phase difference between the temperature series in the water layer and at the bottom of the sediment. Data driven models, which were previously developed by members of the user group, were applied to measure the sediment depths. These measurements were compared with sediment depths measured with a graded system. Figure 4 shows the comparison of sediment depth measurements between the temperature-based system and the graded system. As future developments, an uncertainty analysis is planned to establish the accuracy of the measurements obtained with the temperature-based system.

Figure 3: Temperature time series in water-sediment interface (blue line) and sediment-bed (brown line) for tests on sand (hsed1, top-left), gully pot (hsed2, top-right), stormwater tank (hsed3, bottom-left), and sewer pipe (hsed4, bottom-right) sediments.

Figure 4: Comparison of sediment depths measured with the temperature-based and the graded systems for different sediment samples.

Datasets

The TA Project Coordinator and the user visitor plan to publish the database and a descriptive report of the experimental campaign on ZENODO under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license, which allows anyone to download and read the report free of charge. Furthermore, the dataset may be reused and cited, provided that the original published version is cited. These conditions allow maximum use and publication of the work and at the same time ensure that the authors receive appropriate credit.

The dataset will include data from laboratory experimental campaign where the variations of water and sediment bed deposits temperature were measured, and intermediate heat-pulses were introduced to both measure the sediment thermal properties and sediment depths (time series format). Dataset will also include mechanical, thermal, and volumetric moisture content properties of sediments. The measured parameters, including the units, are listed below:

- Processed temperature time series and sensor calibration process: T [°C]
- Sediment characteristics: Mass moisture content (%), Volumetric moisture content (m^3/m^3), Organic matter (%), Density (kg/m^3) (wet, wet-bulk, dry-bulk), Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}/\text{m}^\circ\text{C}$), Volumetric heat capacity ($\text{J}/\text{m}^3/^\circ\text{C}$).

Dissemination activities

Initial dissemination activities included two articles in peer-review journals. Finally, the user group members decided to publish the results in a peer-review journal and to communicate the results as part of an oral presentation at the NOVATECH conference, 3rd-7th July, Lyon (France). The journal publication is currently under development focused on the main results of the experimental campaign and the validation of data driven models based on the analysis of heat transfer processes in sewer systems.

Career Development

The experimental work developed within this TA Project contributed to the development of the postdoctoral research of the visiting researcher. In addition, an international working group was established, bringing together professionals from academia and industry. Therefore, the TA Project was developed from both academic and commercial perspectives, addressing the needs of the UDS sector in terms of sediment management.

Impact

From a commercial point of view, the results showed the potential use of temperature-based systems for monitoring sediment accumulation in sewer systems. Thus, optimal inspection and cleaning strategies could be performed based on observations rather than periodic operations. This would reduce costs and the risk of combined sewer overflows (CSO) during rainfall events caused by sediment accumulation (social and environmental impact). From an academic point of view, monitoring sediment accumulation may be complemented with hydrodynamic measurements to develop more accurate sediment transport models in sewer systems. This would lead to optimal sewer system designs from a sediment management point of view, and the development of digital twin models.

Conclusions

The TA Project was developed in the HALL facility, hosted by the Eawag, where a lab-scale model was built inside a temperature-controlled room. The project granted 40-day access to a postdoctoral researcher, on behalf of a user group composed of international experts from the academia and industrial of urban drainage.

The performance of temperature-based systems for measuring sediment depths in sewer pipes were evaluated. As an intermediate step, the thermal properties of inorganic and UDS sediments were measured. The results showed the relationship between the attenuation of the water and sediment-bed temperature series, and the sediment thermal properties and depths. Consequently, the initial objectives were fulfilled.

Further steps will include the publication of the database in an open access repository, the publication of an article in a peer-review scientific journal and the communication of the results in an international conference. Future commercial and scientific perspectives include the implementation of these systems for the optimization of sediment management in sewer systems and other UDS infrastructures.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Investigation of the rehabilitated waste water
pressure pipes in response to pressure surges in
operation IKT's Large Test Facility (LTF)**

IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	IKT-01-LTF-Verhulst
TA project title	Investigation of the rehabilitated waste water pressure pipes in response to pressure surges in operation IKT's Large Test Facility (LTF)
TA project theme	In-sewer processes
Facility provider	IKT
Facility	LTF
TA period	23/03/2023 – 11/08/2023
Days of access:	41 working days ¹

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Danny Verhulst	VLARIO /Aquafin	Engineer	Industry	No	Belgium	M	4 ^{2,3}
Dirk de Witt	Aquafin	Engineer	Industry	No	Belgium	M	3 ^{4,3}
Luc Verhuest	Aquafin	Engineer	Industry	No	Belgium	M	1 ^{5,3}
Patrick Willems	KU Leuven	Professor	Academia	No	Belgium	M	- ³
Markus Gillar	IKT	Senior Research Fellow	Academia	No	Germany	M	NA
Thomas Brüggemann	IKT	Senior Research Fellow	Academia	No	Germany	M	NA

¹ Including test times and times for the construction, modifications, bug fixing and test runs. The removal of the test setup in 08/23, 09/23 and 10/23 is not included.

² Visit at 26/08/2022 (1 day), 01/06/2023 -02/06/2023 (2 days) and 29/06/2023 (1 day)

³ Due to time restrictions of staff of VLARIO, Aquafin und KU Leuven, many of these meetings were conducted online.

⁴ Visit at 06/08/2022 (1 day), 01/06/2023 -02/06/2023 (2 days)

⁵ Visit at 06/08/2022 (1 day)

Summary

Pressure surges and fluctuations in sewage pressure pipes can be caused by the operation of the pumps. However, the pronounced pressure surges that can frequently occur are an often-unrecognised cause of damage [1], according to [2]. In order to avoid pressure surges, appropriate measures can be included in the planning of pressure sewers (including pressure surge calculations for longer pipelines, design measures such as the arrangement of aeration and deaeration fittings at high points) and their construction. However, in the past, the pressure surge phenomenon was often not adequately addressed. As a result, consequent damage can be observed in older pressure sewer pipes. In the case of trenchless rehabilitation of pressure sewer pipes using relining, the fundamental question is how the host pipe-liner combination behaves under pressure surge loadings and to what extent it can withstand this. This applies at least to the case where a rehabilitated pipeline is expected to still be subjected to a slight pressure surge load despite the retrofitting of aeration and deaeration valves. There are currently no reliable statements on this because common calculation approaches and currently available publications on scientific investigations are aimed at the host pipe and the situation of an undamaged sewage pressure pipe, but not at a rehabilitated pipe.

This project therefore investigated for the first time the extent to which pressure surge loads can have an influence on a pipeline rehabilitated using a liner. Therefore, an experimental setup was used in IKT's Large Test Facility (LTF) consisting of a wastewater pressure circuit system. A defined section with a length of app. 8 meters was rehabilitated with a so called close-fit-liner (polyethylene of high density), the system was subjected to a range pressure surge loads that can occur in wastewater pressure pipes. After the trials the results are compared to those of a common simulation programme.

The tests discussed in this report could in principle be modelled well with the simulation programme SIR 3S.

Errors and deviations here are mainly due to the following factors:

- Determination of the actual pressure wave velocity in the system,
- Determination of the real valve characteristic curve,
- Proportions of degassed air in the negative pressure area,
- Consideration (modelling) of transient friction approaches.

Keywords | Wastewater pressure pipes, pressure sewer rising mains, pressure surges, host pipe – liner

Material and methods

In IKT's Large Test Facility (LTF) an experimental setup was built on a scale of 1:1. The experimental setup (see figure 1 and figure 2) consisted of a pressure line circuit system (1), made out of steel pipes with an internal diameter of 206.5 mm (DN 200 – 219,1 x 6,6 mm) and a pump (2) with a maximum flow of approx. 155 l/s. Details concerning the pump are shown in figure 4) The lower area of this system was covered with soil. Pressure surges were to be generated with a fast-closing pneumatic slide valve (9). It was installed in the front area of the pressure pipe, directly in the area of the first gradient. Sliders (2, 4, 9, 10, 14), a pressure box (15), a flow meter (6) and pressure sensors (7, 13) were installed to control the system and perform measurements. Inspection openings (8) were installed, so that an inspection by CCTV was possible. Buffers (5) should absorb the vibrations caused by the pressure surges to protect the pump. The section of the test set-up relevant for the comparative simulations is shown in Fig. 1. It is the area between the quick-acting valve and the tank. The length between the quick-closing valve and tank is approx. 18265 mm. The tank contains a volume of water during the tests of approx. 0.97 m³ and a volume of air of about 0.89 m³.

The following height specifications refer to the axis of the return line:

- The liquid level in the tank is: 6220 mm
- The quick-closing valve is at (approx.): 5200 mm
- The lowest level of the section to be simulated is: 3340 mm

Figure 1: side view of the experimental setup.

Figure 2: upper part of the experimental setup with quick acting valve colored orange-black (left), pump with slider and buffer (right)

Furthermore, a defined area (cf. figure 3) of the steel pipeline was rehabilitated with a so-called close-fit liner made of PE-HD (SDR17, 194 x 12.8 mm).

Figure 3: section relevant for simulations

The characteristic curve of the centrifugal pump is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Characteristic curve of the pump

According to the characteristic pump curve, the max. pressure (zero head) at max. frequency converter output is 25 m (2.5 bar).

In the "pressure surge" test mode, the pressure can be increased by water flowing briefly into the tank when it is closed. The amount of water flowing corresponds to the maximum steam volume that is formed when steam is formed downstream of the quick-acting shut-off valve.

The test field was mapped in the SIR-3S program system⁶ as follows (cf. Figure 5):

The components relevant for the hydraulic design such as pumps, valve characteristics, bends, pipe diameter, material and roughness as well as the tank are programmed in analogue to the experimental data.

⁶ SIR3S Version 9.0 - Lizenzgeber: 3S Consult GmbH, Osteriede 8-10, D-30827 Garbsen

Figure 5: Hydraulic model of the experimental set-up in the programme system SIR-3S

The experimental program is divided into three areas. In a first test run, the system was operated over the entire performance range of the pump and the pressure conditions in the corresponding measuring ranges were recorded. Further presentation of these tests will be omitted.

The second test series comprised tests in which a so-called non-return valve was installed. These tests essentially served to introduce a negative pressure into the rehabilitated pipeline section and to maintain it for a longer period of up to 96 hours. In particular, this was a test for the installed rehabilitation system with regard to its resistance to negative pressure. However, these tests are not the focus of the investigations into pressure surge behaviour and are also not presented further below.

For the third series of tests, the non-return valve was removed from the pipe so that a pressure surge behaviour that could normally occur in pressure pipes could be generated in the section of pipe outlined below (cf. Figure 6).

In each test, the quick-acting shut-off valve (see area "V", Fig. 6) is closed within 0.8 s. Thereupon the pump - due to the flow rate control - automatically runs at maximum speed, against the closed valve. It is then opened again (within approx. 1 s).

Figure 6: schematic layout of the test set-up, tests without non-return valve (RSK removed!)

Furthermore, the mean pressure wave propagation velocity has to be determined. Due to the close-fit-liner in the steel host pipe, the elasticity of the pipe material is increased, instead of the higher stiffness to be assumed for steel (modulus of elasticity: approx. $2.11 \cdot 10^{11}$ N/m²), the stiffness is reduced by the liner and the fact that it does not lie evenly against the steel pipe everywhere.

The pressure wave velocity is determined from the transit time t of the pressure signals and the axial length L between the quick-closing valve and the container:

$$A = 4 \cdot L / t$$

Mean pressure wave propagation velocity before cavitation: 397 m/s

Mean pressure wave propagation velocity after cavitation: 301 m/s

The pressure wave velocity decreases due to the degassing of air when cavitation occurs. The higher value should therefore be used for the calculations. All the tests given here were carried out with the container open.

Description of the Results

During the tests a rapid closing, a pressure surge is initially generated in front of the quick-acting valve (area "V", see Fig. 6).

Downstream of/behind the closed valve, the water initially continues to flow, creating negative pressure until spontaneous evaporation occurs. Due to the counterpressure in the container (atmosphere when the container is open or slight overpressure when the container is closed), the flow direction in the area "R & PE" between the closed valve and the container reverses and the steam bubble collapses at the closed valve. This causes a condensation shock, which - comparable to a pressure surge - results in fast and high pressure amplitudes (cf. also figure A3).

The flow rate in this case was about 40 l/s, the corresponding fluid velocity is approx. 1.2 m/s.

Figure 7: Pressure curve of the two sensors P1 (downstream) and P2 (upstream, behind the quick-acting valve) after closing the slider

At low flow velocities of approx. 0.3 m/s (flow rate of 10 l/s) no steam cavitation occurs, the pressure amplitudes (maxima and minima) run harmoniously and with approximately constant reflection time (cf. Figure 8).

Figure 8: pressure curves of the two sensors after closing the valve, having a low velocity of 10 l/s

If we compare the graphs and phenomena at different flow velocities (i.e. flow rate 100 l/s, approx. 3.0 m/s), we find that both pressure surges and condensation surges increase in intensity and thus pressure (cf. Figure 9).

Figure 9: pressure curves of the two sensors after closing the valve with a high flow rate of 100 l/s

The experimental results presented above are supplemented in the following by the simulation results. The two examples with both low and high flow velocities are used as examples.

Compared to the test with a flow rate of 10 l/s (cf. Figure 8), it can be seen from figure 10 that in the simulation a short-time vapour pressure level is reached at the first pressure sensor P1.

In fact, some air is initially outgassed before evaporation occurs.

Figure 10: simulated pressure curves, low flow rate of 10 l/s (to be compared to figure 8)

The pressure drop is thus somewhat lower in reality; subsequently, the first overpressure at position P1 is also somewhat dampened in reality ($p_{\max, \text{experimental}} = 2.5 \text{ bar}$; $p_{\max, \text{calculated}} = 3.7 \text{ bar}$).

In the further course, the experimentally determined temporal damping of the pressure amplitudes is considerably higher than in the simulation; this is essentially due to the real proportions of free air as well as the stationary pipe friction approach used in the modelling - a considerable improvement in the calculation would be achieved by taking into account transient friction approaches and degassed air proportions.

This effect can also be seen in the following simulations with steam cavitation (compare figure 11 with regard to figure 9): As long as steam cavitation still occurs, the calculated temporal damping is larger, as soon as the system is single-phase again, the pressure oscillations are only slightly damped compared to the measurement.

Figure 11: simulated pressure curves, high flow rate of 100 l/s (to be compared to figure 9)

At position P2, the amplitudes ($p_{\max, \text{experimental}} = 2.7 \text{ bar}$; $p_{\max, \text{calculated}} = 2.9 \text{ bar}$) agree considerably better (no calculated cavitation).

The following results are obtained in the tests with steam cavitation: In the experiment with 40 l/s, the calculated and measured pressure peaks are in very good agreement at location P1 (cf. Figure 12): $p_{\max, \text{experimental}} = 7.6 \text{ bar}$; $p_{\max, \text{calculated}} = 7.5 \text{ bar}$. Somewhat higher deviations can be seen at point P2 ($p_{\max, \text{experimental}} = 6.2 \text{ bar}$; $p_{\max, \text{calculated}} = 6.6 \text{ bar}$).

Figure 12: measured(left) and simulated (right) pressure curves, higher flow rate of 40 l/s

Furthermore, it can be seen that the vapour bubble in the measurement is axially somewhat larger than the calculated one, since in the calculation the vapour bubble collapse occurs earlier (at $T_{\text{experimental}} = 1.2$ s compared to the calculation $T = 1.0$ s).

This is due to the mathematically simplified modelling of the friction in the system as well as to the proportions of air dissolved in water that outgas when the pressure drops.

This physical fact has a stronger effect on the timing of the vapour bubble collapse at higher stationary fluid velocities (cf. Figures A5 & A55: Vapour bubble collapse at $T_{\text{experimental}} = 2.0$ s vs. $T_{\text{calc}} = 1.4$ s).

Another deviation between experiment and calculation results from the effect of the "numerical diffusion" (figures 9 and 11).

Here, at the point P2 (blue curve progression in the simulation), comparatively many cavitation impacts are calculated that do not occur in reality (compared with experiments, green curve progression).

The programme therefore calculates many - numerically caused - cavitation impacts, since the vapour pressure with $p = 0.002$ bar is close to the absolute zero level and is "mathematically" very often reached by numerical errors in individual time steps. This then leads to the occurrence of steam hammering in each case. This phenomenon also increases with increasing stationary fluid velocity.

In all calculations, a decisive factor is the pressure loss characteristic of the valve. This can usually only be measured very inaccurately in the throttling range (valve opening positions $< 25\%$), but on the other hand it is precisely this range ($0\% < \text{position} < 25\%$) that is decisive for the occurrence of pressure surges and cavitation impacts.

Datasets

The data collected during the tests are stored as TDMS files. A TDMS file is a data file stored in National Instruments (NI) Technical Data Management Streaming (TDMS) format. It contains simulation or measurement data recorded by National Instruments software such as LabVIEW and DIAdem. TDMS files also store descriptive information, including procedure, test fixture, sensor information and author. In addition, TDMS_INDEX files are created automatically and together with TDMS files. The index files contain information about the associated TDMS file referenced by the application that opens the TDMS file. This allows TDMS files that store large amounts of data to be opened more quickly.

IKT will transfer files and data on an OA Zenodo site and using via Co-UDlabs dissemination channels.

The dataset will include data from laboratory experimental campaign where the tests with different flow rates and pressures were measured.

Dissemination activities

Various dissemination activities were already carried out during the experimental trial period. For example, articles were placed on social media to launch the trials. During the trials an external visiting group (German Municipals and authorities) came to lab and discussed with IKT and Vlarion/Aquafin about the tests and the practical experiences regarding pressure surges. Furthermore, it is planned to produce an article for a peer-reviewed publication based on this report in cooperation with all project participants to communicate the results.

Beyond this a presentation of results at some symposia and a presentation in the context of lectures on rehabilitation methods for wastewater pipes at the University of Leuven is planned

Career Development

The scientific staff of IKT involved in the project as well as the engineers of VLARIO and Aquafin were able to gather important knowledge in the course of the tests, which is of importance for further professional work.

Impact

VLARIO and Aquafin have gained new knowledge through the project. This knowledge should benefit the wastewater companies in Belgium in their daily work (e.g. in calculation of pressure surges and their impact on rehabilitation, in connection with the preparation of tender documents for the rehabilitation of wastewater pressure pipes, in quality monitoring and assurance). Basically the results of the investigations are intended to provide manufacturers of lining processes in particular with information on the actual stresses that act on the products in the worst case. The results of the project can thus build up corresponding market pressure and open up development potential. If they want to remain competitive on the market, the manufacturers of lining processes for wastewater pressure pipes will be forced to an increased extent to improve their products in accordance with the requirements or to develop new products in a targeted manner after completion of the investigations.

Conclusions

The liner survived all tests without damage. After the tests, the results were compared with those of a common simulation programme. The simulation with its calculation approaches could be approximately adapted to the tests. However, the results of the investigation also showed that any errors and deviations that occurred were due to factors that should be taken into account as follows:

- Determination of the actual pressure wave velocity in the system, not knowing precisely interactions between host pipe and lining system
- Determination of the real valve characteristic curve,
- Proportions of degassed air in the negative pressure area,
- Consideration (modelling) of transient friction approaches.

These potential influencing factors need to be identified in detail in further investigations.

Further steps will include the publication of the database in an open access repository, the publication of an article in a peer-review scientific journal and the communication of the results in conferences and in the context of lectures at the University of Leuven.

-
- [1] Thomsen, J.; Morrison, R.; Sangster, T.; Hayward, P.: Inspection Guidelines for Wastewater Force Mains. Water Environment Research Foundation (WERF), Alexandria (Virginia, USA), edited by Jason Consultants LLC, Columbus (Ohio, USA), 2010.
 - [2] Roscher, H.; Rammelsberg, J.; Braun, T.; Brussig, P.; Ahrens, J.; Stiller, B.; Riege, U.; Wildermuth, R.; Gerdes, K.; Zech, H.; Weigt, R.; Kleinau, A.; Rose, A.; Gaebel, W.; Sommer, J.; Möller, W.; Schlosser, H.-U.; Böhme, A.; Kröfges, W.: Sanierung Städtischer Wasserversorgungsnetze - Strategien, Verfahren, Fallbeispiele der Rehabilitation, Verlag Bauwesen, Berlin, 2000.

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
Assessment of Inspection Tools for
Rising Mains (AIR)
IKT-02-LTF-Beenen.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	IKT-02-LTF-Beenen
TA project title	Assessment of Inspection Tools for Rising Mains (AIR)
TA project theme	Assessing the capabilities of several (commercially) available inspection tools for use in sewer rising mains.
Facility provider	IKT – Institute for Underground Infrastructure
Facility	Large Test Facility (LTF)
TA period	03/04/2023-23/08/2023
Days of access:	40 working days ¹

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Ton Beenen	Stichting RIONED	Program manager	Industry	No	NL	M	1 ^{2,3}
Alma Schellart	Sheffield University	Senior Lecturer	Academia	No	UK	F	- ³
Irene Scheperboer	IKT – Nederland	Senior Research Fellow	Academia	No	NL	F	NA
Markus Gillar	IKT	Project manager	Academia	No	GE	M	NA
Iain Naismith	IKT – UK	Senior Research Fellow	Academia	No	UK	M	NA
Thomas Brüggeman	IKT	Project leader	Academia	No	GE	M	NA

¹ Including test times and times for the construction, modifications, bug fixing and test runs. The removal of the test setup in 08/23, 09/23 and 10/23 is not included.

² Planned to visit at 07/06/2023, but was prevented and replaced by a colleague from Stichting RIONED.

³ Due to time restrictions and long travel distance, all steering group meetings were conducted online.

USERS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Alex Towlson	Bristol University	PhD student	Academia	Yes	UK	M	6 ⁴
Joanna Watts	Sheffield University	PhD student	Academia	Yes	UK	F	3 ⁵
Siegbert Scheihing	Xylem	Project manager	Industry	No	GE	M	2 ⁶
Thomas Peitzmeier	Xylem	Project leader	Industry	No	GE	M	2 ⁶
Berry Krijbolder	ROSEN group	Business Line Manager	Industry	No	NL	M	2 ⁷
Patrik Rosen	ROSEN group	Head of New Venture	Industry	No	GE	M	1 ⁸
Tim Visser	Acquaint	Operational manager	Industry	No	NL	M	1 ⁹
Adriaan Otte	Acquaint	Lead Engineer	Industry	No	NL	M	1 ⁹
Carsten Möller	ROSEN group	Project team lead	Industry	No	GE	M	1 ¹⁰
Jürgen Wölke	ROSEN group	Process professional	Industry	No	GE	M	1 ¹⁰
Jonas Credner	ROSEN group	Data analyst	Industry	No	GE	M	1 ¹⁰

Note: The steering group was responsible for the project organization. The user group consisted of the steering group members, representatives of the Dutch pressure sewer network owners and representatives from the visiting companies and institutions. The days of visit were used by companies and institutions specialized in in-line pressure sewer inspections. Groups of end-users - Dutch, Belgian and UK pressure sewer network owners and operators – have also visited the lab at several occasions. These visits were meant to update the end-users about the project progress and offered means to provide input from practice on the project.

⁴ Visit at 24-26/04/2023 (3 days), and 30/05/2023-02/06/2023 (3 days)

⁵ Visit at 03-05/05/2023 (3 days)

⁶ Visit at 22-23/05/2023 (2 days)

⁷ Visit at 12/07/2023 (1 day) and 23/08/2023 (1 day)

⁸ Visit at 12/07/2023 (1 day)

⁹ Visit at 03/08/2023 (1 day)

¹⁰ Visit at 23/08/2023 (1 day)

Summary

Sewage pressure pipes are undoubtedly particularly critical structures in the sewerage system. In the event of a failure, exfiltration, flooding and the associated risks for people and the environment are to be expected. In order to minimize the risk of damage or operational failure of these pipes, regular condition assessments are required. However, the inspection of wastewater pressure pipes poses a problem for many operators. A conventional CCTV condition assessment or leak test as with gravity pipelines is usually not possible due to certain boundary conditions (e.g., lack of access openings, bends, full or partial filling of the pipelines and gradient). New, innovative inspection techniques are required that provide meaningful results on the condition of the sewage pressure pipe. In recent years, some promising inspection techniques have been (further) developed. Within the framework of this TA project, selected innovative inspection techniques have been examined in a test set-up for their performance and application limits. A test setup was constructed in the large-scale test facility of IKT, consisting of a system of wastewater pumps and pressure pipes, with typical damage patterns to be detected by the inspection techniques. Different pipe materials were installed in sections of the test setup to determine their influence on the different inspection techniques.

Keywords: Sewer pressure lines, Inline inspection techniques, Damage scenarios, Pipe materials.

Material and methods

Test set-up

The design of the test set-up is depicted in Figure 1. The test set-up comprises steel and PVC pipe segments with a diameter of DN 300 in the inspection range. The entrance and exit of the inspection pipe line are constructed by a combination of a Y-piece (horizontal entrance) and a T-piece, to make the pipe line accessible to the different devices that are to be tested. Both the Y-piece and the T-piece have a diameter of DN 300. The wall thickness of the steel pipe segments of DN 300 is equal to 7.1 mm, the wall thickness of the PVC pipe segments is equal to 15 mm. The pump installation and DN 200 steel pipe segments in the backloop are reused from a finished project. The system is filled with drinking water. The pressure in the system originates from the pressure of the water inflow into the system and the pressure induced by the air inlet. The maximum pressure in the system should not exceed 2.5 bar due to the relatively low tensile strength of the plexiglass pipe segment. The flow velocity could easily be adapted between 0 – 2.0 m/s.

Figure 1: Experimental setup

The damaged pipes are prepared from new pipe segments which are equipped with unique damages scenarios for the purpose of this project. In this way, the damages are clearly defined and circumstances are equal for all participants. The applied damages in the test set-up are adapted to damage scenarios commonly found in real pressure mains, as discussed with Dutch and British network owners and network operators during online workshops. A summary of the discussion on the most important damage scenarios that are relevant for the chosen materials is provided in the next inset. The applied damage scenarios consist of leakages of increasing size from 0.3 – 7 mm diameter. Some of these leaks are located inside a sand box, which changes the acoustic signals. Furthermore, outside corrosion is simulated by creating small areas of wall loss with increasing depth and by applying larger areas of wall loss. Other damage scenarios are an ovality, surface damage in the form of scratches, incrustation and a gas pocket.

Main conclusions workshop operators on damage scenarios in pressure pipes

For steel pipes, corrosion is one of the main processes leading to damage and may found both internally and externally. This might result in holes of different size and shape (pitting corrosion) or a reduction of wall thickness (inside or outside). Local thickening, due to deposits, can occur with all materials. Ovalization is particularly important for plastic pipes, but may occasionally be found in steel pipes. For plastic pipes, damage in the form of scratches of different shape and size is also found at both the inside and the outside of the pipes. In pressurized segments, gas pockets are severe events. They result in an increased power demand for the pumping station and the pipe wall at the gas pocket is prone to corrosion (in the case of steel or concrete). These gas pockets often manifest at culverts or downward slopes, where sharp vertical bends are present. Damage to the joints manifests itself primarily through angular displacements greater than designed. Axial or radial displacements of tube sections are of less importance.

Test procedure

Academic and commercial parties were invited to inspect the pipe line. An overview on the participants is presented in the next section. The academic parties were able to use the pipeline for research purposes. The commercial parties were only able to inspect the experimental pressurized pipe line as they would for an in-situ pipe line. Details about the entrance and exit points, as well as the internal diameter, wall thickness and pipe material were shared with the inspection firms beforehand, as would be the case for in-situ inline inspections. The damaged parts of the test set-up were covered with foils, so as to provide a blind test for each company, see Figure 9. The foil was applied such that it was impossible to look underneath it to the applied damage scenarios at any time. The participants could perform as many inspection runs as they wish. The flow conditions could be adapted easily in between the inspection runs. The applied damage scenarios were shared with the inspection companies only after they submitted the inspection report, for development purposes.

Before starting the inspections, product specifications were collected for the participating devices. These are presented in three tables in Annex A. Table A.1 comprises the area of application of the device, such as the pipe material it can be used for, geometrical restrictions and pressure and flow velocity requirements. Table A.2 summarizes the expected capabilities of the academic devices regarding damage detection. Table A.3 summarized the (publicly) claimed capabilities of the commercial devices regarding damage detection. For each inspection device, the input for Tables A.1-A.3 were retrieved from the corresponding firm or institutions by means of data sheets and (online) meetings. The data was collected before the inspections started, to set the baseline against which the results are being compared.

Participants

The committed parties were the University of Bristol with an air-coupled ultrasonic array device, the University of Sheffield with the PipeBots acoustic sensor, Acquaint with their device Acquarius, ROSEN group with two complementary devices (pilot tools, under development), and Xylem with SmartBall. The inspection techniques that were part of the project were at different stages of development. The two universities were participating with pilot products that are in an early research stage. Both projects focus on the development of the application of the sensor in wastewater systems. The design of the robotic platform to support these sensors fell outside the scope of these research projects. As can be expected in such a stage, the products were not yet robust and stable. Participation in the projects offered a unique opportunity for the researchers for a testing environment and is very helpful for further development. Acquaint is a young, Dutch company specializing in water supply and wastewater pipe line inspection techniques. The Acquarius tool looks like a cleaning pig, but is equipped with ultrasonic sensors for damage detection. ROSEN group participated with techniques that are in a later stage of development, but not yet commercially available. ROSEN group is an established company in inspection techniques in oil and gas pipes. For several years they have been extending their technology for use in wastewater and water supply pipe lines. Xylem is an established water technology company that develops inspection techniques for wastewater and water supply pipelines. SmartBall is a compact, free-swimming tool specialized in detecting leaks and gas pockets and mapping the pipeline network. PipeDiver is an inspection tool that is customized to different materials. It can be used in a pipe diameter starting from DN 400 and is therefore too large for use in this project. Details of the PipeDiver inspection tool are presented in this section, although independent testing of the features was not possible.

Description of the Results

Academic participants

Pipebots air-coupled ultrasonic device – University of Bristol

Some results generated by the Pipebots air-coupled ultrasonic device are shown in Figure 2. The novelty of the air-coupled acoustic sensor is in the generation of 3D-images of detected defects. At the test loop at the IKT, two clear defects were detected by the Pipebots ultrasonic sensors. The leak at the fifth steel pipe segment of 3mm at the 6 o'clock position is clearly visible in Figure 2a. The round shape was detected correctly. Sizing was not provided for this technique; the location was predicted successfully. The incrustation at the third PVC pipe segment was also detected successfully, although the size was overestimated, see Figure 2b. Other defects were not detected. The results presented in Figure 8 show the advantage of the imaging technique. The data gathered in the pipeline, is presented in such a way that the client is able to easily understand the data. The inspection results are less of a 'black box' to the client, which makes the data-analysis procedure more transparent. Currently, the technique is not yet robust and stable and further development is required before this technique could be applied for inline inspections.

Figure 2: 3D-images of the results of detected damages at test loop by the pipebots acoustic sensor

Pipebots acoustic sensor – University of Sheffield

The Pipebots acoustic sensor has detected two features in the downward slope of steel pipe segments. The first is a joint at 3 m distance, the second is a leak between 4 - 5 m distance. The joint was merely detected using the hydrophone and using this knowledge, some deviations in the accelerometer data could also be identified at the same location. It is concluded that improvements in the reliability of the method might enable replication of this capability of the accelerometer. The leak was identifiable as background noise measurement for both the hydrophone and accelerometer. The main conclusion of the researchers after conduction inspections at the test loop at IKT, is that the sensor used was not robust enough for further testing and required work on the deployment method to ensure repeatable results. This conclusion is shared by the authors of this report.

Commercial participants

The results of the commercial participants are compared against the real damages, thereby considering the specifications of the inspection techniques. An overview of the detected anomalies and their characteristics is provided in Table 2. For each commercial participant, the ability to detect and size the defect is depicted. The results are anonymized, as the companies have not yet given their approval for publication of the results. In Table 2, the green color indicates that the defect was detected and sized accurately. The yellow color indicates that the defect is detected, but the sizing or position detection was not within the specified limits. The blue color indicates that a defect has been detected that was not intended to be present, but the presence of the event is likely. However, their presence and sizing could not be verified. The red color indicates that a defect has not been detected (false negative) or a wrongfully detected event (false positive). The dark grey color indicates that these defects cannot be detected with the chosen technique.

Especially anomalies at the PVC joints are among the unverifiable defects (blue color). The longitudinal joint displacements are not intended at the PVC joints, but are a result of the fitting of the test loop inside the test pit. Sizing of these displacements could not be verified as they are only observable from the inside. The ovalities at these joints were not planned as well, but are a consequence of the used steel clamps, which unwittingly might have ovalized the pipe segments instead of clamping them evenly throughout the circumference. Based on the inspection results of Company 1 and Company 2 combined, it is very likely that at joint J22, J23 and J23 a longitudinal displacement at the joint was present, as both companies detected this type of anomaly at these locations.

Table 2: an overview on the results of the inspections. The green color indicates that the defect was detected and sized accurately. The yellow color indicates that the defect is detected, but the sizing or position detection was not within the specified limits. The blue color indicates that a defect has been detected that was not intended to be present, but the presence of the event is likely. The red color indicates that a defect has not been detected (false negative) or a wrongfully detected event (false positive). The dark grey color indicates that these defects cannot be detected with the chosen technique.

Pipe defect	Pipe segment / pipe joint ID	Acquaint - Acquarius	ROSEN group	Inspection results	Xylem - SmartBall
Leak, 6 o'clock, 3 mm	P4	-	Possible deviation, 9 o'clock	(Entrained) air	
Leak, 3 o'clock, 7 mm	P4	Leakage in pipe segment	Leak	Unknown deviation	
Ovalisation, 6% or 18 mm	P5	Ovalisation, 6,44%	Dent, 12 o'clock, 350x200x18 mm	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, \varnothing 7 mm, 1 mm deep, 12 o'clock	P6		-	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, \varnothing 7 mm, 2 mm deep, 9 o'clock	P6		-	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, \varnothing 7 mm, 4 mm deep, 6 o'clock	P6		-	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, \varnothing 7 mm, 6 mm deep, 3 o'clock	P6		-	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, 11-12 o'clock, 200x200x3 mm	P7	10-12 o'clock, 260x232x4,5 mm	11-12 o'clock, 200x200x4 mm	(Entrained) air	
Wall loss outside, 2-3 o'clock, 200x200x3 mm	P7	2-4 o'clock, 280x174x3,7 mm	3-4 o'clock, 200x200x4 mm	(Entrained) air	
Leak, 6 o'clock, 3 mm	P8	-	-	(Entrained) air	
Leak, 3 o'clock, 7 mm	P8	Leakage in pipe segment	Leak	(Entrained) air	
Tap	P10		-	(Entrained) air	
Gas pocket, \pm 2 m	P12 - P17	-	Gas pocket, 2 m	??	
	P18		Unknown, (tap?), 6 o'clock		
	J20	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 12 mm			
		Joint ovality, 3%			
Scratch, outside, 1x3,4x500mm, 12 o'clock	P21	Scratch, outside, 1,23x520 mm, 12 o'clock			
	J21	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 5 mm	Joint displacement, radial, 8 mm		
		Joint ovality, 4,5%			
		Joint leakage			
Scratch, outside, 3x3,4x50mm, 9 o'clock	P22	Scratch, outside, 2,92x510 mm, 9 o'clock			
	J22	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 14 mm			
		Joint Ovality, 4,5%	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 16 mm		
Incrustation, 400x90x15 mm, 6 o'clock	P23	Incrustation, 389 mm, 6 o'clock	Debris		
	J23	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 80 mm	Incrustation, 400x100x15, 6 o'clock		
		Joint ovality, 4,5%	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 66 mm		
			Ovality, 6%		
			Debris		
Scratch, outside, 5x3,4x50mm, 6 o'clock	P24	Scratch, outside, 5,61x490 mm, 6,1 o'clock			
	J24	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 22 mm			
		Joint ovality, 4,5%	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 16 mm		
Scratch, outside, 7x3,4x50mm, 3 o'clock	P25	Scratch, outside, 7,16x520 mm, 3 o'clock			
	J25	Joint displacement, longitudinal, 21 mm	Debris		

Both companies reported the displacement at joint J23 to be significantly larger than at the other joints. However, the location and size of the other longitudinal or radial joint displacements and ovalities at the PVC joints are not in correspondence between the two reports and are therefore less reliable.

Table 2 shows that the inspection techniques are capable of detecting a large variety of defects and most of them are able to provide sizing within specified limits. The access to the test facility was a unique opportunity for early-career researchers to further develop new types of sensors for application in waste water. In this way, the project enhanced innovation in the field of in-line inspections of waste water pipelines.

Datasets

The data collected in this project consists of written inspection reports, generated by the participating companies and institutions. These reports will be made available in .pdf format, which allows everyone to read the inspection results.

Dissemination activities

Various dissemination activities were already carried out during the experimental period. Several groups of operators, from the Netherlands, Belgium and the UK, have visited the lab and took active part in identifying the main damage scenarios that should be applied to the test set-up. Each time one of the inspection companies or institutions performed their inspections at the test facility, a social media post was launched to keep the public informed on the progress of the project.

A report will be prepared in English and Dutch with an extensive elaboration on the test set-up, the test procedure, the participating techniques and the results. This report is meant to be spread under the community of network operators and network owners. This report will be prepared on behalf of the project manager, stichting RIONED. Additionally, the results will be communicated during several events held for the community, such as the Persleidingenevent (scheduled at December 6, 2023, organized by stichting RIONED and STOWA), and the RIONED-dag (yearly event on waste water management, organized by stichting RIONED). Dissemination activities in the UK will be prepared by Iain Naismith (IKT), who also updated the UK-users regularly during the duration of the project.

The scientific work conducted by the universities of Sheffield and Bristol will be published as scientific articles, written by Joanna Watts (University of Sheffield) and Alex Towlson (University of Bristol). The experiments undertaken as part of the TA-project, will be incorporated in these works.

Career Development

Two early-career professionals from the university of Bristol and Sheffield took this project as an opportunity to enhance their research into sensor techniques for wastewater pressure pipes. The project offered a unique opportunity for them to test the developed sensors in a pipeline environment for the first time. This was especially valuable since they would not know the damage scenarios beforehand and they were faced with the challenges of data analyses of an unknown environment for the first time. Participation in this project meant a large step for the development of their skills in data analyses and identifying the difficulties in bringing the sensor into a pipeline environment.

Impact

The impact of the project is two-fold. Firstly, there is a large interest from the field of network operators to find out the current possibilities in pressure pipe inspection techniques. The techniques are relatively expensive and the operators need assurance that this investment turns into profit in terms of valuable information on the state of the pipeline. This project gives an independent proof of concept of the techniques. On the other hand, the project offers the opportunity for the inspection companies to manage the expectations of the clients and educate their clients on the possibilities and limitations of the techniques.

Conclusions

The TA-project was developed and run in the IKT-LTF, where a 1:1-scale model was built into. Two scientific institutions – the University of Sheffield (UK) and the University of Bristol (UK) – and three commercial parties – Acquaint (NL), ROSEN group (GE) and Xylem (CA) – took part in the project. The design of the test set-up was discussed with pressure sewer network owners and operators from the Netherlands and the UK by means of online workshops and meetings. The test facility was opened for inspection during a period of 95 working days, of which 14 have been used for carrying out inspections and additionally 4 days have been used to host end-users to visit the test facility, provide feedback on the project and receive an update on the project progress. A total number of 50 end-users have visited the test facility during the access period.

A comparison of the inspection reports provided by the commercial parties and the actual damages present show that the inspection techniques are capable of detecting a large variety of defects and most of them are able to provide sizing within specified limits. The access to the test facility was a unique opportunity for early-career researchers to further develop new types of sensors for application in waste water. In this way, the project enhanced innovation in the field of in-line inspections of waste water pipelines.

Further steps will include publication of the project results and dissemination of the results through reports in Dutch and English, oral presentations and scientific publications (by the universities of Sheffield and Bristol). A follow-up project is already initiated by stichting RIONED for further insight into the capabilities of inspection techniques in field situations. Also, the user group is investigating the options for a more permanent inspection pipeline, with a longer length. This would be helpful in monitoring the progress of the development in in-line pressure sewer inspections.

Annex A: Specifications of the participating inspection devices

Table A.1: An overview on the area of application of the inspection technologies for pressure sewers of companies that have participated in this project.

	Acquarius (Acquaint)	(ROSEN)	SmartBall (Xylem)	PipeDiver (Xylem)
<i>Materials</i>				
Cast iron	yes	yes	yes	yes
Steel	yes	yes	yes	yes
Metal with lining	yes	yes	yes	yes
Glassfibre reinforced plastic	yes	yes	yes	no
PVC	yes	yes	yes	no
HDPE	yes	yes	yes	no
Concrete	yes	yes	no	yes
Asbestos cement	yes	yes	no	no
<i>Geometry</i>				
Pipe diameter (mm)	200 - 1600	250 - 1800	>150 ¹ or >300 ²	400 - 3050 ⁴
Maximum diameter change	30% - 50% ^{3,4}	50% ⁵	-	300 mm ⁴
Wall thickness (mm)	≥ 1.5 ⁴	2.5 - 30	-	5.1 - 12.7
Maximum lining thickness (mm)	20	3	-	12.7 ⁴
Minimum diameter entrance (mm)	200	1D or 500 mm ⁷	100	300 ⁴
Minimum diameter exit (mm)	200	1D or 500 mm ⁷	100	300 ⁴
Minimum workspace above entrance (m)	2 × length robot	2D	1.2	1.5
Minimum workspace above exit (m)	2 × length robot	2D	4	1.5
Maximum change of direction (°)	90	180	180	90
Minimum bend radius (°)	1D	1D	-	1D
Maximum rise/descend (°)	90	90	90	90
Length robot (mm)	Variable ³	1.5D	180	2300-4400
Diameter robot (mm)	1D	0.3D	180	Variable ⁴
<i>Hydraulics</i>				
Maximum inner pressure (bar)	40	20	34.4	20
Minimum recommended pressure difference (bar)	0.2	0	1	-
Maximum flow velocity (m/s)	0.5	2.0	1.8	0.45 - 0.9 ⁴
Maximum flow velocity for position detection (m/s)	0.5	2.0	0.9 ⁸	-
Maximum flow velocity for extraction (m/s)	0.2	-	1 - 1.8 ³	-
Minimum flow velocity (m/s)	0.35	0.2	0.15	0.15
Minimum flow velocity for vertical offset (m/s)	0.35	0.2	0.46	-
<i>Other</i>				
Maximum temperature (°C)	45	45	70	40
Maximum inspection duration (hour)	20 ⁸	20 ⁹	24	15-30 ¹⁰
Pressure sewer can remain in service during inspection	yes ¹¹	yes ¹¹	yes	yes

¹ For metal pipes without lining

² In all other cases

³ Diameter dependent

⁴ Material dependent

⁵ Reduction of the largest diameter in the pipe

line.

⁶ Each diameter requires separate inspection

⁷ Minimum value of 1D or 500 mm.

⁸ Easily extended

⁹ Dependent on material and measurement tech-

nique

¹⁰ Including video inspection

¹¹ During insertion the pressure and flow should be turned off.

Table A.2: An overview on the detectable pipe characteristics and damage scenarios for the inspection technologies for pressure sewers of the research institutions that have participated in the project. For each characteristic or damage scenario, the possibility of detection is indicated (yes/no). These sensors are currently under development. Therefore, accuracy of sizing is not yet determined for these devices.

	Ultrasonic array device (U-Bristol)	Pipebots Acoustic sensor (U-Sheffield)
Pipe characteristics		
xyz-location	yes ¹	no
Pipe features (valves/outlets/joints etc.)	yes ²	yes
Damages		
Corrosion: wall thickness reduction	yes	yes
Corrosion: pitting	yes	no
Corrosion: distinguish between internal and external	no ³	yes
Gas pocket	NA ⁴	ND
Incrustation	yes	yes
Leakage	yes	yes
Deformation	yes	no
Broken bars/wires	yes ⁵	no
Surface damage (plastic)	yes ³	no
Displaced/rotated joint	yes/yes	yes/no
Sulphate attack (Asbestos cement and concrete)	no	no
Leaching (Asbestos cement)	no	no

¹ Relative to entry-point, not connected to GIS or map

² Joints always, other features only when they protrude the pipe by at least 2 mm

³ Technique only detects damage at the inner surface

⁴ Currently only available for empty and unpressurized pipes

⁵ Only when concrete cover is removed or bar is protruding into the pipe

Table A.3: An overview on the detectable pipe characteristics and damage scenarios for the inspection technologies for pressure sewers of the companies that have participated in the project. For each characteristic or damage scenario, the possibility of detection is indicated (yes/no), followed by the probability of detection and/or accuracy of sizing. For ROSEN group, the accuracy is always given at 90% certainty.

	Acquarius (Acquaint)	(ROSEN)	SmartBall (Xylem)	PipeDiver (Xylem)
Pipe characteristics				
xyz-location	yes	yes	yes	yes
Accuracy	0.5 m	0.5 m	Variable ¹	Variable ³
Wall thickness	yes	yes	no	yes
Accuracy	0.5 mm	0.4 mm		Variable ³
Probability of detection	10 - 95 % ²	90%		Variable ³
Pipe features (valves/outlets/joints etc.)	yes	yes	yes ⁴	yes
Probability of detection	Variable ⁵	90%		Variable ³
Damages				
Corrosion: wall thickness reduction	yes	yes	no	yes
Minimum detectable depth	0.5 mm	0.5 mm ⁶		30% wall loss
Minimum detectable length / width	10 mm	25 mm		75 mm
Accuracy of sizing length / width	4 mm	10 / 25 mm		Variable ³
Probability of detection	10 - 95 % ²	90%		Variable ³
Corrosion: pitting	yes	yes	yes ⁷	yes
Minimum detectable depth	0.5 mm	0.5 mm ⁶	-	40% wall loss
Minimum detectable length / width	10 mm	25 mm	0.1 L/min	25 mm
Corrosion: distinguish between internal and external	yes	yes	NA	no
Gas pocket	yes	yes	yes	yes ⁸
Minimum detectable size	10 mm	3.75% of perimeter	Small	Variable ³
Accuracy of sizing	4 mm	5% of perimeter	Medium	Variable ³
Incrustation	yes	yes	yes ⁸	yes
Minimum detectable size	10 mm	25 mm		Variable ³
Accuracy of sizing length / width	4 mm	10 / 25 mm		Variable ³
Probability of detection	10 - 95 % ²	90 %		Variable ³
Leakage	yes	yes	yes	no ⁹
Minimum detectable size	TBD	2 mm	0.1 L/min	
Accuracy of sizing	TBD	TBD	High	
Probability of detection	10 - 95 % ²	90%	Variable ³	
Deformation/ovality	yes	yes	no	yes
Minimum detectable deformation	> 0 %	2 mm		Variable ³
Accuracy of sizing	TBD	0.8 mm		Variable ³
Probability of detection	100 %	90 %		Variable ³
Broken bars/wires	yes	yes	no	yes
Minimum detectable number of broken wires	1	1		5
Surface damage (plastic)	yes	yes ¹⁰	no	NA
Minimum detectable depth	TBD	-		
Accuracy of sizing	TBD	-		
Horizontally / radially displaced joint	yes	yes	yes ⁸	yes ⁸
Minimum detectable displacement	15 mm	3 mm		Variable ³
Accuracy of sizing	4 mm	1 mm		Variable ³
Rotated joint	yes	yes	no	no
Minimum detectable displacement	0.25 °	3 mm		
Accuracy of sizing	0.25 °	1 mm		
Sulphate attack (Asbestos cement and concrete)	yes	yes ⁹	NA	NA
Minimum detectable depth	10 mm	TBD		
Accuracy of sizing	4 mm	TBD		
Leaching (Asbestos cement)	yes	yes ⁹	NA	NA
Minimum detectable depth	0.5 mm	TBD		
Minimum detectable length / width	10 mm	TBD		
Accuracy of sizing	4 mm	TBD		

¹ Depending on the amount of reference points

² Depending on pipe diameter, selected number of sensors and defect/feature size

³ Depends on pipe specifications and inspection conditions

⁴ Indirect measurement

⁵ Depending on coverage ratio, dirt, defect size and operator's wish

⁶ For a defect size > 50 mm and a minimum remaining wall thickness of 2.5 mm

⁷ Can be detected as leakage

⁸ In certain scenarios

⁹ Currently under development

¹⁰ Depending on defect size, location, orientation and operator's wish

Co-UDlabs

**BUILDING COLLABORATIVE URBAN
DRAINAGE RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES**

**Transnational Access report:
In situ SUDS modelling
INSA-01-OTHU-SUDS-Fuchs.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

REPORT DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Transnational Access Project Information	
TA project acronym	INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs
TA project title	In situ SUDS modelling
TA project theme	Impact of climate change (heavy rains) on SUDS operation
Facility provider	INSA Lyon
Facility	OTHU-SUDS
TA period	30/08/2022-14/04/2023
Days of access:	3 working days

AUTHORS

Name	Home institution / Company name	Position	Field	early professional career?	Country of work	Gender	Days of visit
Lothar Fuchs	ITWH	Team Leader	SME	NO	Germany	M	5
Katharina Fuchs	ITWH	Eng.	SME	YES	Germany	F	5
Gislain Lipeme Kouyi	INSA Lyon	Full Professor	Academic	NO	France	M	-

LICENSE

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Summary

The hydraulic and hydrological modeling of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) represents a major challenge due to the complexity of considering the processes involved. The modeling of these processes requires the definition of a certain number of parameters, in particular those allowing the simulation of the spatio-temporal evolution of the soil moisture. In order to improve these models, experiments were conducted on a swale equipped with a flowmeter at the outlet. Soil moisture sensors were installed at different depths. An original device for the irrigation of the swale was developed to simulate runoff water linked to rainfall of different return periods. The inflow and soil moisture were measured over a week. The objective is to use these data to improve the capacity of the models to simulate the evolution of the volumetric water content in the soils of SUDS, when extreme events due to climate change occur. Horton model, water balance equation and various empirical functions (power and sigmoid functions) were tested to represent the variation of soil moisture. Results show that Horton model demonstrated the capacity to simulate the storage change in the swale (using the averaged values of performed measurements). The sigmoid function seems better than the power law to capture the variation of the soil moisture according to the depth in the soil.

Keywords | climate change, modelling, SUDS, soil moisture.

Material and methods

First, the calibration of the total of 24 soil moisture sensors TEROS 10 (Meter Environment) was carried out on the basis of the soil samples in the laboratory. Likewise, the "sprinkler system" was built before the tests were carried out (Fig. 1). The inflow of the swale is done by means of slotted PVC-U pipes DN 100. These pipes were slotted every 10cm with a slot length of 70mm and a slot width of 6mm.

Figure 1. Sprinkler system

The irrigation system was built as a frame of PVC-U pipes at the edge of the swale. The slotted sections were installed along the length of the swale so that the inflow would occur at the side of the swale as in a natural occurrence. The profiles were closed along the short side of the swale. The individual PVC-U pipes were connected to each other with sockets, push-in joints and angles. The inflow to the sprinkler system was provided by the local tap system. For this purpose, the nearest hydrant was connected with hoses. The connection of the end hose to the system was made via a PVC-U pipe DN100 which ended in a flow meter with DN70.

Before starting the tests, the soil moisture sensors were installed in the swale. The layout diagram of the sensors is given in Figure 2. The soil moisture sensors were installed at different depths. The depths vary between 0.035m and 0.395m, whereby the sensors were installed at the edge of the swale close to the surface and those in the middle were installed deepest.

The flow meter was connected to the rest of the system via a T-profile and thus formed the inflow to the sprinkler system. The individual connections between the various parts were made using sleeves and connecting brackets.

Figure 2. Layout of sensor installation

Description of the Results

During the experimental period, the following data were recorded:

- Volumetric water content (soil moisture) of the respective sensors
- Flow rate at the measuring chamber (separated by average flow rate per period of 120 s and maximum flow rate within this period)
- Flow rate by means of tilt measurement as total flow rate in the measuring period of 120 s
- Electrical conductivity of the water and water temperature
- Water level in the trough after performing the first test (5 ,0 l/s)
- Measurement of the total flow during the second test (2.5 l/s)
- Weather data from nearby weather station (1 minute resolution):
 - Air temperature on average and humidity in percent
 - Wind speed (Average, Maximum and Minimum during the period) and wind direction
 - Solar radiation
 - Precipitation (measurement by means of tipping device)
 - Evaporation (measurement by monitoring the water level by means of a container of size 0.6 m x 1.2 m)

In Figure 3, an example of the measured soil moisture during the two conducted experiments can be seen.

Broadly, the recorded data show that the sensors measured different volumetric water contents depending on the depth. The sensors installed at lower depths tended to measure higher volumetric water contents than the deeper sensors.

Figure 3. Variation of soil moisture over the time

Datasets

Dataset Information	
Activity	Transnational Access
Dataset ID	IN-SITU-SUDS-MODELLING-ITWH-INSA_2022_08
Dataset title	Measurement of soil moisture in SUDS
Data sources	Data from OTHU-SUDS facility campaign where the variations of water level, inlet and outlet flow rate, soil moisture are measured when water level is varied after soil saturation (time series format). Dataset includes also data from weather station (assessment of evapotranspiration)
Content	Raw and processed water level, inlet flow rate, outlet flow rate, soil moisture time series: h [m], Inlet and outlet flow rates [L/min], Soil moisture content [% v/v]
Formats	csv

ITWH and INSA share the ownership of dataset. INSA will make all data available to Co-UDLABS members after 2 years of embargo.

Dissemination activities

A poster was presented during last NOVATECH 3-7 of July 2023 in Lyon. A Master report is also available. At least two additional publications are planned. The first one will focus on data analysis and the discussion on processes behind the soil moisture evolution. The second one will address the validation of ITWH home-made numerical tools using soil moisture spatio-temporal distribution.

Career Development

A team leader, an engineer and a MSc student were involved. The TA project reveals the leadership of the engineer. She supervised the Msc student and plan to strengthen her skills on infiltration modelling in SUDS under heavy rain conditions.

Impact

The conducted TA work significantly impacts the commercial and scientific aspects of Itwh. Indeed, the collected data are dedicated to make the disseminated tools more reliable. The simulation of SUDS under heavy rain is challenging. Thanks to the TA program Itwh is able to face this challenge.

Conclusions

The experiments went very well. The set-up had to be adjusted during the first saturation of the swale. The inlet hose was not firmly connected to the inlet to the sprinkler system via cuffs at the beginning. In addition, the slope of the slotted pipes had to be adjusted because the initial water pressure was not high enough to provide a constant supply to the swale until the end. After these adjustments, the subsequent tests went smoothly.

The resulting data from these tests were evaluated and analyzed as part of a master thesis. The aim is to publish the results together after sufficient analysis. The possibility to conduct the experiments at INSA and also the personal contact form a very good basis for further cooperation, also for possible later projects.

Annex 2. Survey on 'Co-UDlabs Transnational Access Programme: quality and process evaluation'

Co-UDlabs Transnational Access Programme: quality and process evaluation

Dear Participants in the Co-UDlabs' Transnational Access (TA) programme, thank you again for your involvement in our initiative! This short survey will allow you to evaluate and share your opinion on specific and key features of our TA programme. Your replies will be essential for us to improve the service and support we provide to visiting user-groups, as well as to finetune our research installations for more and more teams to access them, for free and for innovative and groundbreaking research! Thank you in advance for your time and consideration.

Section 1

1. Before we begin, please select your TA project from the following list:

< List of all TAs >

Section 2

Before the TA project

This section enquires about the preparation of the TA proposal and communication between user-groups and facility providers during the global TA call and before the actual beginning of the TA projects and experiments.

2. How did you learn about Co-UDlabs and our Transnational Access programme?

3. Do you think the information on the TA provided on the Co-UDlabs website and social media was adequate and useful?

< > Yes

< > No

< > I was not involved in the proposal preparation process

4. What was your main motivation to apply for a TA with Co-UDlabs?

Please select as many answers you wish and feel free to add in the 'Other' field.

< > Research tasks and objectives

< > Business and/or commercialisation opportunities

< > Accessing the Co-UDlabs and UDS communities

< > Other:

5. Do you think the TA call granted participants enough time to draft their proposals and prepare the required documentation?

Please rate from 1 (too little time) to 5 (plenty of time to draft). This question is not mandatory, if you were not involved in the proposal preparation, please consider skipping it.

1/5 rating

6. How would you rate the process between the end of the call and the communication of the results to applicants?

Please choose one among the following options

< > Faster than expected

< > Fair

< > Slower than expected

< > I was not involved in this phase of the process

Section 3

During the TA project

This section collects feedback on the TA process while the projects were being implemented.

7. How would you rate communication with the facility provider to prepare the access and agree on the User Facility Agreement?

Please rate from 1 (very difficult) to 5 (very effective)

1/5 rating

8. How valuable do you think the Data Management Plan procedure was throughout the TA project?

Please rate from 1 (very cumbersome) to 5 (very useful)

1/5 rating

9. Please feel free to submit any feedback specifically on how the Data Management Plan tasks have worked throughout your TA

Any recommendations or suggestions to make this process more effective and useful to visiting user-groups will be very welcome.

10. How would you rate the provision of allowance and accommodation (availability, quality, reimbursement procedures, etc.) to visiting staff?

Please rate from 1 (uncomfortable) to 5 (excellent)

1/5 rating

11. How would you rate the quality of the installations you had access to?

Please rate from 1 (inadequate) to 5 (excellent)

1/5 rating

12. How would you rate the quality of the scientific support provided on-site?

Please rate from 1 (inadequate) to 5 (excellent)

1/5 rating

Section 4

After the TA project

Finally, this section will let us know more about your opinion after the TA was completed. This is going to be valuable as we plan and define the features and regulations of our second TA call.

13. Do you think that your project in the Co-UDlabs research infrastructure was ultimately successful?

< > Yes

< > No

< > Other:

14. Was your team able to produce new original data to be made available in open access thanks to your TA project?

< > Yes

< > No

< > Other:

15. Do you plan to academically publish the results of your research and/or experiments at the Co-UDlabs research infrastructure?

< > Yes

< > No

< > Other:

16. Do you think you will apply for another TA opportunity at the Co-UDlabs 2nd TA call?

The 2nd TA Call will close in October 2023.

< > Yes

< > No

< > Other:

17. Do you think that taking part in the TA programme has enhanced the prospect of future collaborative work within the Co-UDlabs network and partnership?

< > Yes

< > No

< > Other:

18. Finally, we would appreciate if you could take the time to provide recommendations and suggestions to improve Co-UDlabs' TA programme, or comment on your own experience with the programme

Please feel free to share any opinions that may help us improve our initiative and make the TA experience even better for more researchers from around the world.